

Strategies and approaches for just, transformative change

Deliverable D3.2 Report

Tasks T3.1 – T3.2 – T3.3 – T3.4 – T3.5

Publish Date: M36/November 2025

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Funded by
the European Union

Technical References

Project Acronym	BIOTraCes
Project Title	<i>Biodiversity and Transformative Change for Plural and Nature Positive Societies</i>
Project Coordinator	Stichting Wageningen Research
Project Duration	December 2022 – November 2026

Deliverable No.	D3.2
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work Package	<i>WP3 Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes towards Nature-Positive Societies</i>
Task	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4, T3.5
Lead beneficiary	UGOT
Contributing beneficiary(ies) ²	UGOT, WR, CES, BC3, MRU
Due date of deliverable	November 2025 (M36)
Actual submission date	28 November 2025

- 1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

- 2 UGOT = University of Gothenburg/School of Business, Economics and Law/Human Geography Unit, Sweden
 WR = Stichting Wageningen Research/Environmental Research/Team Biodiversity and Policy, the Netherlands
 CES = Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra, Portugal
 BC3 = Basque Centre for Climate Change, Spain
 MRU = Mykolas Romeris University/Environmental Psychology Research Centre, Lithuania

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
V0.9	14 November 2025 (project consortium review version)	UGOT (lead), BC3, WR, CES, MRU	T3.1: Julia Neidig, Liam Ó Riada T3.2: Katarina Haugen, Marie Stenseke T3.3 Socrates Schouten, Judith Westerink, Rosalie van Dam T3.4: Luciane Lucas dos Santos, Fernanda Branco Belizário T3.5: Audra Balundé Edited by Katarina Haugen (UGOT)
V1.0	28 November 2025 (final version)	UGOT (lead), BC3, WR, CES, MRU	T3.1: Julia Neidig, Liam Ó Riada T3.2: Katarina Haugen, Marie Stenseke T3.3 Socrates Schouten, Judith Westerink, Rosalie van Dam T3.4: Luciane Lucas dos Santos, Fernanda Branco Belizário T3.5: Audra Balundé Edited by Katarina Haugen (UGOT)

Summary

The BIOTraCes project explores how biodiversity initiatives can support just, transformative change toward nature-positive societies. Work Package 3 (WP3) analyses the entire set of nine European case studies of local biodiversity initiatives in high impact sectors for biodiversity loss: agriculture and food production/consumption, maritime/aquatic living sources, forestry and urbanisation. The **aim** of the WP3 cross-case analysis of the BIOTraCes case studies is to identify strategies and approaches that may support transformative change towards strengthened biodiversity, grounded in principles of social equity. The cross-case analyses focuses on different dimensions of change: leverage and scaling/amplification (T3.1), overall strategic pathways for biodiversity initiatives (T3.2), strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation and dialogue (T3.3) just and effective governance (T3.4) and biodiversity interdependencies of the Sustainable Development Goals (T3.5). WP3 analyses the experiences from the diverse case studies through the lenses of the respective tasks to understand what helps or hinders transformative potential and how local action connects with wider systems. The cross-case analysis is attentive to the BIOTraCes 'PEPE' principles: Pluralising, Empowering, Politicising and Embedding.

The cross-case analysis departs from a **literature review** that provides a conceptual backbone concerning transformative change and how it can be achieved through different strategies and approaches. Unlike conventional incremental reform, transformative change entails deep, non-linear shifts in societal values, structures and behaviour that address the root causes of biodiversity loss, e.g. questioning prevailing economic and cultural models. The 'wickedness' of environmental challenges, including biodiversity loss, make them particularly challenging to address, placing high demands on proposed solutions, policy and governance frameworks. The transformative governance literature explores how institutions, frameworks and actors can support or hinder change. Among the various approaches identified in previous research, one is particularly in line with the BIOTraCes case studies: the Small Wins approach, which focuses on how many place-based/local, individually minor initiatives can be upscaled and contribute to accumulated wider systemic change. Furthermore, we outline the conceptual tools of Theories of Transformative Change and Pathways that describe how collective, networked agency can – unlike isolated actors – shift systems over time. We also explore different forms and meaning of upscaling.

Case study research builds general knowledge from in-depth analysis of specific cases but often remains context-bound. **Cross-case analysis** addresses this by identifying broader patterns and themes across diverse settings. Here, *strategies* serve as the main unit of analysis to manage diversity and extract context-sensitive insights without oversimplification. The deliverable draws on rich empirical data collected through informant interviews, consortium focus groups discussions and a survey with the case study research teams as well as their written replies in structured monitoring forms. The material is explored through descriptive quantitative analysis and qualitative thematic analysis. The latter mixes inductive and deductive features to identify patterns of strategies, governance mechanisms and leverage points across the diverse case studies.

Task 3.1 identifies leverage points and amplification processes across the case studies, focusing on how local biodiversity initiatives can strengthen and expand their transformative potential. Leverage points are understood as the social, political, economic, ecological, or cultural factors that facilitate transformative change. They range from shallow (new practices and material processes) through deeper shifts in governance structures, to the deepest changes in worldviews, imaginaries and values that reconnect

people and nature. Rather than 'upscaling', the concept of 'amplification' is adopted, highlighting the relational dimensions of transformation such as trust-building, learning, and co-creation. Three forms are distinguished: amplifying *within* – strengthening or stabilising local initiatives; amplifying *out* – spreading innovations to other contexts; and amplifying *beyond* – influencing policy, governance, or societal values. Analysis was based on interviews, consortium focus group workshops, and monitoring forms, coded in NVivo to identify patterns of leverage and amplification. Results reveal leverage points operating from practical to value-based levels and show that many BIOTraCes initiatives already exhibit amplifying dynamics, demonstrating how local biodiversity actions can scale their transformative impact across systems and society.

Task 3.2 analyses the strategies pursued in the case studies based on thematic analysis of interviews, focus group discussions and monitoring forms (coded in MAXQDA). The main topics are governance settings and institutional context; strategy development and implementation; overarching approaches; target groups; subject matter and focus; methods; challenges and difficulties; transformative potential; and observed outcomes of the strategies and approaches. Strategic approaches range from informal, emergent practices to highly structured, theory-informed frameworks, reflecting differences among key stakeholders as well as differences pertaining to geographical and institutional context. Many strategies entail adaptive planning, combining long-term visions with short-term flexibility, reflexive learning, and collaboration across sectors and scales. The strategies employed often focus on information, knowledge and awareness. Networking, emphasis on social relationships (e.g. trust-building) and co-governance models often support gaining and maintaining momentum and legitimacy. However, limited funding and short-term project cycles constrain continuity and long-term strategising. Overall, effectiveness appears to depend less on any single strategy than on the capacity to combine planning with adaptability, reflexivity, and persistence.

Task 3.3 focuses on 'co-strategies': participatory and interactive approaches with transformative intent. Using an interpretivist approach, strategies are derived from interviews, workshop and monitoring forms. The data are coded against categories representing the features of a strategy (actor, activity, resources, target group, context, occasion, purpose, and outcome) and against the PEPE principles. In addition, exploratory quantification is conducted in R. The analyses rendered 71 co-strategies across the cases. Six activity types recur: advocacy, co-building, encounters, engaged research, multi and public engagement. Actor roles are discussed in terms of networks – focused networks consisting of peers, broad networks consisting of multiple stakeholder types, research partner-societal partner collaboratives, and local/regional government. PEPE tagging reveals a prevalence of Pluralising and Empowering over Politicising and Embedding. The Pluralising + Empowering combination is most common. Outcomes typically include openings for dialogue, new/stronger networks, and partial procedural embedding, whereas structural change is limited. Five meta-strategies are identified: creating spaces for engagement; scaling out practices; building/consolidating networks and initiatives; demonstrating practices; and participatory action research.

Task 3.4 explores how gender equity, intersectionality, and justice can strengthen biodiversity governance based on the case studies across Europe. It analyses data from the project consortium reflections, interviews, and workshops to identify structural barriers and emerging practices for inclusive governance. The findings reveal that decision-making remains dominated by established actors, while marginalised groups – especially women, migrants, Roma, and minorities – rarely exert any significant influence. Their participation

is often symbolic, constrained by bureaucracy, fragmented policies, and a lack of trust. Despite these barriers, promising practices emerge: co-governance experiments, plural knowledge systems, creative engagement, and trans-local networks fostering collaboration and learning. These demonstrate that transformation depends on redistributing authority, valuing local and gendered knowledge, and embracing flexibility.

The analysis underscores that effective biodiversity governance must integrate justice, inclusiveness, and gender sensitivity at all levels – European, national, and local – and link technical and social dimensions of regeneration. Empowerment, long-term institutional support, and recognition of care and reciprocity are of essential importance for transformative governance.

Task 3.5 investigates how biodiversity interacts with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) across case studies. The data have been analysed using descriptive statistical methods. A consortium-wide survey captured how the research teams for the cases perceive and apply the SDGs in their respective biodiversity contexts. The findings show that biodiversity underpins the achievement of most SDGs, sustaining food, water, livelihoods, and resilience. Also, biodiversity recovery depends on progress in goals related to equality, education, and governance. Social justice, trust, and inclusive institutions are essential foundations for ecological regeneration. The SDGs were viewed as both a source of leverage and as a limitation. While it is a common policy language and advocacy tool it can often be seen as too abstract, technocratic, or used for greenwashing. Analysis through the PEPE principles showed strongest alignment with Pluralising (valuing diverse knowledges) and Empowering (inclusive participation), while Politicising and Embedding were weaker and largely confined to local practice. Overall, the study concludes that biodiversity is the systemic enabler of sustainable development, and transformation must be justice-oriented, context-specific, and rooted in local agency.

The joint, concluding discussion – covering all tasks and chapters – highlights the four 'PEPE' principles – pluralising, empowering, politicising, and embedding – as essential dimensions of transformative biodiversity governance. *Pluralising* emerges as the foundation for change, expanding the range of actors, knowledges, and values involved in decision-making while addressing the power asymmetries that limit genuine participation. *Empowering* builds on this foundation by strengthening the agency and legitimacy of marginalised actors, enabling them to co-create governance processes grounded in reciprocity and care. *Politicising* highlights the inherently political nature of transformation, challenging dominant paradigms and creating spaces for contestation, accountability, and shared responsibility. *Embedding* links these dynamics by ensuring that biodiversity innovations become integral to social, economic, and institutional routines; anchored in everyday practices and aligned with long-term governance frameworks. Together, the PEPE principles demonstrate that transformative change depends on relational, context-sensitive processes that connect local initiatives with broader institutional and policy structures. Achieving this requires more than isolated innovation: it calls for dialogue across scales, institutional reflexivity, and enduring commitment to inclusivity, justice, and ecological integrity.

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The interpretations and views presented in this report reflect collaborative research within the BIOTraCes project. They represent the perspectives of diverse participants engaged in participatory action research and should not be taken as a single, unified position of all partners or stakeholders. Readers may encounter interpretations that do not necessarily align with their own perspectives, as the report seeks to reflect the plurality of worldviews and experiences captured in this project.

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1 Introduction

Katarina Haugen (UGOT) and Socrates Schouten (WR)

The BIOTraCes project rests firmly on its case studies, each of which provide in-depth understanding of biodiversity innovations/interventions set in specific geographical and institutional contexts and involving a variety of stakeholders. Like many case studies, despite their high individual value, the potential for theory development and broader knowledge per individual case study is somewhat limited (Pahl-Wostl et al., 2021). Therefore, BIOTraCes includes overarching analysis of the case studies in the form of synthesis and cross-case analysis (During et al., 2023).

BIOTraCes Work Package (WP) 3 – *Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes towards Nature-Positive Societies* – focuses on cross-case analysis of the entire set of case studies, to allow drawing out knowledge of more general relevance based on the findings of the case studies. Focus is on identifying patterns and drawing insights across the various case studies at a higher level of abstraction. This provides a basis for the development of novel strategies and approaches through which to initiate and accelerate transformative change towards protection and restoration of biodiversity under socially just forms. These strategies can, in turn, inform governance and policy development within the different sectors of society (public, private, civil), and in relation to economic sectors and land/water use sectors which have a high impact on biodiversity change. In BIOTraCes, the high impact sectors represented in the case studies are *agriculture and food production/consumption, urbanisation, forestry and maritime/aquatic living sources* (see [Brief introduction to the case studies/Chapter 2](#)).

The **aim** of the WP3 cross-case analysis of the BIOTraCes case studies is to identify strategies and approaches that may support transformative change towards strengthened biodiversity, grounded in principles of social equity.

WP3 unpacks the case studies in relation to certain key issues addressed by its different tasks, namely:

- T3.1 focuses on opportunities for leverage and processes of amplification that increase the impact of the biodiversity innovation within, out and beyond the local context. See [Opportunities for leverage and amplification \(T3.1\)/Chapter 5](#).
- T3.2 focuses on distilling which types of strategies apply in the different cases and contexts from an overarching perspective. See [Strategies and approaches in \(transformative\) biodiversity initiatives \(T3.2\)/Chapter 6](#).
- T3.3 focuses specifically on interactive strategies, i.e. activities and interaction between actors to promote learning, participation and transformation. See [Strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation, dialogue \(T3.3\)/Chapter 7](#).
- T3.4 focuses on strategies that may address power imbalances and empower and include marginalised groups. See [Innovative thinking for just and effective governance \(T3.4\)/Chapter 8](#).
- T3.5 focuses on the importance of the Sustainable Development Goals – which in themselves constitute a key strategy devised by the global community – e.g. the extent to which these can present opportunities or barriers for change. See [Biodiversity interdependencies of SDGs \(T3.5\)/Chapter 9](#).

WP3 approaches the set of case studies with the ambition of disentangling local and context specific and locally unique factors from more general ones, understanding human-nature

relationships, and analysing how the various biodiversity innovations and interventions may, or may not, affect the development within the high impact sectors. We strive to identify ways of invoking change in the long and short term. Long term strategies may entail e.g. focus on structures such as legislative and policy instruments on different levels as well as social structures (e.g. values, norms and cultural traits) among specific stakeholder groups and the general population. These structures also largely determine the context for short term, more immediately applicable instruments and processes in specific places.

The WP3 tasks are attentive to the complementary PEPE principles (*Pluralising, Empowering, Politicising* and *Embedding*), a central point of departure for BIOTraCes and for leveraging transformative change. *Pluralising* concerns acknowledging the roles of multiple stakeholders and variation in views and values, emphasising bottom-up perspectives. *Empowering* entails an ambition of strengthening the voices of marginalised groups. *Politicising* addresses political barriers to transformative change (e.g. power asymmetries, dominating interests and paradigms, path dependencies and 'lock-ins'). Finally, *Embedding* relates to integration of seeds for transformative change in the economy, governance and policy and social practice. Embedding takes place through e.g. upscaling of initiatives of local origin and establishing connections to key stakeholders and power structures across public, private and civil society sectors (BIOTraCes 2023). The PEPE principles are addressed to varying degrees throughout the chapters of this report and are the cornerstone of the joint discussion for the WP3 tasks taken together (see [Concluding discussion](#)/Chapter 10).

1.1 Reading guide

The remainder of this deliverable report is structured as follows. The reader is provided with a brief introduction to the nine European case studies upon which the cross-case analyses is based. Next follows a literature review covering key theoretical constructs and concepts; serving to frame the subsequent analyses. The methodological approach and empirical data are then presented. The approach was coordinated and conducted jointly across the tasks and therefore relates to all tasks except T3.5 (which followed a different timeline). Then, results from the respective WP3 tasks are presented in a series of task-specific chapters for T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4 and T3.5. Finally, we engage in a joint concluding discussion based on input from all tasks in relation to the PEPE principles and transformative potential.

This deliverable, D3.2, is the main BIOTraCes deliverable and includes input from all tasks in the WP. For T3.2, D3.2 is the only deliverable (therefore, the chapter covering this task is the most extensive). For T3.1, results are forthcoming in D3.1 (M40), for T3.3 in D3.3 (M36) and for T3.4 in D3.4 (M36). For T3.5 results have already been presented in D3.5 and D3.6 (M26).

1.2 References

BIOTraCes. (2023). *Biodiversity and Transformative Change for plural and nature positive societies*. Project proposal.

During, R., van Eldik, Z., & Wortel, A. (2023). *Leads and brickstones for a nature positive society—Methodology of the cross-case analysis and across case synthesis* (Project Deliverable No. D1.8; BIOTraCes (Biodiversity and Transformative Change for Plural and Nature-Positive Societies)). Wageningen Environmental Research.

Pahl-Wostl, C., Basurto, X., & Villamayor-Tomas, S. (2021). Comparative case study analysis. In R. Biggs, R. Preiser, A. De Vos, M. Schlüter, K. Maciejewski, & H. Clements, *The Routledge Handbook of Research Methods for Social-Ecological Systems* (1st ed., pp. 282–294). Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003021339-24>

2 Brief introduction to the case studies

Katarina Haugen (UGOT)

This chapter presents brief introductions to the core issues addressed in each of the BIOTraCes case studies (see Figure 2-1), to provide a baseline level of context for the reader. The case study introductions are organised by the biodiversity impact sector to which they 'belong'. More in-depth information about the respective case studies is available in previous and forthcoming reports prepared by the different research teams (see previous and forthcoming BIOTraCes WP2 reports).

Figure 2-1: BIOTraCes case studies across Europe. Source: BIOTraCes (2023)

2.1 High impact sector: Agriculture and food production/consumption

High value nature farming

This case study takes place in central Romania, an area renowned for its high biodiversity, including native vegetation, grasslands rich in species and populations of many protected species. The 'natural capital' of the area is high, with e.g. healthy soils and clean water. The landscape has co-evolved over time through environmentally friendly farming and forestry activities. This has prevailed intergenerationally, and the local population maintains traditional ecological knowledge and views that continuously support local ecological values. The case study investigates underlying drivers (e.g. cultural, consumption and livelihood patterns) of ecosystem change in the area with regard to both flora and fauna, and especially the impacts on agriculture. The case study will produce a guide for local stakeholders to preserve ecosystem services and stimulate transformation towards sustainable farming. Key stakeholders include local farmers, consumer organisations and NGOs). (BIOTraCes & Universitatea Babeş Bolyai, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Romanian case**.

Mértola future lab

The Portuguese case study, run by the CES research team, takes place in the village of Mértola, where Mértola Future Lab is a collectively grounded local strategy aiming towards ecological goals, climate change adaptation and combating desertification. More specifically, the focus is on local food production and consumption. Several societal partners of BIOTraCes/CES are involved in Mértola future lab: in addition to the main partner, the Terra Sintrópica Association, there is also the local municipal council, a community social venue (Santana de Cambas) and local primary schools. Mértola future lab is engaged in furthering novel methods for local food production in a context where agriculture is strongly affected by desertification and water shortage. The case study emphasises agrobiodiversity, not least the relationship between soil level biodiversity and pluralistic knowledge. The societal partner has several strands of action, for example decarbonisation of food logistics/transport and active involvement of especially elderly women. (BIOTraCes & Centro de Estudos Sociais, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Portuguese case**.

2.2 High impact sector: Maritime/aquatic living sources

Fluvial eco-partnership

The Italian case study, run by the UNICT research team, takes place in the Simeto Valley, surrounding one of Sicily's major rivers. It is conducted in collaboration with the Participatory Presidium of the Simeto River Agreement—an alliance of grassroots groups, municipalities, and researchers working to protect and restore the valley. The area faces serious challenges, including climate change, desertification, pollution, irresponsible land use, and depopulation. The study aims to reconnect local communities with the river ecosystem, enhance biodiversity, and make the valley a more attractive place to live. Key goals include mapping and revitalising biodiversity niches and developing a strategic plan for sustainable land use. Innovative governance is seen as essential to counter ecosystem

overexploitation and landscape fragmentation. The case study follows a nested approach, focusing on specific areas within the valley, including the development of large-scale photovoltaic and agrivoltaic plants and the creation of Renewable Energy Communities, which aim to balance ecological integrity with economic and social revitalisation. (BIOTraCes & Università Degli Studi di Catania, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Italian case**.

Free-flowing rivers¹

The Lithuanian case study focuses on the Šventoji River in Anykščiai, a town in northeastern Lithuania. The river is dammed within the town, and its restoration is recognised as a national priority for re-establishing longitudinal connectivity and improving fish migration and biodiversity. Dams are among the main human-induced pressures on aquatic ecosystems, particularly for migratory fish. Across Europe and globally, dams fragment river continuity, block fish migration routes, alter fluvial habitats and disrupt sediment transport. In reservoirs, pollutants can accumulate, while oxygen depletion and temperature changes may occur, further amplifying negative effects on fluvial biodiversity. Studies estimate around one million artificial barriers fragment Europe's rivers, many of which have lost their socio-economic function and even become obsolete (Balleti et al., 2020). Restoring free-flowing rivers is therefore a key objective of the EU Biodiversity Strategy, as dam removal offers one of the most effective and holistic responses to these pressures. In Lithuania, however, progress remains limited. Alongside financial, technical, and administrative limitations, a lack of public support continues to slow implementation. Yet the potential benefits of river restoration may be significant, including enhanced biodiversity, reduced maintenance costs, and new opportunities for communities to reconnect with their rivers and landscapes, opening new possibilities for recreation, tourism, and new everyday interactions with nature. The BIOTraCes research team, in collaboration with Mykolas Romeris University, works with the Anykščiai community to explore perceptions of the Šventoji River and the dam. Using participatory methods, the study examines how people relate to the river, what drives or limits local support and shapes their views on environmental change, and how cooperation can help build shared pathways toward sustainable river restoration (BIOTraCes & Mykolas Romeris Universitetas, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Lithuanian case**.

2.3 High impact sector: Forestry

Bottom-up forest biodiversity

The Swedish study, run by the UGOT team, focuses on the role of private forest owners of small and medium sized forest properties, and their views on forest biodiversity. The case study is set in three areas in southwestern Sweden. Forest management is a pressing issue due to both biodiversity loss and climate change and plays a key role in contributing solutions to these vast challenges. However, the voices of small-scale forest owners – an increasingly diverse group – are seldom heard in debates even though they often possess

¹ The presentation of the Lithuanian case was written by its societal partner, Karolina Gurjazkaitė, who has requested that her contribution be acknowledged in a footnote rather than as formal authorship.

in-depth experience-based knowledge and expertise, especially concerning local scale forestry. By involving forest owners in e.g. forestry policy there is potential for developing novel methods in the entire complex of forest management, from a policy, practical and relational point of view, i.e. the connection between humans and nature. Alternatives to the current standards in the forest industry can significantly strengthen forest biodiversity in terms of species and habitats for both flora and fauna. Co-created methods also strengthen the social sustainability of forestry. (BIOTraCes & University of Gothenburg, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Swedish case**.

Traditional herders' knowledge

Traditional herders are the key stakeholders and societal partners in the Hungarian case study, run by CER, including an association of women herders and other informal networks. Emphasis is on the traditional knowledge and values concerning human-nature relationships which are held by this professional group and have been transmitted over generations. Applying this knowledge provides great benefits for biodiversity compared to conventional conservation management. Sustainable management of the species-rich grasslands requires proper grazing based on in-depth knowledge and innovation based on this knowledge, something that mainstream conservationists have yet to realise. Current regulatory frameworks also tend to create difficulties for herders, and development of novel policies are called for. Beyond integrating herders' knowledge into novel approaches for biodiversity conservation, the case study also means to alter the image of the herding occupation. Recognising the importance of this group and placing value on their knowledge is necessary to maintain the group, which is currently decreasing. Helping young people to become and remain herders is key issue. (BIOTraCes & Ökológiai Kutatóközpont, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Hungarian case**.

2.4 High impact sector: Urbanisation

Foodpark against industry

This case study, run by the UT research team, centres on a local citizen initiative in Amsterdam, the Netherlands, to acquire land in the Lutkemeerpolder for the establishment of an ecological food park. The initiative forms a vision for an alternative urban future, since the suggested land use is in stark contrast with the original plans for the area; industrial/warehouse use. The visions also include an economic transformation, with emphasis on the ecological and social value of land rather than its conventional financial value. One argument for the alternative use of the land is its quality in terms of soil fertility, which renders it suitable for agro-ecological purposes. Values of biodiversity, inclusivity, recreation, education are also highlighted, alongside small-scale local food production. The societal partner of BIOTraCes/UT, Foodpark Amsterdam (in Dutch: *Voedselpark Amsterdam*), is a local group of citizen activists and emerging social movement whose goal is to integrate nature values and ecological food production in an urban setting. The case study involves local empowerment and participation through co-development of a regulatory framework for a community land trust and emphasises citizens' voice in decision-making. (BIOTraCes & Universiteit Twente, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Dutch Foodpark case**.

Urban schoolyards – biodiversity lab

The case study, run by the BC3 research team, takes place in Vitoria-Gasteiz, the administrative capital of Spain's Basque Country, and focuses on a schoolyard greening initiative as part of the city's broader urban green infrastructure strategy. Led by the City Council and the Environmental Studies Centre (CEA)—a BIOTraCes/BC3 partner—the initiative emerged in response to parental demands and is currently being piloted. Schoolyards effectively function as 'living labs' to enhance ecosystem services and climate adaptation, while also co-developing innovative participatory methods with CEA. By transforming grey space asphalt surfaces into green spaces, the initiative helps children build personal connections with nature in an urban setting. It also promotes social sustainability by creating more inclusive public spaces. These interactions can foster environmental awareness and nature-oriented values in younger generations, addressing a gap in formal education where children often learn about nature without experiencing it directly. (BIOTraCes & Basque Centre for Climate Change, 2025). The case is referred to throughout the report as the **Spanish case**.

Nature-inclusive building

In this case study, run by the WR research team, focus is directed towards the housing/construction sector, especially communities that strive for nature-inclusive lifestyles and housing. Emphasis is on living with nature, which makes these building projects and programmes, such as eco-villages/communities, important for biodiversity. However, the social movements working towards this form housing (e.g. 'off the grid') are systematically overlooked in the conventional housing development sector and urban planning process. BIOTraCes/WR work with the societal partner De Beuk Wageningen, the Netherlands, an association comprising five organisations with similar goals of living with nature. WR support De Beuk's participation and inclusion in housing programs and development of regulatory frameworks in the housing sector. The case study also includes a second societal partner, the Province of Overijssel, which was selected due to its high ambitions and innovative policy program on nature inclusivity (BIOTraCes & Wageningen Environmental Research, 2025). The cases are referred to throughout the report as the **Dutch eco-village case** (i.e. De Beuk) and the **Dutch Province case** (i.e. Overijssel).

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3 Literature review

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3.1 Introduction and conceptual notes

This literature review is intended to introduce key concepts and theoretical constructs related to BIOTraCes Work Package 3, thus serving as an overarching framework for the different tasks included in the present report. The literature review commences with framing and contextual issues that define the prerequisites for transformative innovation and initiatives; then moves on to broader governance approaches that set the stage for innovation; followed by a focus on strategies and finally upscaling and diffusion of innovations for transformative change.

We acknowledge the diversity of definitions and interpretations of the term strategy, and its varying relationships with related concepts such as approaches, tactics, pathways, tools, actions, and interventions. These relationships can involve e.g. partial overlaps and nested structures. A general distinction is that tools, tactics, and actions tend to be more concrete and short term. They can be implemented as parts of broader, longer-term strategies or approaches. For example, IPBES (O'Brien et al. 2024) describe a strategy as a general, overarching approach, which in turn consists of a series of concrete actions. The latter can be seen as concrete operationalisation of an abstract theoretical construct.

Acknowledging that a strategy often is something that people 'do' rather than 'have', our understanding is that transformative strategies are about doing something with the purpose of sparking or accelerating transformative change. This definition still allows for great variation in terms of the focus and characteristics of strategies, e.g. the degree of specificity or which components they include.

We use the basic structure of a Theory of Change to clarify the scope of strategy. A typical Theory of Change is structured as follows (Cash et al., 2006; Dhillon & Vaca, 2018; Gibson et al., 2019; Suškevičs, 2012): *Mission* → *Strategies* → *Outputs* → *Outcomes* → *Impacts*. In this framework, *Outputs* describe what an actor or network concretely delivers; *Outcomes* refers to results obtained in the wider system; *Impacts* denotes broader societal or systemic changes. *Outputs* fall within the sphere of control of the actor or network, whereas *Outcomes* and *Impacts* lie beyond it. Causally attributing *Impacts* to the actor's *Strategy* and actions is difficult, as they emerge from the interplay of transformative actions by many actors and networks. *Impacts* also connect back to the actor's *Mission*: the overarching objectives that drive their efforts.

Strategies may be implicit and embedded in actions. For an action to be considered strategic, it should typically have a degree of intentionality and occur as a pattern – not merely once or by chance. This approach to understanding strategies allows for implicit strategising. Just as Theories of Change in social innovations or movements are seldom made explicit, strategies may also be only partially articulated or understood by those involved. However, strategies may also be made very explicit, detailed and 'SMART²'. Especially when informed by an overarching approach (a Theory of Transformative Change:

² Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Realistic, and Time-bound.

ToTC; see Turnhout et al. 2023 (D1.1)), actors can design, plan and evaluate strategies aiming to spark or accelerate transformative change.

3.2 Framing: a brief introduction to transformative change

In recent years, sustainability research and practice have undergone a 'transformative turn' (Blythe et al. 2018). Transformative change can be defined or understood as '*...such non-linear systemic change that leads to fundamental, qualitative changes in societies' cultures, structures and practices*' (Loorbach et al. 2017 cited in Loorbach et al. 2020:253). Patterson et al. (2017) highlight that transformation entails '*fundamental changes in structural, functional, relational, and cognitive aspects of socio-technical systems that lead to new patterns of interactions and outcomes*' (Patterson et al. 2017:2). In connection to biodiversity, IPBES defines it as '*fundamental, system-wide shifts in views, structures and practices that address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline*' (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024:6). Scoones et al. (2020) propose three approaches to how transformative change can be understood and effected. First, *structural* approaches focus on changes in production and consumption within society; including economic and social aspects of organisation, governance and behaviour. Second, *systemic* approaches concern intentional efforts to shift complex and interconnected systems (including actors, institutions and technologies) to attain specific goals. Third, *enabling* approaches highlight the role of agency in terms of values, capacities and collective action to co-create preferred scenarios. On a science-policy interface level, transformative change is a key element of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework as well as the Sustainable Development Goals (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024).

Transformative change entails 'radical, large-scale and long-term changes' (Hölscher et al., 2017:1). While incremental, path dependent development (through policy and innovation) remains dominant, there is broad recognition that transformative change is necessary (Loorbach 2022). This need stems from the limits of reform-based (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024) or incremental approaches, the imperative to tackle root causes, and the wicked nature of many major sustainability challenges, including biodiversity loss (Termeer et al., 2024)- problems of vast 'scope, scale, and urgency' (Vogel & O'Brien 2022:653). *Wicked problems* are dynamic and based on moving, interconnected parts; evading clear definitions and involving multiple actors with conflicting interests (Churchman 1967; Rittel & Webber 1973 cited in Termeer & Dewulf 2019). Such persistent problems are 'complex and multi-sided', 'uncertain and unstructured' and 'difficult to manage'. These problems are key targets of 'mission-oriented' innovation policy addressing current *grand challenges* such as including climate change, environmental degradation, ageing population, public health, access to food/water, and security (Coenen et al. 2015).

The wickedness of ecosystem management problems arises from the dynamism and complexity of social-ecological systems (Armitage et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2005; Walker et al., 2004). There are no universal solutions; problem framing and solving require learning and continuous adaptation. In biodiversity governance, wickedness manifests in e.g. conflicting values and objectives among stakeholders (e.g. conservationists, economic interests, local communities), and mismatches between ecological and geographical-administrative boundaries (DeFries & Nagendra 2017; Suškevičs 2012). Some scholars (Pascual et al., 2022) argue that wicked problems cannot efficiently be addressed through current policy regimes focused on incremental change (DeFries & Nagendra 2017). Others

note that incremental steps remain necessary to avoid the traps of both reductionism (treating wicked problems as tame) and paralysis in the face of complexity. Incremental transitions and transformative change are also interrelated. For example, many small, sustained changes may cumulatively produce transformation (Patterson et al. 2017). The 'Small Wins' approach (Termeer et al. 2019; Termeer & 2024; Termeer & Dewulf 2019) similarly suggests that profound small-scale change can have transformative effects. This approach is discussed further in *Pathways as ideal-types for strategic action*.

The concept of *leverage points* refers to 'places within a complex system /.../ where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything' (Meadows 1999:1). Strategic actions and interventions can be seen as 'levers' used to access the leverage points (Chan et al. 2020). However, Abson et al. (2017) argue that sustainability interventions tend to focus mostly on low hanging fruits in terms of weak leverage points rather than the deeper ones that may be harder to reach but which have stronger potential to leverage transformative change. Shallow leverage points include *parameters* (e.g. regulations and economic incentives) and *feedbacks* (e.g. intra-system interactions) while the deeper ones are *design* (social structures and institutions which set the prerequisites for parameters and feedbacks) and *intent* (social norms, values and views that underpin and shape the system) (Abson et al. 2017).

Whether incremental or transformative, change unfolds through multiple steps or events across levels (scale) and time (phases). Socio-material innovation, such as the BIOTraCes biodiversity initiatives, entail *reconfigurations/shifts* in *practices, structures and views* (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024). These reconfigurations can be less or more fundamental, and thus less or more transformative. Reconfigurations require destabilising, or *opening up*, of current configurations (Hebinck et al., 2022). While the multi-level perspective (MLP) and socio-technical transitions literature capture this process, they often underplay the relational dimensions of transformation (Scoones et al., 2020; Stirling, 2015). Understanding the social and cultural dimensions of *opening up* – pluralising, empowering, and politicising – is key. Opening up may be needed at multiple (or each) of the levels of practices, structures and views. It may be needed to open up mindsets of communities, communicative cultures, bureaucratic routines, or entrenched ideas about property and value. It also pertains strongly to the barriers and blockages which need undoing, overcoming, or circumventing.

After a phase of 'opening up' meanings and institutions – necessary for mobilising, accessing and integrating diverse ways of knowing and doing – 'closing down' into new configurations is inevitable (Hajer, 1995; Stirling, 2008). For example, the design, embedding and reproduction of integrative landscape approaches entail such closure (Forsyth, 2005; Forsyth & Springate-Baginski, 2021). This corresponds to 'embedding' in PEPE: after opening, pluralising and innovating, new practices need to be stabilised and instituted. However, closure is a highly contentious part of transformation – *who* closes down, and *what* is being closed? Ensuring inclusivity, legitimacy and reflexivity in these processes requires institutional and contextual attention to power dynamics.

3.3 Context: place-based dynamics and institutional logics

Strategies and approaches for transformative change concerns how stakeholders can 'plant seeds and help to nurture the potential' for transformation (Blythe et al. 2018:18). The context in which these 'seeds' are planted – geographical, institutional and political –

shapes their outcomes. Change processes are always context-dependent and embedded in complex, multi-level governance settings involving diverse actors (Griffin 2012). For example, local governance is conditioned by institutional frameworks at higher geographical-administrative levels, which can shift power relations (Görg 2007). Transformative initiatives may arise within the public/state, private/market-based or community-based sectors, or through cross-sector collaboration where different actors team up strategically to implement and diffuse innovations (Loorbach et al. 2020). Hence, transformative change depends on human agency at individual, collective/group as well as political levels (Blythe et al. 2018).

In the processual landscape approach, *landscapes* are everything that is present in an area and what flows to and from it; material features, be it abiotic or living beings, and immaterial features, whether individual or collectively shared. Landscape is understood as a process where physical elements of human and/or non-human origin co-evolve with institutional components and intangible aspects such as values, traditions and knowledge (Hägerstrand 2001, Stenseke 2020). A delimited piece of landscape, a particular area, is not regarded as a closed system. Instead, landscapes are locally manifested yet to a significant degree influenced by global forces (Setten et al. 2012). This perspective is mirrored in both the European Science Foundation's briefing on landscape (European Science Foundation 2010) and in the European Landscape Convention (Jørgensen et al. 2016). This approach acknowledges the integration and co-evolution of material and immaterial aspects in a specific place, thereby opening for dialectic synthesis between social-constructivist and materiality-based views, and providing a frame for capturing environmental co-production unfolds. Several perspectives and insights gained in landscape research that can qualify relational values thinking regarding community, identity and stewardship. The European Landscape Convention's definition of landscape, an area, as perceived by people acknowledges subjective and plural perceptions of the same piece of landscape, and consequently manifold demands on its future form/s and function/s (Stenseke et al. 2011).

Lasting transformation change rarely stems from external stimuli alone (e.g. regulatory reforms/incentives); it also develops 'from the inside out' (Pisters et al. 2019:1). In the context of sustainability transformation, this 'inner' perspective implies *place-based* change rooted in socio-spatial relationships between people and place; also described as an understanding of landscape as all-integrating and processual (Hägerstrand 2001, Stenseke 2020). This entails social, cultural and historical dimensions, and sense of place shapes social norms and practices. Place is also a material context including land and other tangible resources used in local livelihood strategies (Pisters et al. 2019). Thus, place-based social innovation is based on the unique characteristics of specific contexts (Mehmood et al. 2019).

Seeds for transformative change – not least those related to biodiversity – are often grounded local context and its geographical, institutional, political conditions. Initiatives often arise in response to opportunities or challenges therein (Loorbach et al. 2020), including place-specific resources and socio-ecological systems. Places are the sites of 'debates, power struggles and negotiations', and of innovations, initiatives and interventions. These shape the place and how people make sense of it, e.g. through place identity processes (Horlings 2016:33; Mehmood et al. 2019; Soja 2009). Transformative innovation initiatives also often connected to the global scale through interactions within potentially far-reaching trans-local networks of peer initiatives (Loorbach et al. 2020). While places are unique, they are simultaneously linked to and embedded within broader,

cultural, economic and political processes through globalisation, at the intersection of local and global scales (Massey 1991). Places, and the innovations that are developed there, are located within nested scales, geographically and institutionally. Therefore, place-based innovation can spark change beyond their origins – provided that supporting/enabling governance structures are in place (Weck et al. 2021).

Concerning institutional and sectoral prerequisites, Avelino & Wittmayer (2016) distinguish four overarching societal sectors – *state*, *market*, *community* and *third sector*. The state sector is non-profit, formal and public', the market is 'formal /.../ private and for-profit', the community is 'private, informal and non-profit', while the third sector is seen as occupying an intermediate position between the other sectors and the dimensions of formal vs informal, for-profit vs not for profit and public vs private. Each sector has its own logic of functioning, sets of actors and power relations (both externally in relation to other sectors, and amongst the actors within the sector). The actors are found on several levels of aggregation: sector, organisation and individual levels. These actors can have different degrees of agency and power as they engage in activities and often interact with each other within the sectoral context (or sometimes within several sectors). Within each of these sectors, there are a variety of power relations and interactions, roles of the different actors, and elements pertaining to both 'regimes' (main, normative and power-concentrated incumbent structures) and 'niches' (e.g. grassroots initiatives, small-scale innovations, activism, movements) (Avelino & Wittmayer 2016). Within *socio-technical transitions* theory, interactions between niches and regimes are understood as impacting the capacity of innovations to become embedded in the mainstream. Both niches and regimes are, in turn, influenced by 'landscapes' i.e. the external context (biophysical and societal) (Hermans et al. 2016).

Cross-sector partnerships (public-private, business-nonprofit, multi-stakeholder initiatives, governance networks and social alliances) are often promoted to address wicked environmental problems that cut across sectors and therefore need to be targeted from several angles. While these partnerships hold significant potential, they face challenges stemming from e.g. the differing institutional logics of participating actors (Vogel et al. 2021).

3.4 Governance approaches and instruments for change

Governance is of central importance for transformative change: it can be part of the problematic structures that need to change or part of the solution by leveraging change. However, Patterson et al. (2017) point out that many knowledge gaps exist regarding e.g. which governance and institutional structures best support transformation across scales and sectors (Patterson et al. 2017). DeFries & Nagendra (2017) outline two general governance approaches to wicked problems in ecosystem management. *Institutional fit* centres on designing institutions aligned with specific ecosystems in spatial, temporal and functional terms, e.g. river basin authorities spanning geographical-administrative jurisdictions. However, a fit suitable for one problem may well be inappropriate for another, related problem. *Institutional interplay* emphasises interaction and coordination among institutions enable system-wide change (DeFries & Nagendra 2017).

A central dimension of transformation is behavioural change. Policy instruments to influence behaviour are often grouped into *carrots* (economic incentives), *sticks* (regulation) and *sermons* (information) (Pacheco-Vega 2020; Harrison 1999). Specific

strategies can range along a continuum from non-coercive, voluntary measures to mandatory regulation ('command-and-control'). They can also be combined into policy mixes (Howlett 2018), e.g. combining voluntary measures with a 'threat' of potential regulation to nudge the recipients to act in the desired way (Pachego-Vega 2020).

Emphasis on *governance* has meant rethinking of policy instruments – their definition, functioning, scope and implementation (Pachego-Vega 2020) – since governance entails 'the structures, processes, rules and traditions that determine how people in societies make decisions and share power, exercise responsibility and ensure accountability' (Patterson et al. 2017:3). Growing evidence shows the usefulness of mixed policy approaches; in contrast with the previous heavy emphasis on either regulation (sticks) or non-regulatory measures (sermons). Non-regulatory approaches are relatively popular due to their light burden for monitoring, enforcement and sanctioning – features that hamper the efficiency of these approaches. For less coercive instruments, the idea is that providing more information encourages agents to self-regulate, possibly even beyond what formal regulations would require (Pachego-Vega 2020). Also, excessive focus on regulation can create a 'culture of resistance,' where actors actively look for loopholes and comply only at the minimum required level (Harrison 1999).

Transformative governance

Transformative governance refers to 'the formal and informal (public and private) rules, rulemaking systems and actor networks at all levels of human society that enable transformative change' (Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021:21). Over time, such systems can evolve to enhance their capacity to support sustainable development by addressing indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. Transformative governance encompasses four main approaches: *integrative*, *inclusive*, *adaptive* and *pluralist*, which together constitute the foundation of governance with transformative potential (Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021).

Integrative governance focuses on interactions across different parts of the governance system—such as tools applied in various geographical contexts, sectors, or scales. A lack of integration (e.g., organisational silos) risks unaligned efforts, leading to incoherence and poor outcomes. *Adaptive* governance starts from the premise that environmental change is complex and requires continuous adjustment of governance approaches, for instance through feedback loops. *Pluralist* governance recognises the need for diverse knowledge and perspectives on biodiversity and sustainability, including non-Western views and approaches beyond conventional scientific tools (Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). Combining different forms of knowledge can enrich strategies and create synergies that accelerate change (IPBES/O'Brien et al., 2024).

Inclusive governance ensures broad stakeholder participation, enhancing legitimacy, accountability, and justice (Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021; Suškevičs 2012), reflecting the importance of equity for sustainability (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024). However, conflicts of interest and values amongst different stakeholders can surface (Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021), and 'win-win' outcomes are rare. Hence, transformative processes often face resistance and tension (Vogel & O'Brien 2022; Loorbach 2022). Challenging incumbent power relations and strengthening marginalised groups likely means the weakening of other stakeholders' privileges, at least in the short-term (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024). Governing this process entails e.g. dealing with resistance from those whose interest align with problematic path dependencies (Patterson et al. 2017). Stakeholders who hold some

degree of power promote and protect their positions. To minimise damage to their interests, these 'incumbents' favour minor optimisations of the current regime over transformation, resulting in 'lock-ins'. In such cases, potential for transformative change occurs only when growing pressures on the system finally trigger a break with the equilibrium (Loorbach 2022). Hence, strategies for transformation may need to include ways of dealing with resistance (Vogel & O'Brien 2022).

Although the scale, scope and urgency of transformative change make it a formidable challenge, it is considered attainable (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024). Effective governance requires diverse tools and initiatives applied across levels and contexts, rather than reliance on single approaches (Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021; Vogel & O'Brien 2022). All four abovementioned approaches are necessary – but in and of themselves. Additional factors include e.g. changed power dynamics, especially empowerment of groups and stakeholders (including indigenous people and local communities/IPLC) who often embody values aligned with sustainability goals. Governance approaches must tackle indirect drivers of unsustainable development – such as biodiversity loss – by addressing entrenched structures shaped by societal values and reflected in behaviours related to demographic change, sociocultural and economic patterns, technology, and institutions (Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021). Also, IPBES/O'Brien et al. (2024) underscore addressing *underlying* causes of biodiversity loss, i.e. mechanisms that produce and reproduce its direct and indirect drivers.

Strategic action is required for transformative change to reverse the current negative development (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024; Loorbach 2022). Accelerating societal transformation entails 'finding strategies, tools and methods that make the radical alternatives that developed in niches the norm' and 'fundamentally challenge business-as-usual' patterns (Loorbach 2022:7-8). Given the wicked and even 'super-wicked' (Schneider & Clauß, 2019) nature of environmental crises, novel strategies must be accompanied by continuous adaptation of governance systems (Termeer & Dewulf, 2019).

3.5 Routes to transformative change

Theories of Transformative Change (ToTCs) provide overarching strategic frameworks to guide transformative efforts, building on *Theories of Change* (ToC). ToC make assumptions explicit about the expected outcomes of intended actions. ToCs typically include detailed, linear, causal models that aid clarity and accountability. However, they have been criticised for being overdetermined (leaving little room for emergent or unforeseen change) and underperform in practice, when complex dynamics fail to conform to the model (Botha et al., 2017; Dhillon & Vaca, 2018).

In the transformative change literature, the term *pathways* is more prevalent to denote processes by which transformative change could be achieved. Pathways are highly flexible: they can take many forms, vary in depth, and accommodate multiple interpretations. Pathways may be seen as bundles of contexts, strategies and events that might result in transformative changes in path-dependent ways (e.g. Fazey et al., 2016). The perspective is rooted in socio-ecological systems theory and complexity theory which discuss system state – and transformation – in terms of basins of attraction and different pathways between them (e.g. Westley et al., 2011).

Pathways differ from ToTCs in several ways. Pathways emphasise the existence of multiple possible routes toward transformation, to be selected or combined. However, pathways

remain elusive, underdefined or only partially understood in much of the literature. By contrast, ToTCs (see (see Turnhout et al. 2023) – understood here as evolved from logical frameworks – explicitly articulate causal processes leading to transformative ends (impacts). Pathways and ToTCs are not mutually exclusive and may well be used in concert (Marciniak et al., 2024).

Pathways and ToTCs can both be likened to routes or roadmaps. All these can assist explanation and projection. However, transformative pathways should not be seen as mere forecasting tools, but as tools to help envision future change, creating alternative futures (Fazey et al., 2016, p. 41). Pathways ‘must be understood as both retrospective explanations of where change has occurred and forward-looking strategies that enable sustainability’ (De Castro et al., 2025, p. 3). According to Sharpe et al. (2016), pathways occupy a specific niche in relation to other devices for charting transformative courses, such as *roadmaps* or *scenarios*. Roadmaps are best suited to contexts with high agency and low uncertainty, while scenarios perform well under opposite conditions. In contrast, pathways analysis, they suggest, is most appropriate for contexts characterised by both high uncertainty and high agency (Sharpe et al., 2016). While this is an intriguing proposition, it remains unclear when and whether ‘high agency’ is present in dispersed transformative contexts. Rather, we suggest that while scenarios explore multiple potential futures, pathways envision multiple ways to arrive at a desired future.

Pathways and ToTCs share a focus and reliance on collective action (networked agency) as a prerequisite for transformation (Bouwma et al., 2022; De Castro et al., 2025; Rice et al., 2020): ‘Change is always the emergent outcome of multiple strategies of multiple actors’ (Bijker and Law 1992). No single actor is sufficiently powerful or pervasive to enforce change alone – and if they could, such change would likely fall short of being transformative in inclusive, just, and profound ways. Nevertheless, ToTCs concentrate on the *sphere of control* of an actor: the resources and strategies they can directly influence to produce outputs. Moving from outputs to potentially transformative outcomes and impacts requires networks of networks. Pathways are conceived as distinct albeit complex modes through which social systems may shift and adapt. However, comprehension of what single actors, groups and/or networks can do to effect such pathways is limited.

IPBES’ overarching strategies

In the recent thematic assessment report, IPBES/O’Brien et al. (2024) identify five main overarching strategies (Figure 3.1) for transformative change in support of biodiversity and sustainability; each targeting different key issues and structures. Given their broad scope, they would entail supra-strategies. The first strategy, ‘*conserve and regenerate places of value to nature and people*’, is grounded in formally established protection, for instance through legal reforms. In particular, IPBES underscores the potential (e.g. in terms of cost-efficiency) in directing attention to places where efforts to protect and conserve nature are already underway. Supporting existing efforts by local communities or indigenous peoples are seen as of key importance when – as if often the case – these are based on and prioritise sustainable values. The second strategy is to ‘*drive systemic change in the sectors most responsible for biodiversity loss and nature’s decline*’. This can involve for example regulations of economic activities or supporting constructive efforts emerging from within civil society. Changing subsidy frameworks to support biodiversity-friendly practices is also a way of rearranging the existing incentive structure to reduce externalities. The third strategy, ‘*transform economic systems for nature and equity*’,

entails radically changing existing paradigms to give more weight to social and environmental values than to (private) financial interests. For example, definitions and measures of economic performance measures can be altered to highlight different indicators and goals. Also, current unsustainable patterns of production and consumption (including related inequities) need to change. Tools to achieve this can include e.g. regulations, taxes and formal agreements. The fourth strategy, ‘*transform governance systems to be integrated, inclusive, accountable and adaptive*’, especially highlights participatory governance processes where many stakeholders – and thus their different perspectives, values and knowledge – are actively involved in addressing the challenges at hand. Finally, the fifth strategy is to ‘*shift societal views and values to recognise and prioritise fundamental interconnections between humans and nature*’. This addresses and calls into question important underlying causes of biodiversity loss related to e.g. cultural patterns, values, norms and perspectives and associated (habitual) behaviour. The necessary shifts can be stimulated through e.g. policy tools and educational reform/adaptations (IPBES/O’Brien et al. 2024).

Figure 3-1: Strategies for transformative change identified by IPBES. (Source: IPBES/O’Brien et al. 2024)

Each main strategy is associated with a set of specific and concrete *actions* (IPBES/O’Brien et al. 2024), including many examples of methods and tools oriented towards sticks, carrots as well as sermons (Pacheco-Vega 2020; Harrison 1999) (see [Strategic action for transformative change](#)). The IPBES strategies are assumed to have high potential to

complement each other and thereby generate positive synergies. The transformative potential of initiatives is not seen as dependent on scale per se, but rather on whether the initiatives target underlying causes of biodiversity loss and are based on 'explicit visions of desirable futures' (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024:23). Also, several of the strategies explicitly focus on the role of local communities. Involving these stakeholders in transformatory processes is considered to be of key importance since they often embody sustainable-focused and locally grounded knowledge, views, values and practices (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024).

Pathways competing in a political struggle

Working on the politics of decarbonisation, Stripple & Bulkeley (2019) highlight that pathways are both conceptualised as *entities* (the route or chain that is followed) and *processes* (the way in which the path is forged) – which hampers proper theory-building according to the authors. Pathways, in their view, are shaped by 'navigational actions' (p. 54). This overlaps with the main idea of 'strategising' found in the present report: finding out how to go in some direction, and even more reflexively, where to go. In the popular aphorism, strategies are about 'doing the right things', instead of 'doing the things right'. Stripple & Bulkeley are interested in scrutinising 'how [pathways] are assembled and congealed', i.e. how messy processes of power create conditions for certain (kinds of) pathways. In their work, pathways act as narratives and as 'governance assemblages', which rather serve descriptive and interpretive purposes than contributing to prescriptive knowledge on 'how to strategise', which we prefer.

Still, power is a critical and pivotal element (Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016). Fazey et al. (2016) use pathway analysis to understand how different social groups experience and perceive transformation (p. 41). One social group will have a different storyline of how the past developed into the present and how it is likely or desirable to continue developing. This is, again, more relevant for an *understanding* of transformations, less for *strategising* about them. An important take-away, however, is that pathways are not only normative, but also power-laden: dominant discourses around pathways 'validate the strategies and practices of those who were better positioned in society' (p. 39). This applies in general but also in transformative contexts – i.e. some tales about transformation, even toward just and biodiversity-inclusive futures, may overlook or overpower alternative (marginalised) pathways.

Pathways as ideal-types for strategic action

Further uses of the term 'pathway' tend to be more ideal-typical, and can help inform strategic action. For instance, Gibson et al. (2019) outline two main strategic 'modes of action': either operating *within* the framework of incumbent power structures or working towards *disruption* of these structures to reach transformation by means of 'resistance, campaigning, establishment of alternative systems' (Gibson et al. 2019:94). In a similar vein and drawing on a theoretical foray into Theories of Change and how networks navigate these, Westerink et al. (2025) distinguish three transformative pathways for social networks: *collaborate*, *challenge* and *disrupt*. They highlight that while all three pathways are likely to be required for transformative change, single actors or networks will not be able to pursue each of them, or it won't be their 'style' to (e.g.) disrupt or to collaborate. Therefore, networking strategies will allow actors to engage with other actors and networks

whose ways of working can complement them. What turns collaborate—challenge—disrupt into *pathways*, then, is the strategic (if->then) and contingent (this->thus) nature.

Termeer et al. (2024) identify three key components of transformative change; *depth*, *scope* and *pace* (see also Strasser et al., 2020). *Depth* signifies 'radical' change, targeting not only surface-level practices but also underlying drivers within a system. *Scope* relates to broad-scale changes that encompass the entire system or society, thus covering many actors and stakeholders, sectors, levels and dimensions. *Pace* refers to time aspects and potential speed of the process of change, whether this can take place abruptly, episodically (progression through different phases; 'slow emergence, acceleration, and stabilisation' (p 2)) or continuously (Termeer et al., 2024). While all three components (depth, scope and pace) are argued to be required to fulfil requirements of transformative change, according to Termeer et al. (2024) it is not possible to simultaneously attain them all. Indeed, trading off depth (radical change), scope (broad change encompassing entire systems) and pace (fast change) against each other is a necessary part of developing transformative governance strategies if these are to have any realistic changes of being successful. This is also a likely reason why there is little evidence of transformative change in sustainability efforts so far. However, it is argued that it is possible to devise governance approaches that pursue two out of three components (in different combinations) as an initial step, to be followed by the third component as a later step (Termeer et al., 2024).

Termeer et al.'s (2024) three key dimensions of transformation – *depth*, *scope* and *pace* – form, when combined in pairs, the basis of three 'archetypical governance pathways' that can be pursued to attain transformative change: each with its own set of risks, suitability etc. (Termeer et al., 2024). First, *Rule Changes* starts with a quick (pace) and system-wide (scope) changes (e.g. changes in incentive structures) intended to generate behavioural change. If successful, the approach can then gradually develop beyond the superficial level (depth) through 'cascading changes'. Second, *Big Plans* approaches are based on initial emphasis on depth and scope – aiming towards profound system change – which can then be slowly implemented over time (pace). Third, *Small Wins* are based on an initial focus on *depth* and *pace* in the form of quickly implemented grassroots experiments and other local level innovations, which can potentially in a later phase be scaled up to transform the system as a whole (*scope*). In other words, transformative change can take the form of small, incremental changes based around a vision that addresses underlying causes of, for example, biodiversity loss. These can later be rolled out more broadly and transferred to other contexts. Thus, small scale initiatives can hold major transformative potential if they succeed in stimulating system-wide changes (Termeer et al., 2024).

A key advantage of small-scale grassroots innovations is how they tend to build bottom-up from local/contextual knowledge, thereby ensuring a good problem-to-solution fit and flexibility (Seyfang & Smith 2007). Also, according to IPBES/O'Brien et al. (2024), case studies based on clear visions tend to outperform those who lack this component and thus have higher transformative potential. Compared to one singular 'big wins', accumulated 'small wins' are more robust and likely to support the development of 'desired path dependencies' (Termeer & Dewulf 2019:207), especially over time (Patterson et al 2017). The 'small wins' approach is also advocated by Bours et al., (2021). Small wins is a concept increasingly used in connection to governance, was originally defined as 'concrete, completed, implemented outcomes of moderate importance' (Weick 1984 cited in Termeer & Dewulf 2019:299) which when accumulated can amount to significant advances and, ultimately, transformative change. On a general level, small-scale grassroots initiatives

aiming to strengthen and/or recover biodiversity conditions can be placed within an overarching strategic approach of experimentalism, which differ from, and have developed in reaction to, absolutist (elitist/top-down) approaches (Meyer 2023). As for BIOTraCes, small wins is the approach most in line with the case studies within the project.

Termeer et al.'s (2024) abovementioned 'archetypical' governance pathways are associated with differently focused governance strategies. *Big Plans* require substantial efforts to develop the plans and organise/mobilise leverage to support their implementation. *Rule Changes* necessitates devising, implementing and continuously upgrading new incentive structures. *Small Wins* emphasises supporting and accumulating small scale local initiatives so that these may reach a critical threshold of transformative potential. While each initiative is of limited importance and scope, there is potential strength in numbers through accumulation and diffusion beyond the local scale through various mechanisms (Termeer et al., 2024). As mentioned, Small Wins best resonates with the BIOTraCes cases: examples of local and relational innovation with potential to scale out to larger contexts.

3.6 Strategic action for transformative change

Our use of the term transformative strategy is rooted in a layered understanding of how change unfolds and can be directed. Strategies are not simply predefined plans but patterns of action, sometimes explicit and sometimes embedded in practice, that seek to influence systems in ways that are deep, sustained, and far-reaching. Strategies are consequential. They entail choices in favour of certain approaches foreclosing the opportunity to do other things. Some strategies are mutually compatible and even reinforcing; other strategies are mutually exclusive. Strategies that work well together may be part of transformative pathways or ToTCs. They may be declared strategies or tacit. Strategies for transformations and biodiversity innovations cannot be neatly broken down into tactics and operations. Yet, the hierarchical view of strategies does give us cues on what level and importance should/could be ascribed to strategies. In this section, we examine the characteristics, variations, and contexts of transformative strategies, and how they operate across different scales and time horizons.

Organisational strategy literature has long been dominated by corporate strategy focusing on corporate management and business strategies. Realising that management under complex conditions is highly recursive, 'strategy as practice' (SAP) emerged in the 2000s (Jarzabkowski, 2004; Jarzabkowski et al., 2025). SAP treats strategy as something that people *do* rather than something that organisations *have*. The SAP literature explores how strategies emerge in dynamic contexts. Most of it has focused on organisational and/or corporate settings, but multi-actor contexts have also been discussed. SAP engages the 'sociological eye' (Whittington 2007). This aligns strongly with the relational perspective advocated in TSI and adopted here.

While the practice of SAP has been well explored, insight about what makes something strategic has lagged behind (Seidl et al., 2024). Seidl et al. distinguish four views of what qualifies activities as strategic: (1) *activities that have important consequences*; (2) *activities that are labelled strategic*; (3) *activities conducted by strategists*; and (4) *activities that perform an important recurrent pattern*. Each of these views has potential and limitations. Views 2 and 3 are narrower and suggest explicit strategists and strategies, while Views 1 and 4 are broader and suggest strategies' qualities in impact and persistence.

3.7 Innovation scaling

Transformative innovations are highly diverse, but share a goal of providing alternatives to incumbent structures that are considered unsustainable in terms of e.g. biodiversity, resource management, climate change or social equity. Over time, pressures on incumbent structures and regimes can destabilise them, thus generating a window of opportunity for change. Transformative innovations differ from conventional innovation and innovation policy through their critical approach to the current state and system-altering ambitions. This is in contrast with incremental approaches that refine and optimise incumbent system and thus may generate path dependency or even lock-ins that are difficult to reverse (Loorbach et al. 2020).

Scaling of innovation processes entail several foci. A typology of three approaches to scaling distinguishes between *scaling out*, i.e. quantitative growth and replication in other places/contexts; *scaling up*, i.e. formal embedding, institutional change, changes in policy and legislation; and *scaling deep* i.e. changes in values, paradigms and cultural features (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024; Moore et al. 2015). A combination of all of these is likely necessary to achieve major systemic change (Moore et al. 2015). The concept of scale can also be interpreted in diverse ways; referring to *spatial* scale (i.e. local to global), *network* scale (i.e. small/medium/large), *innovation* scale (i.e. development stage of maturity of innovations), *administrative or jurisdictional* scale (i.e. from municipal to European) and *institutional* scale (i.e. rules, frameworks, standards, policies, directives and laws with different weight and formal status) (Hermans et al. 2016). The concept is also relevant in relation to *temporal* scale (e.g. duration, frequency); *management* scale (specific asks, larger projects, broader strategies), (social) *network* scale (family, kin, society, trans-society) and *knowledge* scale (from specific and contextual to general and universal) (Cash et al. 2006).

Upscaling of transformative innovations is strongly related to innovation diffusion and adoption which is an inherently geographical process. As argued by Rekers (2016), the societal importance of an innovation depends on its reception and uptake, not least across diverse geographical contexts. Unless innovations are accepted and applied more widely, i.e. beyond their original site of development, they will not contribute significantly to broader societal change (Rekers 2016). Wide-scale adoption of innovations can be understood as a 'socially contagious' process, where potential adopters' decisions are influenced through their social networks as well as through other mechanisms such as media (Lengyel et al. 2020).

In addition to being a social process, innovation diffusion also has significant spatial connotations (Rekers 2016). Innovation diffusion theory posits that innovation adoption tends to initiate in major urban agglomerations, not least those located close to places where the innovation takes hold at an early stage. In later stages, diffusion continues also to smaller localities, especially those in close proximity to previous adopters (Lengyel et al. 2020; Hägerstrand 1967). Also, intermediary actors/organisations (located in-between innovators and adopters in the innovation system) play a significant part in brokering, legitimising and validating the innovation, thus supporting its adoption and the diffusion process. These intermediaries serve to connect the gaps in cases where the actors and stakeholders involved differ in background, interests and priorities, institutional logics and language (Rekers 2016).

The transformative potential of innovations depends on the extent to which they are applied and integrated more generally within society; a process which requires 'some form

of mainstreaming, diffusion, scaling, institutionalisation and/or translation' (Smith 2007; Pel 2016 cited in Loorbach et al. 2020:253). This would also require new forms of governance, since the current forms of governance are assumed to be geared to uphold and reproduce incumbent structures. Also, diffusion of innovations may occur regardless of whether this is part of the actors' intentions from the onset. However, the spread – and thus the transformative potential of the innovation – is also dependent on the actors' strategic abilities in terms of e.g. relating to other innovation initiatives in trans-local networks through which knowledge and ideas circulate. Such connections can be empowering and help build critical mass behind advocacy for policy change (Loorbach et al. 2020).

Strategies for upscaling are key aspects of the overall strategic approach. Loorbach et al. (2020) present a typology of generic strategies and mechanisms through which transformative innovations develop and diffuse, based on findings from EU-funded research projects. First, *Growing* refers to quantitative increase in participation or funding (as a result of e.g. successful communication efforts). Second, *Replicating* is cross-contextual transferral of the innovation, facilitated e.g. through media coverage. Third, *Partnering* involves cooperation and resource pooling with other comparable initiatives. Fourth, *Instrumentalising* concerns identifying and making use of opportunities within the governance/bureaucratic setting. Finally, *Embedding* relates to institutionalisation/mainstreaming of innovations; the process through which the innovation becomes the norm. Starting with small scale, local initiatives, innovations may diffuse through these mechanisms, including for example being reapplied in new contexts (Loorbach et al. 2020).

One key aspect – and challenge – related to governance towards transformative change is the need for analysis and evaluation e.g. to identify whether transformative change has occurred, since there are not necessarily clear indicators or tipping points to lean on. Also, the lack of historic precedents makes it difficult to identify the key characteristics of early and later stages of ongoing processes of transformative change (Patterson et al. 2017). Chan et al. (2020:694) also underscore the importance of not 'simply scaling-up of sustainability initiatives'; and that transformative change requires targeting those leverage points with most potential to trigger change.

The Small Wins approach is well in line with the how IPBES/O'Brien et al. (2024) understand the development of transformative change: as a gradual process that occurs over time and wherein '*seemingly small changes that address the underlying causes can spread in ways that inspire of influence larger and systemic shifts, especially when they overcome barriers and challenges*' (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024:23). Many Small Wins initiatives are of experimental character and so they offer 'possibilities – not guarantees' (Meyer 2023:3). Outcomes of experiments are uncertain. However, even 'failed' experiments may nevertheless contribute to fruitful subsequent efforts. Moreover, experimentalism has potential to serve as a foundation for building networks and 'alliances' which can be mobilised e.g. for spreading and scaling-up new knowledge to other geographical-administrative/jurisdictional levels: intra-urban/local, inter-urban/regional, national, international/macro-regional or global. (Meyer 2023).

The accumulation of efforts through Small Wins holds significant transformative potential (Termeer et al. 2024; Termeer & Dewulf 2019). However, this potential presupposes that 'propelling mechanisms' with the ability to augment the impact of the Small Wins are in place so that an initial minor impact gradually gains momentum and scale through

feedback loops/virtuous cycles (provided that a connection to supportive policy processes is in place) (Termeer & Dewulf 2019).

Termeer & Dewulf (2019) identify five mechanisms for diffusing and scaling up Small Wins. *Energising* focuses on a sense of motivation and of making a difference that can trigger subsequent initiatives). *Learning by doing* concerns identification of possibilities and challenges through small scale experimentation and iterative learning. *Logic of attraction* is based on the observation that having attained a small win facilitates raising resources for additional attempts, potentially resulting in accumulation of many small – and somewhat larger – wins). The *Bandwagon effect* emphasises how Small Wins that are made visible can serve as inspiration for others to engage in similar initiatives, increasing the potential for overall momentum). Finally, *Coupling* concerns e.g. loosely connected events taking place in different areas or systems and across scales, which can generate synergies (Termeer & Dewulf 2019).

Strategising and scaling efforts aiming towards systemic change is a challenge, not least in terms of management, leadership, organisational issues and social dynamics (Moore 2015). Moreover, evaluation of potential impacts of applying strategies to reduce a wicked problems is notoriously difficult, which also entails a risk of 'paralysis' in facing the problem (Termeer & Dewulf 2019). Scaling of initiatives also depends on the ability to handle the barriers which are in place in the particular context of the initiative. If these can be dealt with successfully, this also opens up for upscaling (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024).

3.8 Key take-aways

- *Transformative change* is systemic and non-linear. It entails deep, broad, and often long-term shifts going beyond incremental reforms to address root causes of biodiversity loss and sustainability crises.
- Environmental challenges such as biodiversity loss are *wicked problems* – complex, contested, and without clear solutions – and require transformative approaches.
- Geographical and institutional *context* matter. Local and multi-scalar socio-spatial dynamics, institutional logics, and governance arrangements in different sectors shape both opportunities and barriers.
- *Strategies* exist at multiple levels and can be understood as patterns of intentional activity that can be explicit or implicit, structured/designed or emergent.
- *Theories of Transformative Change* (ToTCs) and pathways offer complementary perspectives and share a focus on providing roadmaps for transformative futures. ToTCs provide explicit causal frameworks, while pathways are more flexible and acknowledge multiple routes to transformation.
- Conceiving pathways as strategic repertoires or as bundles of strategies can enrich our understanding of strategising and be useful in the analysis of cases within widely varied geographical and institutional contexts, while also acknowledging the wide variation in how pathways are defined in the literature.
- Pathways are path-dependent. However, while some pathways are conflicting or mutually exclusive, other pathways may be combined ('navigated' or 'woven'). This requires concerted action within networks of networks. There is potential e.g. in Westerink et al.'s (2025) *collaborate/challenge/disrupt* framework as complementary modes of interaction that can be strategically woven.

- *Pathways* highlight the existence of alternative options or conducts, some of which may be overlooked or even marginalised. Social movements may specifically address 'blind spots' in their strategies.
- Pathways can be constructed from working hypotheses about how and why activities and strategies might contribute to desired changes, and as such assist the construction of Theories of Transformative Change (Marciniak et al., 2024:3) including explication of causal links, mechanism and assumptions (Dhillon & Vaca, 2018; Mayne, 2017; but see Reinholz & Andrews, 2020).
- *Transformative governance* requires approaches that are simultaneously integrative, inclusive, adaptive, and pluralist; thereby serving to combine diverse knowledges, engage marginalised groups, and address entrenched power relations that often resist change.
- Strategies face tensions and trade-offs. *Depth, scope, and pace* of change cannot all be maximised simultaneously. Transformation involves balancing these, navigating resistance from incumbents, and combining diverse strategies (e.g., big plans, rule changes, Small Wins) to sustain progress
- *Leverage points* are key for transformative potential. While shallow leverage points (e.g. regulations, incentives) can spark incremental change, deep leverage points (e.g. institutions, values) are crucial for system-wide transformations, though harder to reach.
- *Scaling* is multidimensional and multidirectional. Transformative innovations can scale out (replication, geographical diffusion of innovations), up (institutional embedding), and deep (cultural/value shifts). Transformation often requires interplay across these forms of scaling, supported by governance and networks.
- *Small wins* can accumulate into big change. Experimental, local initiatives provide learning, motivation, and legitimacy. When diffused through mechanisms like energising, attraction, and coupling, they can generate momentum for broader systemic transformation. Small wins is the pathway most akin to the type of transformation (and transformative thinking) in BIOTraCes.

3.9 References

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4 Methods and materials³

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4.1 Methodological approach

Cross-case analysis

Case study-based research takes as its point of departure in-depth study and analysis of a specific case to build more general knowledge also concerning other cases (Gerring 2007 cited in Fletcher et al. 2015). Nevertheless, case study research is often rather limited in terms of its potential for more general theoretical development; mainly providing case-specific knowledge. Conducting comparisons across cases and case studies is a way of drawing broader insights, not least on 'variable-oriented' knowledge related to specific issues and themes (Pahl-Wostl et al. 2021). Compared to single-case studies, multi-case studies have the advantage of potentially being able to identify and draw insights on themes and features of relevance across diverse contexts (Fletcher et al. 2015).

Diversity within a multi-case setup can generate challenges for cross-case analysis (Fletcher et al. 2015; During et al. 2023). The BIOTraCes case studies can be understood as '*multiple-multiples*' (Raschke et al. 2023) given the many cases and their respective variations in terms of foci, design, methods, materials and approaches. They involve multiple stakeholders across different sectors and levels, and in several cases also have nested structures (several cases within the case). Thus, cross-case analysis to some extent becomes a matter of 'comparing apples and oranges'. To manage this analytical problem, and given the focus of WP3, we have chosen the approach of focusing on *strategies* implemented in the respective cases as principal unit of analysis (rather than e.g. stakeholders or the biodiversity initiatives as such).

Unlike the BIOTraCes case study research teams, the WP3 tasks are not directly involved in field research or analysis of data from the cases (although WP3 team members are involved in varying degrees in several of the case studies through their work in other BIOTraCes WP2 tasks). Rather, the WP3 tasks are focused specifically on analysis on the cross-case level through identification of patterns for the composite set of cases. Our ambition is to draw out broader lessons from case studies embedded in their specific contexts without oversimplifying⁴. Ideally, a cross-case analysis should identify 'what works, for whom, in what circumstances, and why? /.../ and, in recognition of the

³ Note on D3.2 in relation to suggestions in the previous report D1.8: The overall approach followed in WP3 is in line with the methods discussed and suggested in the D1.8 report. In this report During et al. (2023) differentiate between synthesis and cross-case analysis. D1.8 targets WP1-2-3, and its recommendations mainly concern synthesis, which is primarily done at the case study level, i.e. in WP2. WP3 is mainly about cross-case analysis of the case studies, i.e. emphasising various aspects of strategies and approaches across the set of case studies. WP3 nevertheless considers many aspects raised in D1.8, e.g. the importance of relations and power dynamics, and identifying systemic influences that shape strategies. However, discussion in D1.8 about extracting 'proof' for Theories of Transformative Change is more relevant for WP1 (partly based on input from WP3/D3.2).

⁴ A criticism sometimes voiced regarding qualitative analytical approaches such as thematic analysis concerns decontextualisation (e.g. van den Berg 2005) through an analytical process that entails open coding and hence breaking the data up into small pieces/taking it apart to be able to reconstruct it/put it together again in a new way.

importance of learning from failure: what does not work, for whom, in which circumstances, and why not?’ (Cockburn et al. 2020: no page).

At the time of writing, the biodiversity initiatives are still unfolding in different stages of development within the BIOTraCes case studies. This, together with the abovementioned substantial differences between them, calls for caution in drawing conclusions and making ‘deep generalisations on the basis of all cases’ (Suškevičs 2012:235). Moreover, in the process of cross-case analysis, we have been aware of the challenges in relation to specificity and generalisation, respectively. We provide summaries with basic information for the cases ([Brief introduction to the case studies](#)) and include illustrative quotes to ensure that sufficient contextual information is provided to make sense of the analytical results (Stake 2006, cited in Fletcher et al. 2015).

4.2 Materials and data collection methods

Background, approach and motivation (T3.1-4)

The tasks of BIOTraCes WP3 require that information is collected from the WP2 case studies at the heart of the project. Meaningful cross-case analysis requires a certain degree of harmonisation across the case studies to allow for comparative analysis of key themes for BIOTraCes as a whole. However, WP3 does not engage directly with the empirical data from the case studies. The WP3 team acknowledges that it is the prerogative, responsibility and mandate of the respective research teams to gather the necessary data and perform analysis within each case study, including case-specific synthesis with attention to complexities and contextual specificities.

In contrast, the WP3 cross case analysis is based on *results* from the case studies, focusing on particular themes and issues according to the foci of the different WP3 tasks. One methodological question in cross-case analysis is the choice of data upon which to base the analysis, for instance raw data or pre-analysed case study reports (Fletcher et al. 2015). As mentioned, using raw data from the case studies is not our preferred option, not least given the application of PAR methodology in most of the case studies – and the trust issues and research ethics inherent therein – sharing raw data outside the case study team was not considered the most appropriate (or efficient) approach.

One slight complication derives from how the BIOTraCes project was designed in terms of its timeline. The final WP2 case study reports are due to be delivered at the same time as WP3 cross-case analysis, and thus these reports are not available as a basis for our analyses. A different approach to data collection is therefore called for. WP3 is based on its own primary data collected through interactive engagement with the WP2 research teams responsible for each case study. They effectively act as informants for their respective cases given their in-depth knowledge and ability to represent the case participants (societal partners) and their voices/perspectives. This approach also means that the participatory link to the cases is an indirect one, mediated through the BIOTraCes researchers and their analyses, interpretations and narrative framings of the cases.

Data collection from the case studies for use in WP3 is carried out through a series of interactive and linked activities involving WP2 and WP3. Tasks 3.1-3.4 takes a joint approach with coordinated data collection, while T3.5 takes a separate approach⁵.

Interviews (T3.1-4)

Qualitative interviews with the research team informants representing the nine case studies were conducted during 2025; a first round in February and a second in June-July-September (see [Annex B](#) and [Annex C](#)). An iterative approach was chosen to follow the cases as they progress and evolve over time. The first round of interviews was conducted mid-term into the case study processes, and the second at a slightly later stage. The issues addressed were adapted accordingly, so that e.g. issues related to outcomes were covered during the second round. Nevertheless, at this point the case studies were not yet finalised, and conclusions were yet to be drawn.

The interviews followed a semi-structured approach, thereby ensuring coverage of key issues for T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4, while also allowing some inclusion of additional themes and follow-ups. However, time for in-depth probing was limited. The duration of the interviews was approximately 90 minutes (prearranged maximum time) in each round for each case study. In the two rounds of interviews, three hours of interview material was collected for each case study (out of which approximately 40 minutes covered each for T3.1-4). In total three hours of interview material was collected for each case and 27 hours for all nine cases. During the interviews, time was equally distributed across the participating tasks (T3.1-4). The research teams were represented by at least one (often several) informant/s with deep insights into the case. The interviews were conducted digitally using Microsoft Teams, and documented with video and audio recording. Microsoft Teams provided automatically generated transcripts of the material. However, while these transcripts were relatively accurate, they nonetheless were not of acceptable quality. Therefore, the transcripts were carefully read and cross-checked against the recorded interviews by the WP3 team to ensure accuracy and safeguard data quality.

During the interviews, an interview guide prepared by the participating WP3 task leaders provided structure and a point of departure. Before the interviews, the interview guide was sent to the informants, who were encouraged to read and reflect upon the questions, preferably as a joint activity within the research teams (i.e. not necessarily only those persons who participated in the interviews proper). In addition to generating prerequisites for high quality material from the interviews, this procedure was also intended to make the interview situation more 'efficient', given the relatively short time available for each task. The ambition was that this exercise be beneficial both for the interview content (WP3) and for the case study analysis (WP2). The interview guide was developed in collaboration within T3.1-4. A draft interview guide was tested bilaterally among the WP3 task leaders (T3.1/T3.2; T3.3/T3.4) prior to finalisation, a procedure which resulted in some minor adjustments (e.g. clarifications and reduction of the number of questions to be covered given the restricted time frame of the interviews).

⁵ T3.5 deliverables were due earlier than the present report, before data collection for T3.1-4 had even commenced and hence could not take part in the joint approach.

Methodological reflections on the interviews

The interviews proceeded with well-functioning organisation and cooperation among the hosts and well-prepared informants who had all reflected on the questions in the interview guide beforehand. Distributing the interview guide ahead of the interviews together with encouragement to discuss and reflect within the case study teams was likely a key prerequisite to manage to conduct the interviews within the relatively brief time frame of 90 min per interview, covering four main areas each with its own set of questions – all related to strategies and approaches but nevertheless with different foci. The interview time slots allowed roughly 20 minutes per task in each interview, allowing very little time for follow-ups and probes. However, the time was nevertheless sufficient to cover the questions in the interview guide.

The interviews were conducted in English, a second language for most participants (interviewers and interviewees alike), but one of which all have excellent working command. However, it cannot be ruled out that minor language related miscommunication/lack of clarity may have occurred.

The interviews generated narratives of the case studies as interpreted by the research teams. Through subsequent analyses, these accounts are then filtered again through the process of interpretation by the WP3 team. This means that the results presented in the present report are distant from the empirical level of the cases. However, given the aims of the WP3 cross-case analysis and hence abstraction this does not present any major concerns, but it should nonetheless be noted. Also, there is of course, always a risk that layered accounts (narratives of narratives) can turn into a game of 'Chinese whispers'. Yet, our overall assessment is that the informants have provided transparent and nuanced accounts of the respective cases, raising both strengths and weaknesses.

The overall design of the interviews entailed somewhat unusual situation colleagues effectively interviewing each other – either colleagues within the BIOTraCes consortium or even colleagues within the same organisations. The interviews had several participants, both a 'panel' representing the four WP3 tasks and the case study team informants. There were more interviewers than interviewees. Here, the project-internal setting and prior acquaintance of the interview participants likely reduced the risk of problematic dynamics stemming from power differences as might otherwise arise in one/few-to-many situations.

Workshops, focus group discussions (T3.1-4)

Data were also collected through workshops similar to focus group discussions (see [Annex D](#)). These were conducted face-to-face at the project consortium meeting in Hungary in May 2025. Contrary to the interviews, the focus groups mixed participants representing different case study research teams to create opportunity for exchange of experience and reflection. The workshop was organised as a 'world café' style discussion, The groups of informants (5-6 people per group) rotated around between four tables, each hosted by the task leader/s for T3.1-4 who had prepared one of a few questions for discussion for 30 minutes. In total, the material from the discussions amount to two hours per task. The discussions were audio recorded and later transcribed by each task leader.

Monitoring forms (T3.1-4)

As a complement to the WP3-specific activities, data were additionally collected through the monitoring forms coordinated by WP2 (see [Annex A](#)) in December 2024. The forms included a section with one question each for T3.1-4 for the case study research teams to answer. Most answers were provided in open-ended qualitative format, and for one question in quantified format. The informants were encouraged to provide elaborate, detailed answers to the questions. Because these questions were posed in monitoring forms and therefore without opportunity to follow up- probe or clarify, the questions were formulated to not require immediate elaboration. The data collected through the monitoring forms were used both for direct analysis and as part of the preparation for the subsequent interviews. Through these answers, the interviewers had a good pre-understanding for key issues of the cases pertaining to the respective WP3 tasks to use as a point of departure for the interactive data collection.

Survey on sustainable development goals (T3.5)

In November 2024, the MRU team conducted a survey across all BIOTraCes project partners to explore how Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are understood and enacted within diverse biodiversity-related contexts. The survey followed an internal literature review on SDGs and was designed by the MRU team. The instrument was further refined through discussions within Task 3.5 on Biodiversity Interdependencies of SDGs (UGOT, BC3, UBB, CER, WR).

The main survey ([Annex E](#)), distributed among the nine case study teams from eight European countries, combined closed and open-ended questions and invited each team to reflect collectively on how SDGs emerged—or failed to emerge—in their day-to-day work with communities. Questions were both analytical and creative in nature, culminating in a visual mapping task carried out through Google Drawings ([Annex G](#)). This task encouraged respondents to illustrate the interconnections between biodiversity and specific SDGs as they manifest in their case studies. A sliding scale (from 1 to 10) was used to capture perceptions of SDG relevance and interdependencies, while open-ended and multiple-choice questions allowed participants to elaborate on their reasoning and local experiences.

Research teams could either complete the survey collectively or delegate one member to represent the team's joint perspective. The survey targeted researchers working on participatory action research projects in fields such as sustainable farming and herding practices, forest management, river biodiversity conservation, food production, urban greening, and sustainable lifestyles (see [Brief introduction to the case studies](#)/Chapter 2). The diversity of these cases created ideal conditions to observe how the SDGs' relevance and meaning shift across highly contextual and heterogeneous environments. All invited teams responded, resulting in full coverage across the consortium.

To complement the researcher survey, a shorter and more targeted version ([Annex F](#)) was shared with societal partners, yielding 11 responses representing six case studies. These responses captured locally grounded perspectives and experiences with biodiversity-related SDG implementation. In both surveys, participants were asked to express their own interpretations rather than repeat formal definitions, emphasising lived experiences and context-specific insights.

Survey responses were analysed descriptively, and qualitative input was reviewed thematically to identify converging patterns and contextual nuances across cases. The survey outputs are provided in the annex for transparency and reference.

This method offered a grounded view of how SDGs take shape within practical biodiversity work, extracting common challenges and context-specific insights across the consortium.

Note on research ethics

WP3 follows the BIOTraCes data management plan, which states that 'The project will follow the principle of responsible research and innovation and will comply with The Brussels Declaration: Ethics and Principles for Science & Society Policy-Making, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in all stages of the project, from the research design to the dissemination of the research output. When necessary other research ethic-relevant regulations will be complied with' (Balundè et al. 2023:21).

In the case of WP3, which is led by UGOT, any data managed by UGOT must also comply with the Swedish Ethical Review Act (the national research ethics legislation). Ethical threshold analysis (initial risk and vulnerability analysis) has therefore been conducted (dnr GU 2024/1199) at the Departmental Research Ethics Committee at UGOT/Dept of Economy and Society; and concluded that further ethical review is not necessary.

WP3 does not focus on collection of (sensitive) personal data but rather research results from the case studies at a more aggregated level. Nevertheless, to reduce the risk that such material might emerge inadvertently, participants were asked during the interviews to not reveal personal information about individuals.

4.3 Methods for qualitative analysis (T3.1-4)

Combination of collaborative/joint and task-specific approaches

The WP3 material is extensive, complex and rich, and therefore each task has needed to focus on those parts that were specifically dedicated to it, i.e. the parts of e.g. interview transcripts that cover the task-specific questions. However, since task-relevant data can potentially scattered be throughout the material, analysts were also encouraged to flag to each other in such instances, and to also make sure to have an overview of the entire material. Concerning the interviews, many of the task leaders participated in most of these occasions, which also provides a stable basis in terms of insight into the material.

The analysis for T3.1-4 combines certain elements, described below, as a joint approach. This is complemented with task-specific approaches chosen by each research team (see the following chapters for each task for additional methodological details). The chosen unit of analysis is the strategies implemented by the stakeholders/actors in the cases. Focusing on strategies provides a workable solution to the problem of 'comparing apples and oranges' that otherwise emerges from the substantial differences between the case studies. Focus is primarily on strategies implemented by main stakeholders within the cases, specifically the 'societal partners' or active BIOTraCes partners (i.e. not all potential stakeholders who are in some way involved in the context of the various cases).

Inductive-deductive thematic analysis

T3.1-4 used thematic analysis as a joint, main point of departure for the analyses of the collected data. Thematic analysis is a core method of qualitative analysis focused on searching for, identifying and analysing patterns in data. The method can be applied both inductively and deductively to qualitative materials, and it is flexible in terms of theoretical and epistemological points of departure, i.e. does not require taking particular positions (Braun & Clarke 2006; 2022). Thus, thematic analysis can be conducted in varied ways, but with a common analytical focus.

Thematic analysis involves a process of coding, categorisation and building themes. For WP3, the analysis is a hybrid approach that mixes inductive and deductive features (e.g. Fareday & Muir-Cochrane 2006). We combine searching for connections to theory and previous research (as to not 'reinvent the wheel' but build on incumbent knowledge) while retaining an openness to what is potentially new in the material, allowing it to reveal new, empirically grounded insights.

For additional detail about the analytical process for T3.1-4, see the respective chapters for each task.

Review of findings

Involving collaborators in the analytical process contributes to both research quality and legitimacy (Fletcher et al. 2015). Preliminary findings from the analyses of the first round of interviews and the monitoring forms were shared and discussed with the participants representing the different case studies at the project consortium meeting in Hungary in May 2025. For the second round of interviews, time limitations did not allow for such a dedicated occasion for discussion. Instead, participants were invited to review the results of the analyses of the collected material in its entirety (two rounds of interviews, monitoring forms and focus groups) in a 95% finished version of the present report in November 2025. The review resulted in various minor corrections and clarifications concerning the specific case studies.

WP3 will also discuss the findings with the BIOTraCes Influencer & Stakeholder Board. A workshop will be organised with in early 2026 to e.g. consider the potential of the identified strategies for public and private policy makers and change makers. WP3 is also planning to produce a separate policy brief with recommendations based on the findings of this D3.2 report in 2026.

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5 Opportunities for leverage and amplification (T3.1)

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5.1 Introduction

Task 3.1's contribution to this report consists of a list of opportunities of leverages identified in the nine BIOTraCes case studies. This chapter remains on the more descriptive level and builds the base for report D3.1, that will synthesise and analyse both opportunities for leverage and upscale emerging in local and institutional contexts and root causes of biodiversity loss and current barriers, lock-ins, and blockages constraining the local biodiversity innovations to better understand cross-scale dynamics at play currently enabling or hindering transformative change for biodiversity.

The **overall objective of this chapter is twofold**: first, **to identify opportunities for leverage**. Here, we interpret opportunities for leverage very broadly as those factors - social, political, economic, ecological or cultural - that facilitate transformative change. The **leverage points** can reach thereby in their transformative potential from shallower leverage points to deeper leverage points (Meadows 1999). Shallower leverage points refer to new practices and material processes closer aligned with deep human-nature relations, also referred to as the 'practical sphere'. Processes aiming for changes of the 'political sphere', the governance structures and rules of the system, represent deeper leverage points, while the deepest leverage points lie in those processes impacting the 'personal sphere', referring to paradigms, worldviews and values overcoming a human-nature distinction (O'Brien 2018).

Second, the chapter further provides **a list of opportunities for upscale** that have been **reinterpreted as amplification processes** and referring to those processes that increase the impact of biodiversity innovations. We re-interpret this task from upscaling to amplifying given that the 'solutionism' of scaling overlooks the relational processes required for trust-building, experimentation and co-creation (Pfothenauer, 2021). Following Lam et al. 2020 (p3), 'amplification processes describe diverse actions deployed by sustainability initiatives together with other actors (e.g., from government, business, or society) to purposely increase their transformative impact (e.g., initiating a new initiative in another city).'

We further draw on Lam et al. (2020)'s distinction of **three overarching amplification processes**, i.e., amplifying within, out, and beyond. *Amplifying within* refers to increasing the impact of one specific initiative or action in the local context, e.g. by stabilising it over the long term or by speeding it up. *Amplifying out* describes processes that increase impact by leaving the initial context and community, and involving other places, such as spreading or replicating a specific initiative elsewhere. *Amplifying beyond* refers to both a scaling up, that is, achieving change in higher policy scales, and scaling deep by impacting values, worldviews, and broader paradigms (Lam et al. 2020).

5.2 Methods of analysis

We draw on data received through the two rounds of interviews conducted in the framework of WP3, the WP3 workshop at the project live meeting in Hungary 2025, and the case study reports (D2.5) written by the respective partners in WP2 (see [Methods and materials](#) for more detail). We coded these documents in Nvivo based on an inductive approach, looking for (i) amplification processes, i.e., processes achieving an increase of impact, with sub-codes of amplifying within, out, and beyond, and (ii) opportunities for leverages divided into the codes of practices and material processes as leverage; structure, governance, rules; and paradigms, worldviews, and values.

5.3 Key findings

Table 5-1 shows the key leverage points identified in the nine BIOTraCes case studies. They range from shallower to deeper reaching leverage points, including processes and actions that can leverage through shifting practices and material processes, through changing governance structures and rules, to those that can serve as leverages for embedding relational paradigms, worldviews, and values more attentive to closer human-nature relations.

Table 5-2 shows those amplification processes that are already happening or that hold great potential to be implemented in future, as identified by consortium partners. Those amplification processes can broadly be clustered into amplifying within, out, and beyond following Lam et al. (2020). We expanded Lam et al. (2020)'s classification with subcategories specific to the BIOTraCes case studies.

Table 5-1: Opportunities for leverage

Abbreviations of case studies: Dutch Foodpark case: NL-FP, Romanian case: RO, Hungarian case: HU, Portuguese case: PT, Lithuanian case: LT, Italian case: IT, Spanish case: ES, Swedish case: SE, Dutch eco-village case: NL-EV; Dutch Province case: NL-P

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
PRACTICAL SPHERE: PRACTICES & ECOLOGICAL PROCESSES	Ecological processes	Natural processes requiring adaptation	ES: Urban heat islands triggering rethinking of schoolyards PT & IT: Desertification triggering rethinking of agricultural model HU: Traditional herding as essential to maintain grassland ecosystems
	Alternative economic practices	Creating economic infrastructure and markets for more sustainable livelihoods	RO: Promoting sustainable tourism and local traditional products, e.g., through village festivals selling local products from sustainable agriculture SE: Developing local infrastructure and markets for high-quality timber. IT: Renewable energy communities as a collective and local alternative to dependencies on big energy companies IT: Simeto Bio-district - a network of small organic farmers PT: Mértola Food Network
		Nature-connected and small-scale production practices	IT & PT: Agroecological production, e.g. through crop-diversification, short supply chains, and restoration of agricultural land through syntropic farming or permaculture

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
	Research practices & use of knowledge	Co-producing evidence base of social-ecological change for decision-making	IT: collaborative mapping of photovoltaic plants to make visible the scale, distribution, and socio-ecological impacts of industrial photovoltaic installations across the Valley
		Research workshops as spaces of dialogue enabling community building	ES: Space for educational communities to voice their opinions with municipal actors SE: Space for dialogue between forest owners on alternative forestry as first contact point
		Research activity as catalyst for awareness raising	LT: Research activity, e.g., interviews, to bring the local community's attention to the importance of river renaturalisation
		Leveraging scientific knowledge	PT: Creating a research centre to support innovation in biodiversity loss control ALL: using BIOTraCes outcomes as a form to leverage local biodiversity innovations

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
		<p>Enabling knowledge exchange</p>	<p>PT: The development agency ESDIME facilitates farmer-to-farmer exchange</p> <p>ES: the city hall organises conferences to exchange knowledge and practices regarding schoolyard transformations</p> <p>IT: Farmers are exchanging with experts regarding alternative agricultural practices</p> <p>HU & PT: Passing ecological knowledge from older to younger generations</p> <p>NL-P: The province is providing toolboxes and material regarding nature-inclusive building</p> <p>Successful practices as an inspiration for others to follow</p> <p>Successfully implemented initiatives serve as inspiration for others to follow</p> <p>NL-FP: potential: Winning the public tender (although for a much smaller area than planned) as inspiration for others to follow</p> <p>ES: A successful bottom-up schoolyard transformation in one of the city's schools has motivated other schools to follow</p> <p>ES: Successful municipal schoolyard greening programs from other cities, e.g. Barcelona, has inspired the municipal pilot program</p> <p>NL-EV: Potential: the collective land acquisition can set the path for other similar initiatives to follow</p>

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
<p>POLITICAL SPHERE: STRUCTURE, GOVERNANCE, RULES</p>	<p>Changing educational practices</p>	<p>Learning in nature to shift mindsets & capacities to address biodiversity loss</p>	<p>PT: School gardens shifting children's perceptions of agricultural production</p> <p>ES: Project-based learning in green schoolyards as a means to foster systems thinking and collaborative decision-making</p>
	<p>Supportive legal frameworks & policy tools</p>	<p>Embedding biodiversity innovation in legal frameworks across scales</p>	<p>LT: European Water framework directive and biodiversity strategy as a top-down enabler for local renaturalisation efforts such as renaturalisation of rivers</p> <p>NL-EV: Clashes between ambitious European and national (anti-) restoration goals as anchoring points for local innovation. De Beuk embedding local innovation in European Goals as a leverage against national policies</p> <p>ES: Embedding sustainability and new forms of embodied learning in national education laws and curriculum</p> <p>NL-EV: Creation and testing of municipal tools that provide the legal framework for biodiversity innovations to be implemented, such as the CPO policy</p> <p>NL-P: POTENTIAL: Private building sector demanding from policymakers a rating system for including nature-inclusivity in building programs, so that developers' efforts are recognised and lead to some benefits. This would further enable an easier integration through the creation of specific indicators</p> <p>NL-P: Creation of a biodiversity policy programs at the province level, such as the Community of Practice that provides grants to smaller local initiatives</p>

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
	Plural knowledge in decision-making	Integration of traditional/ local knowledge into decision-making	ES: Creation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program enabling schoolyard renaturalisation of 14 schools
			PT: Recognising lay people's knowledge in municipal decision-making has played pivotal role in changing the municipal mentality
			RO: POTENTIAL leveraging traditional ecological knowledge as potential base for policymaking
	Collaborations between institutional & non-institutional actors	Supportive institutions - Collaborations with authorities	HU: Upscaling traditional knowledge by researchers to inform national and European policy-making
			LT: Recognition of biodiversity challenges at the national level translate into political support (e.g., funding or policy support) for biodiversity innovation locally
			NL-FP: Local authorities starting to recognise biodiversity innovations, e.g. Amsterdam's donut economy approach reflects to an extent the social-ecological vision of Foodpark Amsterdam
		PT: Reducing economic risk involved in biodiversity innovation by providing support (funding, training) to make the shift towards more regenerative agriculture	
		ES: POTENTIAL- Setting standards for green schoolyards at the municipal level	

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
		Co-governance based on meaningful participation	PT: Co-governance between municipality and relevant actors leading to improved management of SES IT: Eco-museum as the outcome of a process of co-governance
		Institutional niche innovators	NL-P: civil servants of the province navigating institutional dynamics to pursue biodiversity goals ES: civil servants of the city-hall employing various strategies to funding and prolongation of the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program
	Bottom-up niche innovators	Innovations to overcome structural barriers	NL-EV, an association, started a landscape cooperative as cooperatives can acquire land, while associations cannot. This is to facilitate the collective land acquisition
		Bottom-up organisation, community, and network building	IT: Renewable energy communities as laboratories
			ES: Collective manifesto of all municipal parents' associations and school to demand changes for educational environments from the city hall
			SE: Collaboration between forest owners to exchange services needed for continuous cover forestry and push for change in organisations
		PT: Creating a food network to reduce dependence on external purchase	

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
PERSONAL SPHERE: IMAGINARIES & VALUES	Shifts in governments	New governments allow new discourses to emerge	NL's change in government shifted discourse from anti-nature towards one more inclusive of environmental policies.
	Imaginary shifts	<p>Changing the imaginary of the territory</p> <p>Challenging paradigms by creating social-ecological and locally rooted imaginaries and framing local initiatives as an alternative towards high impact sector 'wrongs'</p>	<p>IT: Shifting from modernist narrative of territory as underdeveloped to a relational narrative of the territory rooted in its history and culture</p> <p>PT: landscape with no future reframed to 'territory of regeneration'</p> <p>NL-FP: reframing Lutkemeer as a place enabling consumerism towards one centred on its biodiversity and the community</p> <p>NL-FP: Foodpark Amsterdam as a model of moving from extractivist, neoliberal to relational economic paradigms (e.g. the commons), by showing shortcomings of current economic paradigm (current model fails to support socio-ecological wellbeing)</p> <p>NL-P: Reframing nature from being a barrier (human vs nature) towards being a benefit and part of social systems. E.g. Nature not as an additional cost in the building sector, but as an integral part of building. The province also up took 'health' as an objective in their policy program, as this is more likely to be approved and supported in the current political climate than nature on its own</p> <p>NL-EV: large scale housing developments vs. small scale ecovillage; falsify the usual assumption that sustainable building in close harmony with nature is more expensive than using mainstream materials and procedures</p>

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
	Values		<p>ES: Emerging shifts from a modernist towards a relational educational paradigm in national laws and in local framings of schoolyard greening that include care and stewardship</p> <p>ES: Approaching schoolyard greening through three holistic goals of the renaturalised schoolyard's contribution to achieving sustainability, co-education and inclusivity</p> <p>IT: Challenging dominant sector paradigms, e.g. small-scale agroecological production vs. industrialised mono-cultures, or renewable energy communities vs. monopolised large-scale photovoltaic power plants</p> <p>PT: Regenerative farming as a way to counter agricultural practices driving desertification</p> <p>SE: Continuous cover forestry vs. monoculture forests</p>
		Research activity bringing marginalised human-nature relations to the fore	<p>IT: PAR led to a reinterpretation of traditional fishing and livestock practices, reframing them as important components of the local SES</p> <p>ES: multi-actor workshops gave space for relational perspectives of schoolyard greening to emerge</p>
		Leveraging relational values	<p>SE: People holding cultural and relational values attached to forests as a potential driver of transforming current extractivist practices</p> <p>ES. Green schoolyards as relational places that strengthen practices and sentiments of care and stewardship</p>

OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEVERAGE	Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
		<p>Generational change brings new values and can hence lead to new innovations</p>	<p>RO: Connection of oak trees with identity leveraging activities to protect them</p> <p>IT: Building upon an already existing sense of place and community in the Simeto Valley to amplify local initiatives</p> <p>IT: Activities and practices implemented by the eco-museum as a way to strengthen relational values</p> <p>SE: Succession as opportunities for alternative ideas on forestry</p> <p>PT & RO: Youths returning to rural areas and bringing biodiversity innovations</p> <p>HU: Opening a herder school to enable younger generations access to traditional knowledge and to keep it for the future.</p>

Table 5-2: *Increasing the biodiversity innovation’s impact by amplifying within, out, and beyond*

Abbreviations of case studies: Dutch Foodpark case: NL-FP, Romanian case: RO, Hungarian case: HU, Portuguese case: PT, Lithuanian case: LT, Italian case: IT, Spanish case: ES, Swedish case: SE, Dutch eco-village case: NL-EV; Dutch Province case: NL-P

Amplifying how?		Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
Within (the local context) through creating awareness and community surrounding the local innovation.	Creating awareness and spreading word about the biodiversity innovation locally.	SE: Slowly building community by bringing together individual actors through research activities, LT: Creating a community by sharing, communicating about the river renaturalisation.
		Co-producing local knowledge: Researchers as trustworthy knowledge brokers and facilitators within the local community.	LT: Amplifying plural voices: collecting existing local perspectives of the river from community members as a starting point to create awareness and open space for discussions locally, as first step trust-building. IT: Co-creating and sharing a social-ecological mapping of photovoltaic plants by involving local actors in the data collection and visualisation.
		Celebrating small wins and communication success stories (Energising - Termeer & Dewulf 2019).	NL-EV: Celebration of small wins that help De Beuk get closer to their goal of building an eco-village, also to maintain motivation and to communicate innovation to local communities.
		Creating local economic infrastructure and markets.	RO: sustainable tourism and branding of local products at local festivals, IT & PT: food and farmers networks, SE: Promoting high quality timber production.

Amplifying how?	Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
<p>... through deepened multi-actor collaborations.</p>	<p>Campaigning for the biodiversity innovation.</p> <p>Creating local communities, networks, and synergies that share goals of transformative change.</p>	<p>ES: bottom-up schoolyard transformation project campaigning for neighbourhood votes in the annual municipal participatory budget contest.</p> <p>SE: Communication and network building between forest owners interested in alternative practices.</p> <p>ES: Collective manifesto signed by all municipal public schools demanding the transformation of school environments and increased perception of importance of the biodiversity innovation.</p> <p>IT: Co-creation and management of social-ecological map and its database AND co-creation of Eco-museum diversifies actors involved and grows knowledge regarding biodiversity challenge within the local context.</p> <p>IT: Sharing own micro strategies of regenerative agriculture with other farmers and experts in the region helps to grow knowledge regarding alternative agricultural practices.</p> <p>HU: Connecting traditional herders to initiate knowledge exchange and to create a herders community.</p>

Amplifying how?	Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
	<p>Collaborating with local authorities/ increasing institutional recognition of the biodiversity innovation.</p>	<p>HU: Researchers collect data regarding immunisation of foxes from diverse actors, incl. hunters & institutions, to share it with low-and mid-level authorities, so they communicate with higher level authorities.</p> <p>ES: Presenting the collective manifesto for school transformations to the city hall led to the formulation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program.</p> <p>NL-FP: Winning a public tender for a plot of land that allows Foodpark Amsterdam to develop a part of their project.</p> <p>NL-EV: Collaborating with the municipality to advance and test policy tools that could set a precedent for future actions, such as the Collective Private Commissioning policy.</p>
	<p>Niche innovators advocating for biodiversity innovation from within the institutions</p>	<p>ES: municipal technical staff advocating inside the city hall for prolongation of schoolyard greening pilot program.</p> <p>NL-P: civil servants at the province creating novel policy programs for biodiversity.</p>
<p>... through learning by doing (Termeer & Dewulf 2019).</p>	<p>Agroecological experimentation.</p> <p>Pedagogical experimentation.</p>	<p>IT: Experimenting with different alternatives to monoculture</p> <p>NL-FP: Experimenting with commons-based approaches to agriculture</p> <p>IT & PT: Experimenting with agricultural techniques to regenerate the soil</p> <p>ES: Creating and sharing materials & methodologies with teachers for the use of renaturalised schoolyards in curricular and extracurricular activities</p>

Amplifying how?	Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
	<p>... through stabilising and speeding up (by doing the same biodiversity innovation longer or faster) (Lam et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Implementing pilots until they stabilise (logic of attraction - Termeer & Dewulf 2019)</p> <p>Integrating the biodiversity innovations into day-to-day practices to increase communities' capacities to enact change.</p> <p>Creation of municipal tools that enable replication of the biodiversity innovations.</p>
<p>Out (to other places and communities)...</p>	<p>... through building networks across different places and communities.</p>	<p>ES: From pilots to long-lasting programs: Replicating schoolyard greening in several schools, to achieve a critical mass showing the positive impact of the biodiversity innovations.</p> <p>NL-EV: De Beuk is applying to become a pilot for Nitrogen-free building, setting a precedent for nature-inclusive building close to nature reservoirs, showing that living in harmony with nature can be possible.</p> <p>ES: Using schoolyards in teaching and recreational activities, normalising children's contact with nature as an integral part of the educational day-to-day.</p> <p>IT & PT: Micro strategies of regenerative agriculture, e.g. new ways of using water</p> <p>NL-EV & ES: Experimentation and implementation with municipal tools, such as the CPO policy or a municipal schoolyard greening program.</p> <p>ES: City-hall organising conferences and participating in city networks to exchange about schoolyard greening programs and initiatives.</p> <p>NL-EV: Participation in a vast number of networks, e.g. the one of ecovillages, including diverse actor groups.</p> <p>HU: Connecting with traditional herders across the globe, e.g. by participating in the International Year of Rangelands and Pastoralists.</p>

Amplifying how?		Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
	<p>... by spreading (Lam et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Building education programs that teach traditional knowledge</p> <p>Transdisciplinary dissemination and communication (by combining arts and culture with biodiversity actions)</p> <p>Researchers communicate traditional knowledge's importance to higher scale policy levels.</p>	<p>HU: establishing herder schools that enable younger generation's access to traditional knowledge while also fostering innovations, following examples of schools in Spain.</p> <p>IT & RO & HU: Traditional festivals selling local products and showcasing local traditions.</p> <p>HU: Slow films following a day of herder on YouTube that reached a broad audience.</p> <p>IT: Exhibitions showing the history of the rivers and the community which then turned into a mechanism of networking with other Eco-museums.</p> <p>LT: Designing and using games together with the local communities where participants could write down their wishes for the local river.</p> <p>NL-FP: Dutch architecture biennial where Foodpark Amsterdam presented their initiative through a short film in collaboration with the Twente team.</p> <p>ES & NL-P: Creating toolboxes and setting standards in how to put biodiversity innovations into practice, e.g., toolboxes for integrating schoolyards in the teaching or for integrating nature in building practices.</p> <p>HU: upscaling traditional knowledge through researchers acting as knowledge communicators on the higher policy scales.</p>

Amplifying how?		Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
	<p>... by replicating and transferring (Lam et al.).</p>	<p>Exchanging and replicating traditional practices and knowledge with other regions</p> <p>Disseminating scientific knowledge about the biodiversity innovation</p> <p>Sharing and replicating locally successful innovations with other regions (Bandwagon effect - Termeer & Dewulf 2019)</p> <p>Potential: Setting an example by successfully implementing ambitious policies, to replicate them in other places.</p>	<p>PT & IT: learning and implementing regenerative agriculture practices from other places (syntropic farming, permaculture)</p> <p>PT: Transferring syntropic agricultural techniques outside of Portugal through volunteering and refugee programs</p> <p>HU: Sharing of and learning from traditional herders' knowledge around the world</p> <p>ALL: Using BIOTraCes activities and results to increase legitimacy of biodiversity innovation by communicating results with communities and policymakers.</p> <p>IT: Using counter-mapping tools, such as social-ecological mapping of energy production, in other contexts.</p> <p>PT: Neighbouring municipalities replicating syntropic farming practices and being inspired by Mértola's vision</p> <p>ES: Conferences where pioneer municipalities or regions share experiences of schoolyard greening initiatives</p> <p>RO: Expanding eco-tourism activities in the region, expanding local festivals that promote sustainable agriculture</p> <p>NL-FP: Community land trusts</p> <p>NL-EV: collective private commissioning of the municipality of Wageningen</p> <p>ES: Municipal schoolyard greening program with fixed annual budget</p>

Amplifying how?		Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
<p>... beyond (towards governance structures and worldviews, paradigms)...</p>	<p>...by scaling up through changing rules (Lam et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Influencing and/or changing legislation & regulations</p>	<p>ES: New national education law proposing alternative education models as an opportunity for shifting education paradigms (coupling - Termeer & Dewulf 2019)</p> <p>LT: EU water directive that requires renaturalisation of rivers implemented by national governments</p> <p>NL-P: Potential: Adapting residential permitting processes to accommodate nature-positive lifestyle choices, e.g., electric-only vehicles, prohibition of fireplaces, and pesticide-free gardening. If residents were willing to comply with such conditions, they could be permitted to live closer to protected natural areas</p>
	<p>... by scaling deep through changing values (Lam et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Amplifying new human perspectives of nature (including human dependency on nature)</p>	<p>NL-EV: New narrative of nature-positive living in the De Beuk project.</p> <p>IT: Showing the history of human-nature relationships in a museum exhibition, changing relationships with the territory.</p>
		<p>Shifting imaginaries around biodiversity in policy, society, and economy.</p>	<p>ES: Potential: Integrating emerging relational perspectives of schoolyards into policy framings, e.g., by attaching an overarching narrative of schoolyard greening to practices of care.</p> <p>NL-P: connecting nature-inclusivity with other discourses, e.g. health, to increase recognition of the challenge.</p>

Amplifying how?	Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
	<p>... by showcasing successful and scalable examples that prove change is possible.</p>	<p>Embedding regenerative practices aligned with sustainable ways of living in & from the territory.</p> <p>IT: Replacing intensive agriculture with permaculture along the river, embedding historic social-ecological relations.</p> <p>PT: syntropic farming to regenerate the soil and provide sustainable agriculture to the local community.</p> <p>SV: forest owners lobbying together at forest owners' organisations to give counselling on continuous cover forestry and creating new infrastructure that supports these practices.</p> <p>NL-FP: Potential: Community land trust as alternative landownership model to privatisation; Changing economic paradigm at municipality level (Doughnut Economy; commons agenda).</p> <p>ES: Potential: Mainstreaming schoolyard greening as the norm, not the exception.</p> <p>NL-FP: Potential: Mainstreaming nature-inclusive building as the norm.</p>

5.4 Discussion

Leverage points

At the practice level, a leverage point encountered in several of the case studies refers to the creation of alternative local economy structures that allow communities to gain an income through different biodiversity innovations, e.g., by building up a sustainable tourism sector, developing local infrastructures around agriculture and energy, and creating networks of local businesses employing small-scale and sustainable production and consumption practices. At the practice level, we further identify processes aiming for the creation of spaces of dialogue that allow for community- and trust-building a key leverage point and main condition for transformations to appear and take shape. Here, the research activities implemented under BIOTraCes and following a participatory action research approach have been considered in some cases as a crucial momentum supporting the creation of awareness locally for the biodiversity challenge and the emergence of local and traditional knowledge and values of diverse community members.

Leverage points occurring at the political sphere and constituting a window of opportunity to change the governance context are, for instance, already existing legal frameworks and policy tools supportive of transformative biodiversity innovations. Those can imply European directives and visions, such as the EU Water framework directive or the EU nature restoration law (relevant for the Lithuanian), or take the form of national laws, such as the latest Spanish education law that puts sustainability and project-based learning at its heart (relevant to the Spanish case), or concern ambitious policies and tools developed and implemented at the regional and municipal scale, such as a regional biodiversity program in the Dutch Province case, municipal collective private commissioning policies or community land trusts that enable collective land acquisition (both Dutch cases), or the implementation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program (as in the Spanish case). Those policy tools across scale are key leverages for local innovation, as they allow local initiatives to be embedded in broader policy visions and hence create legitimacy of the innovation.

In the political sphere, next to these top-down processes, the role of bottom-up movements is crucial. In cases where institutional actors are supportive of local biodiversity innovation, collaborations involving local authorities, civil society, and in some parts also economic actors have been found key leverage points as they allow for alternative practices to occur. Collaborations can take the form of community actors receiving financial support by institutional actors or of co-governance and meaningful participation in decision-making processes regarding the future of the territory. In those BIOTraCes cases, where institutional support of the local biodiversity innovation is absent, bottom-up community- and network-building and collective organisation has been crucial for the biodiversity innovation to occur. This, for instance, includes the creation of renewable energy communities by local residents in the Italian case, local food networks in the Portuguese case, or the writing of a collective manifesto presenting community demands to the city hall in the Spanish case.

Leverage points situated in the personal sphere are those that can reach the deepest as they change paradigms, worldviews and values informing both the political and practical sphere. In the BIOTraCes cases, we identify processes leveraging both alternative imaginaries and values. Leveraging new social-ecological and locally rooted imaginaries is occurring, for instance, by framing local initiatives as an alternative towards high impact

sector 'wrongs'. In some of the BIOTraCes cases, this even supported the creation of new, positive imaginaries of the territory needed to overcome a human-nature disconnection. For instance, local initiative's imaginaries are countering dominant sector paradigms, e.g. small-scale agroecological and forest production vs. industrialised mono-cultures (in the Portuguese, Italian and Swedish cases), renewable energy communities vs. monopolised large-scale photovoltaic power plants (in the Italian case), nature-positive ecovillages vs. large-scale housing developments (in the Dutch eco-village case), or a Commons- and nature-based society vs. one centred on consumerism (in the Dutch Foodpark case). Following, imaginaries that describe territories and landscapes as underdeveloped, without future, or little ecological value can be re-framed towards those challenging broader paradigms, while also offering sustainable alternatives for local communities.

Amplification processes

In terms of amplifying within the local context, we find a lot of relational processes such as building trust and networks, also through the celebration of small wins, necessary for bottom-up movements to grow into biodiversity interventions. Crucially, these involve a lot of experimentation, highlighting the need for context-dependent solutions instead of the replication and scaling of preexisting uniform policy solutions. Multi-actor collaborations, especially between institutional and community actors are key to achieve a stabilisation of the biodiversity innovation over the long term. The testing of innovative policy tools, such as collective private commissioning, can thereby play a core role in embedding the biodiversity innovation into institutional structures. Niche innovators inside institutional structures can thereby act as important facilitators translating the biodiversity innovations' goals into policy program.

To increase the biodiversity innovation's impact beyond the local context, namely amplifying out towards reaching other communities and places, amplifying mechanisms include the participation of local actors in diverse networks, including civil society, policy, and multi-actor networks. The participation in cross-scale networks enables the sharing of locally created knowledge and experiences with other similar actors to replicate successful practices elsewhere or the advocating for new policy tools that could facilitate the successful implementation of the biodiversity innovation's goal, such as collective land acquisition mechanisms.

Many of the BIOTraCes case studies further draw on transdisciplinary dissemination and communication. By combining artistic tools of communication with scientific knowledge, e.g. through museum exhibitions or films visualising local social-ecological histories, the biodiversity innovation can more easily be communicated to a broader audience, leading to increased awareness across multiple actors. Lastly, bandwagon effects (Termeer & Dewulf 2019) are highlighted in many of the cases, where the success of local innovation can be seen in biodiversity innovations being replicated in other places. While these are so far often potentials that are seen for upscaling, such as the possible expansion of eco-tourism in the Romanian case, or the wider adoption of community land trusts and collective private commissioning in the Dutch Foodpark case and Dutch eco-village case, there are several examples where biodiversity interventions have already inspired the replication in other places. Those are be found for instance in the Portuguese case where more neighbouring municipalities to Mértola implementing syntropic farming techniques, and the increase in schoolyard greening programs in a European context.

Lastly, the case studies show how changing legislation on higher policy scales can amplify local innovative practices. In some cases, the biodiversity issue is already directly addressed at the highest policy levels, such as the EU water directive, which nudges national riverbed restoration efforts through a top-down process (such as in the Lithuanian case). In other cases, coupling between different policy areas and scales is taking place, such as in the latest education Law in Spain, where higher-level changes in education policy are creating synergies with municipal greening initiatives to offer a legal framework for embodied and nature-inclusive teaching and learning practices that can be applied in renaturalised schoolyards. If accompanied by shifting imaginaries, such as reframing renaturalised schoolyards' benefits through an emphasis on its relational value, or connecting nature initiatives holistically with other goals, such as health, an amplification beyond current rules, governance structures and values could be achieved. Ultimately, biodiversity innovations can only then unfold their full impact when they show that alternatives are possible and can be successful, for instance, when Foodpark Amsterdam has been successfully implementing a community land trust (Dutch Foodpark case), Sweden's forest owners shifted to continuous forest covers on a larger scale (Swedish case), schoolyard greening is fully embedded into the annual municipal budget (Spanish case), or syntrophic farming has been established as the common agricultural production model (Portuguese case). It remains to be seen, however, if biodiversity innovations explored in BIOTraCes' case study will be successfully implemented over the long run and across various scales.

5.5 References

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6 Strategies and approaches in (transformative) biodiversity initiatives (T3.2)

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6.1 Introduction⁶ and methodological notes

As previously mentioned, the cross-case analysis of the BIOTraCes case studies aims to identify strategies and approaches that may support transformative change towards strengthened biodiversity, grounded in principles of social equity. This is also the aim of T3.2, which focuses on strategies and approaches from a relatively broad perspective (rather than focusing on e.g. particular types of strategies or particular phases of their implementation process).

T3.2 analyses strategies in the case studies with a relatively broad take on the strategy implementation process that covers many pertinent aspects from prerequisites to impacts: the contextual setting of strategies; how they are elaborated and evolve, their overarching focus, the target groups that they attempt to influence, their content and subject matter, methods for implementation including challenges and difficulties, their transformative potential as interpreted by the informants, and their outcomes in the cases – so far.

The data for T3.2. are analysed following the approach to thematic analysis elaborated by Braun & Clarke (2006; 2022). The interviews and monitoring forms (collected as described in *Methods and materials*) have been analysed with initial open coding and categorisation in several iterations (using MAXQDA software), in parallel with gradually evolving theme development and revisions and memo writing, again in an iterative process, and write-up of the findings. To illustrate and liven the account as well as for validity reasons, excerpts from the material are included throughout. Following a hybrid inductive-deductive approach, the analysis focuses on certain key theoretical issues based on previous research while also analysing the material unconditionally, in its own right.

6.2 Findings

Figure 6-1 provides an overview of the results: themes and sub-themes. Each branch in the figure represents one of the sub-sections in this chapter, each dedicated to one of main features of the strategies in the set of case studies: *Governance structure and institutional settings*; *Strategy development and implementation*; *Overarching approaches*; *Target groups*; *Subject matter and orientation*; *Methods*; *Challenges and difficulties*; *Transformative potential*; and *Outcomes*. These also include more detailed figures including the sub-themes that are collapsed (represented by numbers) in the overview version below.

⁶ In the original project proposal, T3.2 was titled *Strategies for public, private and civil society actors to initiate and accelerate transformative change*. The explicit focus on societal sectors has been reduced, as it was not prominent in the data and the limited number of cases – often with similar sectoral contexts – makes comparisons unfeasible. The task now focuses more broadly on strategic approaches within the cases. However, sectoral issues are still addressed.

Figure 6-1: Overview of thematic analysis for T3.2

GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES AND INSTITUTIONAL SETTINGS

Figure 6-2 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to the governance structures and institutional settings in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-2: *Governance structures and institutional settings – themes and sub-themes*

The case studies provide various examples of **tensions** between stakeholders and actors across different **geographical-administrative levels**. Tensions are often related to *asymmetric power relations* between the actors in the various governance settings. Local-level stakeholders, especially those without connections to formal authorities, are often at a disadvantage in relation to higher positioned or otherwise more powerful actors, especially national-level agencies but also local governments.

The Hungarian case stresses that national authorities are insufficiently or incorrectly informed and thus ill equipped for devising good policy. However, when the national-level governance/institutional context fails to provide support, the European Union level can fill the gap to some extent. In the Dutch eco-village case, the European level nature restoration regulations can complement and counteract national-level political forces who pull in a non-nature friendly direction:

It actually helps De Beuk that Europe has this restoration goal [considering that] the Netherlands, [...] our main political constitution at the moment, is really trying to combat certain nature restoration goals which are getting more formalised by the [European Union] nature restoration law. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview round 2)

Governance structures can be highly centralised as in the Romanian and Lithuanian cases. Plans with heavy local-level impacts may be elaborated at the national scale without a reasonable level of local democratic consultation and participation in the process, as in the Lithuanian case. Here, weak trust relations across levels of government were also a potential complicating factor:

It seemed that municipality level authorities might not necessarily have a good connection with the national-level authorities, and they do not necessarily trust in them. (Lithuanian case, Interview Round 2)

Lack of interest and support in local initiatives can be due to them posing perceived threats/challenges to the power balance of the existing governance structure. However, a lack of interest for local stakeholders' engagement is not necessarily a wholly bad thing, as shown in the Italian case where lack of support turned into a source of empowerment and independence:

...it was clear from the start that the social partner would have to rely on its own capacities, /.../ its own resources and /.../ [was] very limited [in terms of being able] to trust, both the regional government support or [the support of] the local municipality. And so this /.../ motivated /.../ the partners to show /.../ that local actors can lead /.../ cultural and ecological innovation /.../and it forces [them] /.../ to build autonomy and to build independence from the governance structure itself. (Italian case, Interview Round 2)

Political changes can vastly influence the preconditions for biodiversity initiatives and the strategies chosen by local stakeholders. One example of where this is taken to an extreme is the Swedish case about forest biodiversity. Given the extensive time spans/rotation periods in forestry, there is an enormous scope for change – political or otherwise – over the course of time during which decisions taken will continue to have a tangible impact on the forest landscape. This can result in landowners being unsure and highly cautious in making decisions, particularly those with a bearing on economic output:

Most forest owners who are a bit more knowledgeable and active in their choices in the forest also recognise that it's really difficult to see where this will end up. Because the politics /.../ will have changed several times probably, in 80 years from now. The climate will have changed, the surrounding world will have changed, the prices on different stuff, and the markets will have changed. So /.../ at least in economic terms, there's always a risk. (Swedish case, Interview Round 2)

Private sector/industrial actors are an important part of the governance structures and institutional context in several cases. For example, the financial sector influences the preconditions for eco-village development in the Dutch eco-village case. The Italian case describes how the development of photovoltaic installations in Sicily effectively strengthens the position of multinational energy companies in the area. The Swedish case shows that 'standard' forestry practices are often promoted and applied by forest industry representatives, without sufficient consideration of local conditions and context or the landowner's priorities. The Dutch Foodpark case highlights fluid power relations depending on context. The Foodpark organisation, despite e.g. their high profile in local and even national media and having made important achievements are nevertheless 'irrelevant' (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview Round 2) when it comes to challenging the public-private partnership working with land use planning in the area in question.

Some of the case studies, in particular the Portuguese and Italian cases, involve initiatives that are explicitly **co-governed** by **cross-sectoral** combinations of actors representing the public, private and civil sectors. These governance structures are chosen as they offer opportunities for broad local participation, action-taking, networking as well as efficient implementation of the initiative. In the Portuguese case, the co-governance set up involves 'producers, schools, technicians and political representatives' (Portuguese case, Interview Round 2) whose joint and aligned efforts make possible the development of a new local food system.

STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 6-3 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to the strategy development and implementation in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-3: *Strategy development and implementation – themes and sub-themes*

Strategies can take on different forms and be either planned in advance or develop spontaneously through ad hoc processes as activities and situations unfold.

The sets of strategies in most case studies contain elements of deliberation and design. When there are clear goals in place, then these tend to be accompanied by correspondingly **planned** strategies; at least in the form of a framing guideline for the long term, while still allowing flexibility in the shorter term. The Dutch Foodpark case exemplifies a case with a structured approach to strategising in relation to different time spans. A long-term vision is complemented with *'biannual strategy meetings where /.../ the strategy for the next six months is planned out, and their monthly gatherings for the entire team'* (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview 1). Another example of careful co-development of the strategic approach is the Romanian case:

'Implementation begins with multi-stakeholder workshops where local authorities, conservationists and businesses assess strategies, identify gaps. Then there is the feedback. So it is to improve the strategy' (Romanian case, Interview 1).

The issue of longer and shorter temporal frames in strategy implementation is present in all case studies. In the Italian case, the local stakeholders have consciously chosen to focus on the relatively **short-term** project-by-project time frame rather than an underlying need for political change processes that likely will take longer to evolve. However, the project format in itself precludes long-term strategising, potentially creating a lock-in in short budget cycles and limiting the possible activities. In contrast, the Swedish case illustrates how certain land uses – in this case forestry – by their very nature require **long-term** perspectives when making strategic choices; and therefore also connect the present with both future outcomes and consequences of past choices:

When it comes to strategies for forest management, I think they are very much planned /.../. Because forestry requires a long-term thinking all the time. So you need to plan like 80 years ahead and often with, kind of, intergenerational perspectives as well. And you have to deal with decisions and strategies that people have been doing in the past as well. (Swedish case, Interview 1)

In addition to the planned strategies, the stakeholders also engage in various **agile** strategies, developed with flexibility and agility in response to developing circumstances, especially when the context is dynamic and prone to change. As exemplified in the Dutch eco-village case:

...there is a limit to what you can strategise with, like a certain horizon, and most strategies have come up in response to quite spontaneous actions or happenings.

(Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1)

Changes in the external context can require that stakeholders be *agile in responding* to these, including adapting their strategies. The biodiversity initiatives are – to varying degrees – dependent on external structures and conditions. Changes in these can significantly alter the prerequisites for implementing the initiative in terms of opening opportunities or posing barriers. In the Dutch Foodpark case preparedness involves plural strategies through which the ‘seasoned activists’ in the movement...:

...are always mobilising a diversity of strategies to respond pragmatically to opportunities that arise. So it's extremely dynamic. (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview Round 2)

(Dutch Foodpark case, Interview Round 2)

The Hungarian case exemplifies the importance of the structural preconditions in which the case plays out. Developments within institutional settings and governance conditions – such as economic policy, agricultural policy or animal protection policy on different geographical-administrative levels – influence herder communities and the herding profession both directly and indirectly:

There are quite direct changes in the economics and the livestock keeping conditions and rules. And they are influencing the herders quite harshly. So we have to adapt our methods /.../. Because in the old times there were not big changes in the lives of herders. Or in the natural environment. But now it is changing so fast [that] /.../ we have to accommodate yearly, weekly...

(Hungarian case, Interview Round 2)

Adjustment based on new experience and insights

Experiences from the case studies point to the importance of adaptive capacity and flexibility in strategising. A pertinent aspect in this regard is the need to continuously revise and refine strategies as they play out in real life situations, especially in response to feedback from the actors involved:

When you have local feedback, you should always adapt your strategy in order to not impose rigid solutions. (Romanian case, Interview 1)

(Romanian case, Interview 1)

In several cases, the strategies employed in the case studies have shifted as the biodiversity initiatives evolve. **New experiences and insights** are used to modify or refine approaches. The **adjustments** can relate to the orientation/content of strategies, changes in governance structure or work processes. For example, shifting focus is a way of addressing issues emerging as particularly important, of overcoming barriers, or of making use of opportunities that arise along the way.

In the Portuguese case, the local stakeholder networks have strengthened over time, causing strategies to become more intertwined, coordinated, and dependent on these

social connections. The Dutch eco-village case shows that De Beuk has by necessity⁷ shifted towards growing emphasis on regulation-related and economically-related issues (cf. 'sticks' and 'carrots' (Pachego-Vega 2020)). At the same time, they focus on internal social cohesion within the network while biding their time and waiting for their efforts to bear fruit despite attempts by external agents to delay development.

Both the Italian and Dutch Foodpark cases were initially grounded in political resistance movements in response to local development tendencies deemed to be problematic. However, they have since moved on to (also) focus on other issues, e.g. complementing the initial criticism with 'developing an attractive vision' of an alternative development route (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview Round 2).

The schoolyard greening initiative in Spanish case is an example of how **case evolution** can change the basic prerequisites for strategising. The initiative originated from grassroots-level (parents of school children) push. However, when it became somewhat more established, its governance was taken over by institutional (local government) actors. So, the original innovators were driven out from/abandoned the project, while other actors stepped in to take over and likely devising strategies of their own.

The initiation phase was purely bottom up. Then it got taken to the establishment phase. Institutional actors came in, took it over, defined it, designed it and then the bottom-up were [...] not pushing anymore. So strategies, now if we look the strategies are purely on the top-down actors. (Spanish case, Interview Round 2)

Strategic adjustments also involve moving towards **more tailored** strategies **rather than uniform** ones. The Spanish case highlights how socioeconomic variations within the city translate into variegated needs which need to be reflected in strategies. Similarly, it is acknowledged in the Hungarian case that different local communities require different strategic approaches due to e.g. socioeconomic differences.

In the Italian case the original political emphasis that sparked the initiative, has been discontinued in favour of other strategies seen by local stakeholders as more useful under current circumstances.

The element of resistance is long gone now. That was the generative moment. And now that they've shifted decisively towards planning [...] in the last 10 years. [...] this element of resistance [...] is now something that is alien to the way the[y] work. (Italian case, Interview 1)

⁷ A need to pay attention to managing financing and bank relations given the unconventional not-for-profit basis of the movement.

OVERARCHING APPROACHES

Figure 6-4 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to overarching approaches in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-4: *Overarching approaches – themes and sub-themes*

Grassroots empowerment through activation and participation

As a key baseline of their overall approach nearly all case studies have elements of bottom-up **grassroots** orientation, **participatory** approaches and ambitions of **empowering** local stakeholders⁸ in the different case study contexts. This emphasis expresses an ambition to achieve (more) fair and balanced conditions and shift power relations by supporting and strengthening the position of less powerful groups who tend not to be included/involved in business-as-usual approaches. Activating and involving local communities in new initiatives – or building on local action that is already taking place to create momentum – in matters that concern their immediate environment not only empowers locals but is also seen as a prerequisite for transformative change in the desired direction; akin to a logic of ‘getting everyone on board’.

...change cannot happen without the older rural people and their availability to forge new imageries on space, nature and agricultural practices/.../ to make villagers both revitalise good farming practices and experiment new ways of doing (Portuguese case, Monitoring form)

Our current strategy is to try to change the way conservation works from the bottom up, from within. (Hungarian case, Monitoring form)

However, while participatory and grassroots oriented foci are seen as essential for change, certain critical points are raised regarding how these are applied. For example, the Portuguese case highlights limitations of conventional bottom-up approaches which tend to concentrate on local organisations rather than involving the broader community, thus potentially missing the mark.

⁸ A separate but related issue: these characteristics are in line also with the overall methodological approach for BIOTraCes and have likely served as (implicit or explicit) selection criteria for the case studies in the project.

Challenging ideas, discourses and power structures

Many strategies attempt to address and/or shift existing power structures, not least dominating ideas and discourses. This theme includes efforts directed at conventional views and valuations of nature within a diverse set of stakeholders.

In the Portuguese case, attempts are made to shift and strengthen values and practices in a biodiversity-friendly direction and in support of climate change adaptation by focusing on benefits. In the Hungarian case, long-term collaboration and **trust-building** between the research team and stakeholder group of male herders include efforts to change deeply ingrained cultural traits which pose hurdles to the reproduction of traditional knowledge:

...herders started to share their own knowledge with others. Which is a huge impact of our work in the last 15 years with herders, because that's a competitive occupation and in the past, family traditions were kept, and everything was kept secret between outsiders and between herders. So I think now after 15 years of hard work, herders realised that keeping the knowledge secret can lead to knowledge extinction. /.../ Because it was a competitive occupation, they are very bad at collaboration networking. They don't like to organise themselves into an NGO /.../ The women are much better. That's why we have the women herder group. But the [male herders], they are not ready for collaboration among themselves. (Hungarian case, Interview round 1)

Most cases highlight the importance of understanding and **acknowledging** the **varied perspectives** of different stakeholders; thereby potentially bridging conflicts of interest that may hamper efforts in support of biodiversity. This also corresponds to the *pluralising* principle of the BIOTraCes PEPE framework. Another example is addressing pervasive **social and geographical imaginaries** and discourses of rural places and regions, e.g. national-level narratives and perceptions of a region as backwards or as having 'no future', as in the Portuguese case, concerning the Baixo Alentejo region.

Lobbying and resistance

Within the broader theme of *Challenging ideas, discourses and power structures*, a distinct sub-theme of strategies focuses more specifically on **lobbying and resistance** with the aim to influence political processes, policy development and/or formal decision making. Stakeholders who pursue a biodiversity-oriented agenda or initiative attempt to draw attention, raise awareness and influence other relevant actors and processes to move in a desired way. Activities include e.g. voicing protests, participating in key meetings, providing decision support material (e.g. pilot project evaluations to support continuous funding and support, as in the Spanish case), building pressure for policy level incorporation of their ideas. The efforts are not necessarily directed 'against' other actors but can also be collaborative in character, e.g. seeking common ground, possible compromises, and joining forces with like-minded actors inside target organisations.

What the parents [of pupils in Vitoria-Gasteiz] did at the very beginning, basically, when they formulated the social demand, they wrote a manifesto informing what they actually demand, and then they sent that to the City Hall, which then started the program there. (Spanish case, Interview 1)

So, [the strategy of] 'stopping the bad' or 'breaking the old', that is really mostly oriented towards the municipality of Amsterdam, because they are ultimately

the people that can change the ordinance plan of the land and that can stop the building activities. There is a great uncertainty about who will be settling there but as soon as [Foodpark Amsterdam] knows who is going to be there, they usually also reach out to them and say, 'hey, do you actually know what kind of land you're building [on]?' And most of them do have a conversation with them as well. And see whether some kind of compromise can be found, or not. (Dutch Foodpark case Interview 1)

The lobbying attempts occur on most *geographical-administrative levels*. Depending on which actors are seen as crucial for the case in question – perhaps combined with an idea about where efforts are most likely to have the intended impact – the attempts address local decisions, national legislation, international industry-specific regulations or EU-level regulations. As for the potential results of the efforts, these are mostly yet to materialise. In the Dutch Foodpark case, for example, the conversations have not yet lead to any change.

Strategy void

In some cases, and for some stakeholders – individuals, communities and institutional actors – there is something akin to a **strategy void**. Rather than devising potentially efficient strategies to reach their goals, these stakeholders remain mainly *passive* or at best *reactive* in relation to others' initiatives. There are also examples of stakeholders who continue along previously treaded, but increasingly obsolete, paths without questioning.

Some of the factors which appear to explain this passive approach are *lack of knowledge, lack of coordination and/or organisational capacity; flawed communication; or considering biodiversity an issue of low priority* compared to other issues perceived as more immediately pressing. For example, in the Lithuanian case, political agendas currently prioritise geopolitical and security issues while environmental problems are pushed to the side as 'luxury topics'. Their *policy invisibility* is a likely reason for the lack of action:

Environmental problems [...] do not have like clear or obvious damage to people. Th[ey] are not explicitly seen. [...] Forests that are being cut down in Lithuania on a massive rate. People who live close to this forest [...] that [is] going to be [...] logged, so they initiate change, right? And they participate very actively because it's very obvious. But it's not very obvious what's going to happen when you remove a river dam or what's going to happen in the long run if we keep the river dam, right? So these issues that are not very obvious with the people do not see like clear consequences today, these issues are kind of left, you know, to their own devices, [...] there is no urge to [...] initiate any grassroot movement (Lithuanian case, Interview 1)

There are also cases where individual-level goals and plans are made and followed, but where there is no coordinated strategy or organisation together with peers. For example, the herders in the Hungarian case *'do not have comprehensive strategies, but seek individual solutions for their own sustenance in their immediate environment'* (Hungarian case, Monitoring form). This group therefore benefits from the long-term cooperation with researchers who actively *'try to bring them together to think and brainstorm'* (Hungarian case, Monitoring form). The case of the small-scale private forest owners in the Swedish case reveals that although they as landowners have substantial power and mandate over

properties and hence opportunities to shape them according to their wishes, they often take quite passive approaches:

[The individual forest owners] are passive so they don't do so much /.../, they do limited things in their forests according to what they want /.../ and what they believe /.../ The forest owners themselves actually formulate the goals and have more /.../ power over their properties, but at the same time they often don't have that much knowledge, background knowledge and interest in actually managing the forest. (Swedish case, Interview 1)

TARGET GROUPS

Figure 6-5 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to the target groups of the strategies in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-5: Target groups – themes and sub-themes

The strategies implemented in the cases are intended to influence specific targets. These are various (often public) organisations or groups who **hold** some level of **formal power** (mostly at the national or local level), the **general population** or specific **sub-groups** therein, or other private **organisations** (including businesses). Given the interconnectedness and complexity of many of the cases, the case stakeholders sometimes need to address several actors from a system perspective, e.g. both local authorities/municipalities and local economic actors. As in the Romanian case:

'They influence the whole system that we analyse. They influence the locals, the small farmers, also the bigger scale farmers, the local authorities.'
(Romanian case, Interview 1).

Holders of formal power

In a few of the cases, certain ***national level authorities*** are, through their position of formal power, of key concern and interest for stakeholders to influence to achieve their goals. Examples include the State Forest Agency in the Netherlands who are one of the landowners in the Dutch eco-village case; and the national conservation and veterinary authorities in the Hungarian case.

However, among public sector actors, it is more common for case study stakeholders to focus on exerting influence at the local level, i.e. ***municipalities*** which tend to be the key locus of power needed to achieve the changes the stakeholders are striving for. As in the Spanish case: '[there's] a strategy of the parents' associations targeted towards the city hall. They want to influence the city hall to actually make [schoolyard greening happen] (Spanish case, Interview 1); or the Dutch Foodpark case: '*...the municipality of Amsterdam /.../ are ultimately the people that can change the ordinance plan of the land and that can stop the building activities*'. (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview 1). In the latter case, there is also a certain level of reciprocity or potential mutual gains (win-win) in the relationship between the citizen initiative and municipality, whose self-image is in line with some of the goals of the Foodpark:

...the city of Amsterdam would like to portray themselves as a place where different people can come together, where food is produced organically and shared, where there are care activities and cultural and learning activities.
(Dutch Foodpark case, Interview 1)

Landowners are another important type of holder of formal power (which sometimes overlap with local authorities). Not least, this is explicitly mentioned in the Dutch eco-village case and the Dutch Foodpark case. In both, the goals of the citizen initiatives depend heavily on gaining access to land on which to develop the Foodpark and eco-village, respectively, which requires them to target, negotiate, communicate and strategise in relation to landowners and developers. The land issue is perhaps particularly pertinent in the Dutch context, which is characterised by high density, land use competition, and pressure on scarce urban and peri-urban lands, not least in Amsterdam (e.g. OECD, 2017). The Swedish case, with its focus on private forest owners, also highlights the importance of landowner priorities, and their underlying values and goals, for biodiversity-oriented forestry. Despite being formally in charge many forest owners, due to e.g. (perceived) lack of knowledge, choose to rely on advice from professional consultants representing organisations in the industrial forestry sector to e.g. develop forest management plans:

...the decision making on the ground often is /.../ handed off to these industrial consultants. Of course they listen to the forest owners and what they want with their forests. But /.../ the alternatives that the forest owner gets are also the alternatives that the forest consultant presents. (Swedish case, Interview 1)

The Romanian case, Portuguese case and Italian case all point to the role of farmers, who presumably are often also landowners. Farmers are the target of various efforts to strengthen biodiversity and nature conditions through raising awareness and stimulating changes in agricultural production (relating to e.g. crops, livestock, techniques).

The general population and its sub-groups

In many of the case studies, the **general population** and **local communities** are main target groups. Strategies include efforts to shift public opinion in support of the goals of the initiatives, thereby working to shift patterns of views, values and ultimately behaviours to improve biodiversity.

In some of the cases, their efforts include an explicit element of consumer awareness paired with broader criticism of contemporary global consumption patterns. As in the Hungarian case:

...we have to make an impact on the shopping system even. /.../ Herders can only stay and /.../ help to maintain biodiversity, if they can maintain themselves [economically]. And I think this is the part where we cannot only think about decision making systems in the state. We have to make many, many efforts in the civilian lifestyle. (Hungarian case, Interview 1)

The strategies in this case study combine attention to the general public with a 'guerrilla strategy' for also influencing formal decision makers through their private lives as laymen:

...one channel to reach decision makers, is through their laymanship, the hobby, the free time. /.../ a minister also watches news, so we cover the all the news portals in Hungary. (Hungarian case, Interview 1)

Children and youth, especially in a school/educational context, stand out among the specific **population sub-groups** of interest in the case studies (see also [*Innovative thinking for just and effective governance \(T3.4\)*](#)). The multiple values of green schoolyards are at the core of the Spanish case: greening can help strengthen children's connection with nature, thereby influencing their value development. It can also support pedagogy and learning, stimulate play, enhance gender sensitivity in school environment design, and reduce heat stress. So, in a somewhat longer-term perspective, interventions targeting children and young people through their education is thought to be a route towards change. It may generate shifts away from anthropocentric values and help to prevent or reduce future tensions and conflicts. The Lithuanian case suggests that educational efforts need to be adjusted according to the specific local context and circumstances:

In the communities where they have dams, especially those who really need to be removed, there might be education specifically tailored for these schools, like for children starting like from a young age /.../ and just talk about what is the, you know, damage of the dams. Just /.../ introduce this topic, like neutrally, and try to just give it as a general knowledge. (Lithuanian case, Interview 1)

Besides children and youth, other population sub-groups that are targeted to a somewhat lesser extent in some case studies are *girls and women, elderly people, and migrants and refugees*.

Girls and/or women are particularly important in the strategies in the Spanish case and Hungarian case. In Hungary, targeting and supporting women within the male dominated herding profession has strengthened the networking within the group and also stimulated international connections. In the Spanish case, gender sensitivity and inclusivity in developing children's play spaces is a key aspect of the schoolyard greening initiative:

Schoolyard greening is the issue of unequal use of space by gender. So, it definitely targets girls and tries to create a schoolyard where there's

more diverse play opportunities that are more inclusive, compared to the status quo of just having a football pitch where they are, essentially, relegated to the sides. (Spanish case, Interview 1)

Concerning *migrants and refugees*, in the Spanish case the choice of schools for the greening projects is done with social concerns in mind; focusing on ‘segregated’ schools with a large share of immigrant families. In the Portuguese case, a project aiming to attract refugees and other migrants was launched by local stakeholders; part of attempts to counteract depopulation and challenge a perceived negative national-level narrative of the region as being of little importance. The stakeholders in the Portuguese case also explicitly target *elderly people* in attempts to raise knowledge and shift their views, which tend to be deeply rooted through lifelong experience.

SUBJECT MATTER AND ORIENTATION

Figure 6-6 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to the subject matter and orientation/focus of strategies in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-6: Subject matter and orientation – themes and sub-themes

Information and knowledge

Strategies oriented towards information and knowledge are common across the case studies. The widespread use of strategies with this particular emphasis may be related to the fact that the direct stakeholders are seldom in possession of the formal means or mandate to e.g. offer economic incentives or devise formal policies (cf. *carrots, sticks and sermons*⁹, see [Governance approaches and instruments for change](#)). They are mostly operating from a grassroots level of the governance context, not from within institutional/government settings.

⁹ The themes in the cross-case analysis of subject matter and orientation of strategies resemble the carrots, sticks and sermons typology (Pacheco-Vega 2020). However, the typology is conventionally applied mainly in relation to formal policy approaches and instruments, a different governance/government context compared to the (mainly) grassroots level of the BIOTraCes case studies. However, even if the case stakeholders may not possess any formal mandate/power to e.g. explicitly formulate or change regulations (sticks), this may nevertheless be what their strategies and actions aim to achieve – something that is often the case.

Many examples of strategies involve education and (co)learning activities such as efforts to inform, raise awareness or empower local stakeholders. For example, the Portuguese case includes examples of '*vocational training for wildlife management and biodiversity conservation, [the] regenerative pastures model and recognition of local knowledges*' (CES, Monitoring form). The pilot project in the Spanish case includes training for the schools involved. The Hungarian case includes monitoring and spreading awareness of the impacts for biodiversity and for key stakeholders of policy and formal decision making. In the Swedish case, forest sectors stakeholders (in particular state/public sector actors) provide private forest owners with information about e.g. alternative, more biodiversity-friendly, forestry methods although apparently without much success. Landowners and other forest sector (business) actors are also offered:

...financial incentives and educational programs for forestry workers and firms to adopt alternative methods. They also emphasise the development of business models that incorporate not just timber production but also the broader societal benefits of continuous-cover forestry. Furthermore, public agencies aim to enhance outreach to private forest owners by offering targeted consultations and creating digital tools to identify forests suitable for such practices. (Swedish case, Monitoring form).

As could be expected given the participatory approach of most of the case studies, many of the information and knowledge-oriented strategies concern bottom-up activities. These often emphasise co-learning between e.g. *researchers and local stakeholders* in efforts to bridge '*the gap between scientific terminology and local perspectives, ensuring the participation of all community members, regardless of social or educational background*' (Romanian case, Monitoring form). The importance of local, contextually grounded knowledge is acknowledged, along with the role of (re)connecting people and nature, stimulating awareness and behavioural change for biodiversity and nature values. For example, the Romanian case has included participatory workshops where:

Local communities identify key biodiversity/nature elements like water, forests, and pastures. A participant emphasised the cultural role of pastures, saying, 'That's where we played as children and picked wildflowers for our homes'. /.../ Civil society supports participation, local knowledge, and cultural pride, creating bottom-up leverage for biodiversity. (Romanian case, Monitoring form)

There are also examples of bottom-up co-learning involving *local communities* or specific demographic, social or professional groups therein. Attempts are sometimes made to transmit this knowledge to higher levels of government to strengthen its impact. For example, in the Hungarian case, knowledge co-created between herders and researchers resulted in drawing attention to a game management (vaccination) practice by the veterinary authorities which caused economic damage to the herding community, and which was subsequently altered according to suggestions. This is also an example where the implemented strategies involved a mix of issues connected *knowledge* co-creation, *economic* impact on herders and game management *regulations*.

Many strategies include communication activities, not least distinct elements of support/encouragement of dialogue among stakeholder groups; and drawing attention to the issues at hand to stimulate action from e.g. local authorities. A few of the case studies specifically highlight the importance of approaching local stakeholders with respect and attention to their (different) views. For example, the Lithuanian case suggests there is a need for improved communication and humility between '*top-down experts*' and local communities:

...researchers, biologists, ecologists, biodiversity specialists, /.../ they have values in the right place /.../ they kind of value nature and they want to conserve nature. But the issue is they have no skills to communicate with communities and they, sometimes I would say more often than not, they're quite rude with local communities. /.../ ...they sometimes really also lack skills on how to communicate this, /.../ and how to be diplomatic and perhaps how to be understanding of why communities have different views towards conservation. (Lithuanian case, Interview round 1)

The case studies address and engage with various forms of knowledge. Formal, research-based knowledge is emphasised to some degree, including the need for cross-disciplinary combinations of knowledge and skills (e.g. Lithuanian case). There are also examples where theoretically informed strategic frameworks are applied (e.g. the Dutch Foodpark case). Several case studies focus specifically on the importance and role of **traditional knowledge**: recognising it, using/reviving it to protect and foster biodiversity, spreading it, and in some cases combining it with contemporary/modern knowledge and methods. The informants also point to the existence of barriers to more extensive application of traditional or alternative practices. The obstacles include an unrecognised/unfulfilled need to integrate this knowledge into conservation strategies and in designing solutions (Romanian case and Portuguese case); restrictions posed by formal frameworks (e.g. Natura 2000 regulation of land use practices related to grazing; Romanian case); and historically rooted unwillingness to share knowledge within peer networks (Hungarian case). The latter could in a worst-case scenario contribute to extinction of important knowledge.

Economic aspects

Several cases feature strategies whose goals entail to influence economic structures and/or prerequisites to better support and encourage biodiversity-friendly behaviour when developing livelihood or business strategies. As illustrated by the Swedish case, economic incentives (cf.. 'carrots' (Pacheco-Vega 2020)) can be efficient enough to even reach sceptics, albeit not by changing their views or values but by incentivising behavioural change:

The forest owner organisation ha[s] this conservation premium which obviously acts as a carrot because even – I have one forest owner who I talked to who was very much against biodiversity because he felt it was just some kind of rubbish – but he followed the goals of that conservation premium because it gave him more money for his forest. And that obviously works even with very sceptical people. (Swedish case, Interview 1).

The Romanian case shows how nature-dependent livelihood strategies can support all pillars of sustainability in a local context:

Practices such as the collection and commercialisation of wild plants, mushrooms, and local fruits have re-emerged as a strategy for livelihood diversification /.../ local products become vehicles for community identity, cultural pride, and economic resilience while simultaneously promoting biodiversity protection through sustainable sourcing. (Romanian case, Monitoring form)

Some additional examples of economically oriented strategies include financial incentives from public sector actors to reforest land and develop ecotourism businesses (Romanian case); networking with local business representatives (Portuguese case); and promoting alternative economic principles (Dutch case Foodpark case). In the Dutch eco-village case, acquiring land on which to develop eco-village housing is a key goal. Therefore, their strategies have a strong emphasis on attaining the necessary finances, something that also conditions other activities:

So, of course De Beuk themselves are strategising to acquire the land, that's their main goal /.../ and in order to do that, they're forming this landscape corporation to resolidify their financial position. And they are also working on a communication strategy, but it all depends on whether or not they acquire the land. So strategies are very much focused on that. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1)

Regulations and policy

There is rather strong emphasis on regulations, rules, laws and policy and their various consequences across many cases. These issues concern all biodiversity initiatives that develop in an institutional and governance context, especially perhaps when connected to several geographical-administrative levels and nested frameworks.

In some cases, current regulatory/legal frameworks are perceived as **insufficient or lacking**, and so strategies aim to change these to generate stronger biodiversity-friendly impacts. This is illustrated in, for example, the ambitions for system-wide changes in the Dutch Province case and the Hungarian case:

Overijssel is much more working in the system and trying to change the system of building in their province and therefore they are cooperating with a large network of project developers and municipalities and whoever wants to join. (Dutch Province case, Interview 1)

Our goal is to work with herders to propose professionally justifiable changes in regulations and procedures for conservation and land management. And if the state of the natural environment improves, the situation of herders improves – it goes back and forth between them (Hungarian case, Monitoring form)

Other examples concern inefficiency e.g. in terms of 'messy' regulatory frameworks which can cause difficulties for implementing biodiversity initiatives and be exploited by actors according to their agendas. As in the Italian case:

...the [institutional] landscape is that of cumbersome, chaotic regulations with a lot of legal loopholes and vacuums. So a lot of things that are not regulated. And in this mess, regulatory mess [and] uncertainty, private insurance comes in and try to benefit, maximise. (Italian case, Interview 1)

In other cases, the current regulatory/legal frameworks are perceived as **excessive and rigid**. Attempts are made to change or allow exceptions to e.g. regional or EU level rules or changing industry-specific standards in order to support local biodiversity-friendly practices. On a more positive note, there are some examples of how stakeholders have in some cases, through their strategies, succeeded in desired changes of regulations, as in the Hungarian case and Portuguese case. The Swedish case and Romanian case both

exemplify perceived negative effects of regulations, even if well-intended. Emerging problems include regulations that contribute to sparking/stirring tensions or even contribute to stakeholder behaviours that may counteract the basic purpose of the regulations. Regulations can cause farmers to be unable to let their livestock graze; and some landowners may even try to avoid the development of high nature values on their forest properties to avoid becoming subject of regulatory enforcement.

...the current species legislation [...] hinders [forest owners] from using the forest in the way that they have intended and that creates a lot of frustration. Sometimes aggression between different actors, and a lot of tension. (Swedish case, Interview 1)

METHODS

Networking: making strategic connections and cooperations

Figure 6-7 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to methods in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-7: *Methods – themes and sub-themes*

Stakeholders in the case studies often pursue their aims through seeking and establishing strategic connections with other key actors; developing cooperations and benefiting from their support. This **networking** strategy occurs both horizontally and vertically: across geographical-administrative levels ranging from local through regional and national to even international levels.

Cooperation is sought and created with various actors and across sectors. The choice of which contacts to make is also strategically made to strengthen the likelihood of success for the goals in question. In the Dutch eco-village case, networking constitutes the core of the strategic approach:

...they have a very big network of people. That are working in the system to advise them [...]. They divided themselves into five working groups [...] [and] they are also connected to the global eco-village network. So, there is a big

network of people and institutions helping them. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1)

Among the actors who are approached in these networking activities are municipality and regional authority representatives, (local) business/industry representatives and entrepreneurs, local associations and NGOs. Also, researchers and research organisations, including the researchers involved in the BIOTraCes project. The clearest example is the Hungarian case where the researchers are the ones who – in close collaboration with the herder community – push for change and devise strategies to support herders. The research team also includes ‘a bridging person’ (Hungarian case, Interview 1) who is involved in the case study both as researcher and as herder apprentice.

One networking-related strategy is to **join forces** and actively contribute to the activities of other actors. For example, the Dutch eco-village case, whose planned development is adjacent to a Natura 2000 area is actively approaching the responsible authorities with a suggestion that would support both the eco-village plans and the Natura 2000 area:

[The eco-village] will be the neighbour of the State Forest Agency, and the neighbouring land falls under the Natura 2000 restrictions; and they are now offering their help to manage the neighbourhood. Because they are striving for a nature positive environment and they don't want to restrict that to the terrain that they are maybe acquiring. So that's also a part of the strategy, that's being a good neighbour and producing a lot of, yeah, ecological pluses. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1).

Mechanisms for transformative innovation

Loorbach's et al. (2020) typology of generic strategies and mechanisms through which transformative innovations develop and diffuse include the categories *Growing*, *Replicating*, *Partnering*, *Instrumentalising* and *Embedding*. These are identified in the case studies to varying degrees.

What particularly stands out in the case studies is the extensive use of **instrumentalising**, i.e. identifying and making use of opportunities within the bureaucratic setting (Loorbach et al., 2020). In the case studies, ambitions to instrumentalise are heavily focused on working in project form towards their goals. This can aptly be conceptualised as **projectification**. The choice to participate in the BIOTraCes project is in itself an example of the importance of this strategy. At the core of the projectification theme are two processes: Fundraising and Gaining access to competencies.

Fundraising is, unsurprisingly, a key issue of projectification. While mainly a means to an end rather than an end in themselves, these are nevertheless crucial parts of strategy bundles and provide necessary prerequisites. The activities of the various stakeholders presuppose access to resources, not least financial ones. Therefore, the stakeholders engage in numerous fundraising activities, mainly applying for means through formal channels but in some cases also informally, e.g. volunteers who contribute with their work, time and skills, and crowdfunding/donations.

[The local organisation] have mainly shifted /.../ to what they call the proposal phase, which is a planning; and also fund scoping, phase. And currently, they have also really specialised in European projects, European planning. So they

managed to capture [a] considerable quantity of funds. (Italian case, Interview 1)

...the reason why these initiatives [such as Foodpark Amsterdam] are somehow still so resilient and really managing a lot with very little [...] resources is because they have the community support, and that is also financial. So there's crowd funding going on, but also a lot of volunteer support, and spaces are rented for free or there are donations. (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview 1)

For some case studies (e.g. the Spanish case), a key goal is to get a regular, annual budget in place to provide the schoolyard greening initiative with a stable source of funding and thus a possibility to plan further ahead than what is possible within one-year budget cycles. Insecure and short-term funding is also highlighted e.g. in the Italian case, with projects being funded one at a time in a competitive context. Regarding competition, other case studies (e.g. the Portuguese case) also find that different local initiatives seek to acquire the same limited funds. Also, in several cases there are no funds available locally and instead must be sought at higher levels, not least EU funding.

The second main theme related to projectification is *gaining access to competencies*. In addition to having sufficient funds, the cases are also dependent on access to human resources with relevant skill sets. Stakeholders therefore engage professionals with the necessary competences to pursue the different missions:

... once this interdepartmental cooperation was established, they had most of the contacts and competences to carry out the project, like a lot of expertise, for instance on nature-based solutions from the [the partner organisation] CEA. There's also, yeah, an architect in the CEA, even though in some cases they did also employ some private architects. (Spanish case, Interview 1)

In several cases these skills and competencies represent a rather high level of specialisation. Human resources are at times part and parcel of the fundraising strategy, since e.g. writing successful funding proposals is a demanding task that requires particular competences. In the Italian case, some stakeholders who have been involved in the initiative for a long time have attained PhD-level education, at least partly motivated by a wish to be better able to secure funding from e.g. the EU. The Italian case is also the one where the projectification strategy takes its most advanced forms, e.g. through the establishment of a dedicated support organisation:

Recently, the Simeto Participatory Presidium has decided to give rise to a cooperative specialised in fund scoping and project planning. This cooperative is called Nesti and is conceived as an instrument to enhance the overall capability to intercept funds and invest on new projects. (Italian case, Monitoring Form)

Several case studies feature elements of **partnering**, i.e. cooperating with other similar initiatives (Loorbach et al., 2020). This takes various forms, from loose contacts between grassroots organisations or municipalities, learning from others' experience (similar cases elsewhere), or more formalised cooperation of independent agents working towards similar goals. In the Lithuanian case, a form of partnering also occurs at the level of the case study research team, who collect and mediate knowledge from other international experiences to the local case:

...it is important to listen to others, I mean, and just try to see what works best because we already have had meetings with international researchers who work in other countries of the world, like in Canada and France, with river dam removal and the communities within which a river dam will be removed. So they have a lot of experience, do's and don'ts, you know, from their case studies. (Lithuanian case, Interview 1)

Replication refers to cross-context transfer (Loorbach et al., 2020), and in the BIOTraCes case studies this appears to be mainly an issue of different geographical contexts (rather than e.g. sectoral context). The Portuguese case and Romanian case both include examples where other similar agents (e.g. municipalities) are following along on the trail blazed by the cases; or where some form of expansion or upscaling is discussed:

...there is evidence that these new practices in Mértola and surrounding municipalities have reached new followers and supporters /.../ in the Baixo Alentejo Region, with other municipalities following the paths of Mértola Municipality and partners towards proximity agriculture (and promoting economic flows among them to support the local dimension). (Portuguese case, Monitoring Form)

The strategy of **growing**, i.e. quantitative increase in members/supporters (Loorbach et al., 2020), occurs in a couple of case studies. This is also related to outreach activities as a way of attracting others to join the movement, e.g. in the Dutch eco-village case:

They're very well connected to the municipality. They have short lines, so they also presented their ideas quite well /.../ [and] they use the strategy of like organising events for themselves, but also to attract others to join De Beuk. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1)

Attempts at **embedding** (Loorbach et al., 2020) occur in the case studies to some degree where stakeholders are working/pushing for the biodiversity initiative to become the norm or mainstreamed through some kind of institutionalisation of innovative practices currently considered as alternative. As in the Spanish case: *'the goal is to fully institutionalise the project'* (Spanish case, Monitoring form). However, while embedding is part of the strategic approaches in some cases, so far there are few signs of the initiatives succeeding in this regard.

CHALLENGES AND DIFFICULTIES

Figure 6-8 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to challenges and difficulties in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-8: *Challenges and difficulties – themes and sub-themes*

There are various examples of obstacles for efficient implementation of biodiversity initiatives and associated strategies. One issue concerns organisational change/redesign resulting in the disappearance of key actors/roles/functions, as in the Lithuanian case. Another source of difficulty, again illustrated by the Lithuanian case, is the politically motivated reluctance of key actors to take action due to disincentives for addressing controversial issues, driven by concerns about jeopardising their chances of re-election.

Many of the perceived restrictions are related to **funding and budget issues**. For example, key actors' unwillingness to accept a certain economic risk has closed the door to a potentially fruitful approach in the Dutch eco-village case:

There is a legal possibility for the public administration on the municipal level to acquire the land [on which to develop an eco-village] before it is publicly commissioned. That is called the First Land Rights and they could do that and then set up a new procurement for public-private commissioning. But the municipality doesn't want to do that. There's too much money involved, and they see risks et cetera. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1)

Budget insufficiency is also often related to **lack of political commitment**. Small budgets pose strict limitations to what is doable. If there is no political will in e.g. municipalities to invest in the biodiversity initiatives then the situation is not likely to improve unless finances are found elsewhere. Lack of interest and commitment from political actors, especially when this is in stark contrast with the initiative stakeholders' own efforts, is a source of frustration. As exemplified in the Italian case:

Despite the considerable effort that has been made in in launching and sustaining this innovation; /.../ from the other side, [the] institutional level, there is zero /.../ recognition, and general lack of involvement /.../ and so this can lead to some serious frustration and /.../ make the feeling of invisibility worse. (Italian case, Interview Round 2)

Broader structural constraints that can also impact the opportunities to finance the biodiversity initiatives. In the Netherlands, the current national housing policy effectively disqualifies all but somewhat numerically larger housing development projects from the possibility of being subsidised, causing major disadvantage to a small-scale movement such as the Dutch eco-village case.

Prevalent views and ideas also feature as challenges and can be the cause of staying at status quo despite a clear need for change. In the Lithuanian case such dynamics cause a stalemate and is seen as a reason that strategies are currently lacking. However, the existence of dominant views that run counter to the initiative can also be the very focus of strategies that seek to challenge these, possibly providing an impetus to work for change.

In some cases, the dominance of particular views can generate active **resistance** to the biodiversity initiatives. For example, in the Spanish case certain parents of pupils (boys) at schools whose schoolyards have been 'renaturalised' have voiced negative opinions about the change because it entailed a reduction of space for sport (e.g. grey space football pitches). This example of resistance is seen as emanating from conventional, gendered views of children's activities.

Strategy implementation in the Italian case and Portuguese case is to some extent complicated by their prerequisites in terms of basic **geographical traits**. In the Italian case, the context of the case study is a large and administratively complex area made up of ten municipalities which share a need for externally financed interventions. In the Portuguese case, the dispersed settlement structure of Mértola, with more than a hundred villages scattered across the municipality, is also seen as a challenge.

Finally, some difficulties arise in connection to **stakeholder heterogeneity, dynamics and representation**. These issues need to be moderated and balanced in accordance with the principle of equal treatment. However, some case studies have experienced problems of representation of certain groups, either in the initiative implementation from a general point of view or in specific activities/situations. For example, the Portuguese case has not managed to reach vulnerable groups such as migrants or Roma people – an example which also relates to the abovementioned geographically-based challenges:

Roma communities, migrants, even these isolated villagers are not being reached, and often public institutions don't show a strong concern about including them. (Portuguese case, Interview Round 2)

In the Romanian case, social dynamics and power asymmetries during workshops caused women to fall silent when certain (male) 'authority figures' (Romanian case, Interview Round 2) were present. To bypass this problem, the women were approached separately. In the Hungarian case, efforts have been made to make sure that benefits of the initiative are well distributed across different sub-groups within the herding community – where some voices are louder than others – and to avoid social tension or rivalry.

TRANSFORMATIVE POTENTIAL

Figure 6-9 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related to the transformative potential of strategies in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-9: Transformative potential – themes and sub-themes

Opportunities

Concerning the transformative potential of the strategies employed in the case studies, several opportunities are identified (see also [Opportunities for leverage and amplification \(T3.1\)](#)). Across several cases, **collaboration and networking** is seen as a key feature. This can take many forms, from organising informal local cooperation among neighbours (e.g. Swedish case), involvement of NGOs in local community activities (e.g. Romanian case), innovating within incumbent organisations or establishing new ones (Swedish case and Dutch eco-village cases), collaboration between local stakeholders and researchers (the Hungarian and Italian cases), seeking political support from formal government agents (e.g. Dutch Foodpark case), and building alliances with other, similar social movements (Dutch Foodpark and Dutch eco-village case). These activities all involve interacting and developing connections with others. In some cases, they are expressions of consciously devised strategies, and in other cases develop ad hoc rather than by design. Collaboration and networking can support the biodiversity initiatives through e.g. a way of building critical mass behind them. In the Dutch Province case of Overijssel, networking activities have resulted in a broader platform from which to act:

One transformative potential that is within the Province is the network building that they're doing. First it was quite small, only internal, and they call it the 'dark green' people and now they're also reaching the 'lighter green' people. [...] if you talk about changing values, that has a truly potential if you start from

within and everyone activates each other and it's also, empowering to know that they are part of some kind of movement. (Focus group discussion)

Networking can become a force for transformative change through the development of a sufficiently broad base and frequent interaction so that key stakeholders (e.g. local government) are compelled to listen to, and consider, the message conveyed. However, building networks and collaboration with a diverse set of actors can also entail difficulties, as exemplified in the Italian case concerning power relations between the various stakeholders:

The strength is that I think a very good point of this strategy is how many different actors are involved. And a weakness is the power imbalance, because we are talking a small local municipality with local association versus like amazon kind of dimension. So it's a big challenge. (Focus group discussion)

Many cases highlight the role of individuals or small groups of enthusiasts. The importance of these **torchbearers** lies in them dedicating their time and efforts (whether professionally, privately or on a volunteer basis) to spread awareness, push for change and motivate others to become actively involved. As described regarding the Romanian case:

Certain members of the community have the passion and the will and the mental capacity and energy to inspire other people and to coordinate, and the time availability at some point to do it. (Focus group discussion)

One way of building momentum for change is for these torchbearers to work from within relevant stakeholder organisations, as suggested in e.g. the Swedish case:

...there are some that are really engaged in environmental issues and could be spearheading in this already existing organisation, /.../ spreading awareness and knowledge and /.../ self-esteem. (Focus group discussion)

Torch bearing can also be done by proxy, e.g. using the medial reach and influence of 'famous people' (Focus group discussion) as a way of drawing attention to one's goals, as in the Dutch Foodpark case.

However, heavy reliance on particular individuals of course comes with a degree of vulnerability. For example, if biodiversity initiatives are closely connected to local politicians' and their agendas there is uncertainty should they not be re-elected once the term of office concludes. As in the Portuguese case:

...there is an instability in terms of if this local government will stay [after the elections]. /.../ I think if the government changed, we would try to find other ways to organise and to relay the municipality to this project. But it may be hard. (Focus group discussion)

Also, a potential shortcoming associated with strong beliefs and dedication is the risk for inability to consider other perspectives than that/those seen as most important. The Lithuanian case exemplifies how stakeholders may need to weigh in the views and values of other actors rather than implement strategies completely based on one single perspective. Otherwise, strategies are at risk of turning out inefficient or even counterproductive e.g. through triggering locked positions between stakeholders rather than contributing to progress:

A stakeholder for biodiversity side /.../ has these like strong views, you know, that /.../ at any cost /.../ [the river dam] has to be dismantled and so on. /.../ So, the strategy /.../ to just go and say and prove that 'this needs to be done', sometimes – [s/he] has a point, but it's not /.../ effective. Yeah, so this is like the weakness, but also the strength, that [they] really want [change]. (Focus group discussion)

Most case studies emphasise the importance of knowledge-oriented strategies and indeed they do address various forms of knowledge: locally specific and context-based, traditional, expert, and knowledge as a means to counter misconceptions. **Building knowledge** fosters greater **awareness** and **shifts in values** which can, in turn, enhance confidence and empowerment, often stimulating behavioural change such as individual choices that diverge from peer norms or external expectations. For example, the Swedish case suggests how local knowledge can be mobilised within organisations to challenge entrenched structures like the prevailing industrial forestry logic. Another example, where knowledge is needed for 'myth busting' purposes, is the Dutch eco-village case whose '*their aim is to show and prove that building with nature is not a limitation, is not more expensive and does not have to be elitist*' (Focus group discussion). A recurring issue in the Romanian case is reconnecting people – not least children – with nature through ecological knowledge:

...the solutions [people suggested] to cope with biodiversity loss and other problems /.../ [were largely] about information and awareness campaigns. /.../ that people need to be much more aware of the value of nature, about its contribution for the people. /.../ for example /.../ to organise some courses for children in nature /.../ because they were saying that the traditional ecological knowledge is lost. And this could be a very good way to revive this knowledge. (Focus group discussion)

Knowledge can also be used to build a strong argument and simultaneously provide legitimacy for the initiative, as in the Dutch Foodpark case, where the initiators organised a joint fact-finding session together with the municipality of Amsterdam (who afterwards referred to it primarily as an in-depth conversation):

Both parties brought a number of experts and then, together with these experts, they discussed a series of key topics ranging from urban planning, to infrastructure, ecology, and food in order to discuss the value and necessity of a food park versus a business park. The final report is also creating a kind of legitimacy for the Foodpark. (Focus group discussion)

The case study initiatives often have broader goals besides stimulating biodiversity; mostly emphasising the concomitant support of social goals, in line with transformative change theory. These **biodiversity co-benefits** include for example addressing gender relations, social justice and inclusivity, environmental justice, economic regional development (e.g. livelihood diversification), organisational and governmental development (e.g. participatory work processes). For example, the Romanian case features tourism development in rural areas, paying attention to visitor-host relationships and socioeconomic dynamics:

It's a question of ethics, because we want them to stay there, you know, and when we go there, those two day[s] /.../, to enjoy the natural landscape /.../ homemade food and so on. And then it's not fair to keep them in the same

state of economic, low economic standards and so on just to be, just to enjoy this, I think it's almost a museum. (Focus group discussion)

Drawing attention to the biodiversity initiative is oftentimes an important part of the strategies. Communication and outreach activities, not least through media, is a way to draw positive attention, generate interest and foster recognition. This builds pressure on other actors to act in desired way. It also contributes to internal empowerment among the stakeholders. For example, in the Dutch Foodpark case, Foodpark Amsterdam has a deliberate media strategy which also builds on the professional journalistic competences of people involved:

...they're very experienced in making their voice heard /.../ and also seen, so there are really nice visuals, nice movies, nice little -, but they organise a lot of activities so they're making themselves well known. (Focus group discussion)

Media and public debate more generally can also provide a way of gaining political attention to key issues, especially when opportunities arise to *strike while the iron is hot*. For example, in the Swedish case, forestry has recently become a central and timely topic in public debates because of both the EU nature restoration law and the broader sustainability discussion.

Another important aspect is **demonstrating alternatives (without lecturing)**. This entails showing other actors that business-as-usual approaches are not the only ways of doing things, thereby inspiring them to try something different. If possible, this should preferably be combined with providing support (technical, financial) to those who choose to embrace a biodiversity-friendly path over conventional ones. This can be done in a low-key way, as in the Portuguese case:

...they are not telling everyone that they are talking about syntropic agriculture, but they are disseminating the principles. And because they are not all the time preaching syntropic agriculture things has happened as they as they want /.../. And it's a success. (Portuguese case, Interview Round 2)

Similarly in the Dutch Province case, deliberate choice of wording is seen as necessary given political prerequisites: the current regional parliament includes a strong farmers' party which tends to view nature in opposition to agriculture. Therefore, using strategically chosen terms influences the chances of gaining political support, or at least avoiding opposition:

So, they don't use the words 'nature' or 'biodiversity', but they focus more on using 'green'. That's a very subtle, but also a very important change. (Dutch Province case, Interview Round 2)

Most of the BIOTraCes case study biodiversity initiatives are similar to **Small Wins** approaches (Termeer et al. 2024; Termeer & Dewulf 2019; see [Pathways as ideal-types for strategic action](#)). They are mainly small scale, locally focused/anchored initiatives. These features come with certain advantages. They can allow for efficient problem solving because problems that emerge tend to also be locally confined to a substantial degree and therefore more delimited and manageable (e.g. Hungarian case). Also, starting out small and locally based is a way of initiating a conversation that can subsequently grow and broaden to other locally pertinent issues (e.g. Lithuanian case).

However, the expected impacts of the biodiversity initiatives are sometimes seen from an at least partially sceptical point of view, especially considering the potential for scaling. For example, the Swedish case study describes a group of like-minded local forest owners with ideas about alternative forestry, but who are too minor and too much of a ‘*random occasion*’ (Focus group discussion) to have any real impact on the forest industry. The Romanian case is another example of context-specific, structural factors that pose significant barriers and limit the potential for scaling/innovation diffusion:

Things in Romania change from top to down, unfortunately. What we are doing at the local level will remain at the local level. And I don't know if they will have a very relevant impact, a very small impact probably. (Focus group discussion)

Even though the tangible outcomes may be minor, they can nevertheless¹ represent important steps towards something bigger, especially if considered in relation to the many other similar initiatives taking place. ‘Small Wins’ refers precisely to such accumulation of many individually small successes. For example, the Spanish case concerns schoolyard greening on a scale that is ‘*not in itself going to do much for biodiversity*’ (Focus group discussion). Rather, the physical change is at the surface of the initiative which is mainly about creating prerequisites for children to connect with nature. Moreover, even if the tangible end results are humble, they should be considered in relation to the baseline, which in this case was virtually no greenery whatsoever:

What we find when we arrive [at the schoolyard], it's an asphalted surface. 90% of those surfaces are covered by a sport field. Usually there is no single square meter of grass or any tree or any bush, anything. While the rest of the urban area is very green. We have one of the most green capitals, not only in the national level, but also we're the third [most] green European capital in Europe. So, ironically our schools are just black, black and grey. (Focus group discussion)

Barriers

Slowness and inertia in processes of change is the most common barrier to transformative potential of the biodiversity initiatives and the strategies implemented therein. The reasons vary. Regulations and associated formalities can delay key processes, thereby effectively acting as barriers to the implementation of initiatives, as e.g. in the Romanian case or the Dutch eco-village case:

Although regulations aim to prevent overexploitation, locals highlight that ‘by the time permits are approved, it's often too late’, reflecting delays in decision-making. (Romanian case, Monitoring form)

...the [land] right now has a forest designation partly, so it still has to be put into a building designation which will have the result that the land will be much more expensive. And of course, the landowners first want to wait for that before they're going to sell it. (Dutch eco-village case, Interview 1)

In some cases, small seeds for change take a long time to grow into something more substantial. As in the Swedish case) ‘...[new approaches] *might spread but it might take 200 years. So who knows? Is that fast enough? No, I don't think so*’ (Focus group discussion). In contrast, the Romanian case is an example of how allowing things to take time and being patient with the process has paid off through the reestablishing of a

previously abandoned occupation: *'...it's a big effort, it takes time, but I see now an important and people got involved and they appreciate nature and they know how to harvest this'* (Focus group discussion). Another source of slowness is how organisations are run. If, for instance, the internal work processes are based on full inclusion and consensus then reaching a decision can entail inertia, hampering swift action. As described in the Dutch eco-village case:

To safeguard the principle of equity and justice they do everything by social decision-making. So no decision is made unless everyone agrees. And otherwise, if someone disagrees, they can deliberate about it until agreement. The weakness of that is that it takes time. It's slow. And sometimes in order to achieve what is most important right now, a tangible outcome, you need more quickness. So this is a risk at the moment. (Focus group discussion).

Slowness can also result from working towards a vast goal such as systemic change. For example, the Italian case includes farmers working to transform incumbent citrus monoculture farming into *'a more biodiverse kind of environment'*. Although this is going well and is even quite efficient, it is nevertheless *'super slow. It's a decades kind of perspective'* (Focus group discussion).

In some cases, there are underlying, systemic problems that are difficult to efficiently address; and **key issues are out of reach** for the stakeholders. In the Dutch eco-village case, the main barriers to achieving their goals are national level regulations; and in the Romanian case the basic problem is described as a corrupt political system. Since the basic underlying problems are (too) difficult to address they are perhaps not the best place for stakeholders to direct their energy, at least not in the shorter term. As pointed out concerning the Romanian case:

It's very important when we think of strategies to think of the actions over which we have the control, [which] we can change. (Focus group discussion)

In a few case studies, the informants highlight that **suboptimal strategies** have been chosen rather than the most appropriate ones. In the Dutch eco-village case, given the goal of planning and building an eco-village, legal support could have significantly strengthened the current set of strategies (which mainly focus on collaboration and seeking municipal support):

It would have been wise if they would have invested more in the legal aspects. Because it is in the legal aspects that their limitations are, but also where the possibilities lie for change [...] ...norms for building, norms for construction, norms for processes, participation processes, norms for... Also, regulations about land ownership. (Focus group discussions)

In the Lithuanian case the approach is passive, at best reactive, and lacks any distinctive strategies. Consequently there is little potential for transformative change, in fact the opposite is more likely:

Of course it is counter-transformative. 'Cause if you don't have strategy or you are ignorant, nothing happens. So no change. No, transformation. Nothing to scale. (Focus group discussions)

OUTCOMES

Figure 6-10 provides an overview of themes and sub-themes related outcomes in the cross-case analysis.

Figure 6-10: *Outcomes – themes and sub-themes*

A key focus is the outcomes achieved in the BIOTraCes biodiversity initiatives and their link to the strategies used. These outcomes span material changes, shifts in behaviour or values, and organisational development.

Many initiatives remain in early stages, while others (e.g. the Italian case, the Portuguese case, the Hungarian case) have been active for years, predating BIOTraCes. During data collection, all case studies and research activities were ongoing, and outcomes had not yet been formally evaluated or reported.

Attributing results to specific interventions is also challenging due to the complex contexts in which the initiatives operate. This is especially true for efforts aimed at fostering knowledge, awareness, or changes in norms—processes that evolve slowly and may yield visible effects only long after the project’s conclusion. As stated concerning the Italian case:

...this kind of open process makes it a little difficult to pinpoint a clear beginning and end of a specific innovation or a specific outcome. (Italian case, Interview Round 2).

Tangible impacts

Various concrete accomplishments have been made by the biodiversity initiatives and stakeholders therein; often seen as attributable to successful implementation of well-chosen strategies. For example, in the Spanish case 14 ‘renaturalised’ schoolyards are a key result:

It started with a /.../ manifesto by educational communities to ask for improved school environments [which] was taken up by the City Council, was translated into a pilot program, which is then administrated by different institutional entities (Spanish case, Interview Round 2).

The Dutch Foodpark case has reached partial accomplishment of their goals through winning a tender that allows them to develop a pilot implementation of their vision. This is seen as closely connected to the strategic approach:

So they're able to realise their part of their ambition in a much smaller area. That's a clear sign that the way in which Foodpark has manifested themselves at the level of the municipality, but also in public communication and the other things that they do, it is resulting in this recognition. (Dutch Foodpark case, Interview Round 2)

Several case studies (e.g. the Hungarian case and Italian case) have resulted in the production of educational/communication material and exhibitions e.g. at museums and events (festival, congress). Together with e.g. websites and digital meetings, they are parts of the outreach activities of the initiatives. These outcomes are in line with the emphasis on information and knowledge-oriented strategies in many of the cases, and may well have contributed to some degree to an evolution of knowledge and awareness in targets groups.

The Portuguese case and Swedish case both include examples of experiments with alternative practical approaches in agriculture and forestry. In the Swedish case, some of the participating private forest owners have e.g. planted alternative tree species, avoided clear-cut harvesting in pursuit of non-economic forest values, or commissioned a biologist – rather than a forestry industry representative – to develop their forest management plan. However, these examples are quite few. The Portuguese case entails more systematic experimentation with methods for soil improvement (reversal of degradation). Data collection and valuation and have shown that soil fertility has indeed improved, thus strengthening the evidence base for these syntropic agricultural approaches in semi-arid contexts such as Mértola. In addition, the Mértola case also entails efforts to restore the habitats of threatened steppe birds, including:

*...roller birds, *Croesus garrulus*, [...] in Portuguese 'rolieiro', one of the ground nesting birds in Portugal that is critically threatened due to changes in the use of soil. This roller is important to agriculture because it's a kind of bioindicator of farming practice. So when [it] disappears, something bad is happening in terms of the quality of the soil. (Portuguese case, Interview Round 2)*

The Portuguese case also entails a series of connected activities and initiatives which together have contributed to 'the forging of a local food system' (Portuguese case, Interview Round 2) involving food production, consumption, Importantly, the Mértola case has also generated interest from other municipalities in the Baixo Alentejo region and thus shows signs of a potential upscaling in the form of geographical diffusion (i.e. *scaling out*, Moore et al. 2015; see also [Opportunities for leverage and amplification \(T3.1\)](#)).

Behavioural change

The case studies provide several examples of behavioural change in the target groups. Different choices and patterns of practice develop, and new conversations take place. For example, the herder community in the Hungarian case shows signs of broadening its horizons and system of thought and self-perception in relation to wider society – a change that could perhaps be considered as transformative within the group:

...now they are not just thinking about themselves as a society, 'what should be done for us', but they are thinking in a big picture. And from a very traditional and culturally segregated group it is a big movement. (Hungarian case, Interview Round 2)

Behavioural change is often a subtle, gradual process that evolves over time, as suggested by e.g. the Lithuanian case study. In this process, important early steps can be to open up for discussing topics that were previously perceived as too sensitive or controversial, such as dam removal:

[It's about] planting a seed. Of course, it's a really long process for community to adopt new ideas and change dramatically. But I think the main outcome is that people are not afraid to talk [...] about this topic. (Lithuanian case, Interview Round 2)

The temporal aspect of behavioural change is also highlighted in the Swedish case, where intergenerational transfer of forest property can provide a window of opportunity for breaking path dependency and moving from conventional to alternative, biodiversity-oriented forestry methods:

We have [...] examples of forest owners who have been doing conventional forestry for the entire 20th century and then the new generation is coming and they want to, they have perhaps read something about mixing tree species and then [...], the old generation listens to them, while they're still the forest owners, they listen to the new generation and try to involve them in decision making. And then there's a larger diversity on the forest property. (Swedish case, Interview Round 2)

Knowledge and awareness

Many of the biodiversity initiatives focus their strategies on knowledge and awareness of biodiversity issues that are relevant in the respective contexts. There are examples where these strategies seem to have succeeded in furthering such development, at least to some degree. For example, the Romanian case study has observed a certain rise in local awareness of biodiversity values, and knowledge exchange has taken place between local communities and researchers. The Hungarian case entails intergenerational reproduction of professional traditional knowledge within the herder community, as well as knowledge exchange between herders and researchers and knowledge transmission to other sectors. The latter includes decision-making bodies for the agriculture sector and thus suggest that certain *scaling up* (Moore et al. 2015) to the institutional context has taken place. In the Italian case, knowledge of current conditions and problems are seen as a source of empowerment, and analysis of the local socio-ecological system has contributed to:

...building relationships, deepening awareness of biodiversity and complex psychologies [...] of the Simeto valley. In order to give [...] a more complex and multi-layered picture of the valley. (Italian case, Interview Round 2)

Discourse and values

Change in terms of discourses and values (cf. scaling deep (O'Brien et al. 2024; Moore et al. 2015)) entail issues such as care, pride, identity, place attachment, wellbeing and a sense of responsibility for future generations. For example, the Spanish case initiative demonstrates both social care for peers and care for the local environment:

There are schools that implement a care program where the older kids teach the younger kids how to take care of the school yard, how to maintain it, also care about the plants, care for the other kids. So there's like a whole discursive shift that we notice from people participating and also from the educational communities. (Spanish case, Interview Round 2)

In the Swedish case, those forest owners who felt strong place attachment (e.g. through living on or close to the property or family historic connections) had a caring perspective in their land ownership. This in turn translated into forest management approaches that reflect long-term thinking and consideration of future generations.

The Romanian case emphasises how local communities have begun connecting biodiversity with local and cultural identity, heritage and wellbeing, as well as a sense of pride in traditional knowledge and practices.

The strategy employed was framing low intensity farming as innovation, not just tradition. So the farmers, they began to see /.../ that their practices are not [seen as] old or backward or..., but as valuable, as important for biodiversity goals. (Romanian case, Interview Round 2)

Networks, relationships and social cohesion

Outcomes related to the building of networks, relationships and/or social cohesion are found in several case studies. In the Dutch eco-village case, a strong internal network and social cohesion within the movement plays an important role:

Now, because the uncertainty is still there, the strategy is focusing a little bit more to the insides /.../, 'how can we keep the community together and stay positive and really keep working towards our common goal' (Dutch eco-village case, Interview Round 2)

Social cohesion is also emphasised in the Portuguese case, Romanian case and Italian case, among others. In the Portuguese case, elderly people participated more actively than expected, and their knowledge was explicitly recognised. Similarly, the Romanian case revealed strong local social cohesion across diverse 'fields and domains', which facilitated internal dialogue among stakeholders. In the Italian case, change is likewise viewed as dependent on local social processes as they evolve over time.

External networking and relationships between actors and across sectors are another outcome in several cases. Connections have been established between local communities/stakeholders, local and regional level government bodies and other organisations, and researchers. Some of the case studies (Portuguese case, Hungarian case) also report that once networking activities within take off, change can advance at a rapid pace. In several cases, the forging of relationships deliberately aims to build trust as a prerequisite for dialogue and interaction. This is especially pertinent for researcher–local community interactions, e.g. in the Hungarian case and Romanian case.

Organisational learning and maturity

A final set of outcomes concern the organisations involved in the interventions and how they have developed and matured over time. Several case studies report organisational learning in terms of workflows/internal processes, the design or participatory activities, 'self-awareness', and internal integration/coordination within an organisation. For example, the Spanish case shows how the schoolyard greening initiative has moved into a more mature state characterised by more momentum and a stronger ability to both voice demands and to raise/apply for additional funds: 'there was a huge process of learning' (Spanish case, Interview Round 2). The Dutch eco-village case has also, over time, shifted their approach regarding internal organisation from 'central' coordination towards decentralisation and distributing responsibility and ownership for tasks and action plans within the network.

Unsurprisingly, organisational maturity is reported in cases that have a longer history than the BIOTraCes time frame, such as the Portuguese case and Dutch Foodpark case. The Foodpark movement is well organised, has a carefully designed strategic approach, and is run by people with, in part, relevant professional backgrounds and with strong voices. The Portuguese case highlights the importance of commitment and perseverance. It has also opted for a co-governance strategy where participation of local organisations is welcomed but not 'forced', and which tries...:

...to respect the rhythms [of local stakeholders and organisations] in the sense that they decide when to come and how to come. (Portuguese, Interview Round 2)

6.3 Concluding discussion

Strategy is, at its core, about devising and implementing routes towards reaching goals. This also entails planning and anticipating alternative scenarios and preparing to navigate in a context of uncertainty. Strategising means thinking ahead while recognising that not all 'ifs and buts' can be controlled or even foreseen. In the BIOTraCes case studies of biodiversity initiatives across Europe, approaches to strategising for biodiversity initiatives vary considerably. The range from an apparent absence of strategy to highly structured, theoretically informed, and carefully targeted approaches. These variations should be understood in relation to the highly diverse institutional, governance, and geographical and socio-cultural contexts within which the initiatives have emerged and operate, as well as the scope and complexity of the initiatives as such.

While not every challenge can be anticipated, many potential obstacles – and likewise many opportunities – can be envisioned. This allows for at least broad-brush planning for alternative scenarios and backcasting strategies to support the materialisation of desired ones. The formulation of a coherent strategic framework can help identify an initiative's potential sphere of influence and control while also clarifying its outer boundaries, to clarify the most efficient direction for strategic efforts, at least in the short term. Within their respective spheres of influence, initiatives (organisations, movements, etc.) can build internal capacity through development of competencies and extend their influence through targeted cooperation with other actors and stakeholders. This can include cross-sectoral networking both horizontally, e.g. within peer groups, or across geographical or sector settings; or vertically, e.g. across geographical-administrative levels.

At the time of writing, it is still too early to draw firm conclusions about the initiatives of the BIOTraCes case studies and their strategies; or indeed about the connection between the different strategies employed and the impacts that have been observed so far. Nevertheless, there are indications to suggest that the mere presence of explicit strategies relate to a sense of direction, momentum and resilience that can be considered as prerequisites for leverage. Strategic mixes can be designed to provide structures to support action while also leaving room for flexibility. They can include several time scales, e.g. long-term visions combined with short-term agility in response to changes in dynamic external contexts characterised by many 'moving parts' (e.g. political, economic or social factors). Longer-term strategies might e.g. emphasise how the zone of influence of the biodiversity initiatives might expand to reach more high hanging fruits. Processes of reflexive learning and feedback allows strategies to evolve as implementation progresses. Hence, planning for a strategic approach benefits from being understood as an iterative, adaptive and agile process, not a fixed and rigid 'blueprint'.

The biodiversity initiatives cover many aspects related to the supra-level strategies of IPBES/O'Brien et al. (2024; see also [Routes to transformative change](#)). For example, they are all engaged in 'driv[ing] systemic change in the sectors most responsible for nature's decline', many focus on 'shift[ing] views and values to recognise human-nature interconnectedness', or 'transform[ing] governance systems to be integrative, inclusive, accountable and adaptive'. They also represent many of the more specific 'actions' such as addressing social norms and cultural narratives, co-creating knowledge, adaptive learning, inclusive governance (IPBES/O'Brien et al. 2024; see [IPBES' overarching strategies](#)). The biodiversity initiatives employ varying strategies, often mixing different emphases. Not least, information and knowledge-oriented strategies including e.g. awareness-raising, co-learning, and communicative activities (comparable to 'sermons' (Pacheco-Vega's 2020)), are commonly used – not least in those biodiversity initiatives that have already reported tangible outcomes. Such approaches may also have indirect effects by shaping values, attitudes, and informal norms – thereby influencing the policy or economic spheres over time. Information- and knowledge-oriented strategies are potentially efficient in many cases, but the apparent fondness for them is perhaps also a result of a mix of the initiatives' access to resources (especially financial means) and (formal) power. The stakeholders do not represent government bodies responsible for formally devising policy with budgets for e.g. economic incentive schemes and explicit instruments. However, they are nevertheless able to apply strategies oriented towards economic or regulatory *issues* in a broader, indirect way – not least when combined with information and knowledge-oriented strategies. Economic and regulatory issues are of key importance in many case studies, and the strategic efforts often entail attempts to achieve changes in these areas. For all strategic options, the case studies also show the need for careful adjustment and contextual sensitivity for local prerequisites.

Relations between stakeholders at various governance levels and across sectors are of substantial importance in the cases. Differences in power, values, and interests between actors are relatively common, and tensions may arise e.g. when initiatives challenge established structures or dominant agendas. Anticipating such dynamics and planning for how to grapple with them is likely helpful for maintaining momentum in initiatives, possibly also reducing the common problems of inertia in key work processes. Trust-building and relationship management can be important strategic concerns, as suggested in several case studies. Establishing trust takes time and requires openness, reciprocity, and humility; qualities that are often absent in conventional top-down settings. In contrast, co-

governance models that bring together a variety of actors, e.g. from across the public, private, and civil society spheres can enhance legitimacy and ground initiatives in local contexts, building from the bottom up – e.g. in the low-key, non-lecturing but supportive way suggested in some of the case studies. These approaches can of course entail complexities and potential tensions of their own. Hence, building capacity for persistence and patience regarding the various processes involved in implementing biodiversity initiatives – whether social, bureaucratic or something in-between – are important prerequisites for enduring engagement.

Adequate funding is a necessity for sustained strategic work. The importance of this baseline prerequisites is illustrated through the emphasis of many initiatives on instrumentalising (Loorbach et al. 2020), not least projectification strategies. Given that the biodiversity initiatives are currently generally not well embedded (Loorbach et al. 2020) in e.g. institutional frameworks that could provide a stable financial basis, limited budgets and short-term project cycles constrain the capacity for long-term thinking and increase vulnerability to changes in the external/contextual setting of initiatives. Securing reasonably long-term and stable funding and/or institutional support could make a significant difference in both planning and implementation of the initiatives, especially considering the apparent tendency for the processes involved – not least social ones – to require some time to evolve.

Across the case studies, networking is a key component of the strategic approaches – in line with the theoretical expectation that transformative change requires networked agency (Bouwma et al., 2022; De Castro et al., 2025; Rice et al., 2020; see [Routes to transformative change](#)). Internal networks strengthen social cohesion and a sense of shared purpose, while external networks is a way to exert influence and reach target groups as well as to expand the membership base and tie additional competencies to the initiatives (cf., growing, partnering (Loorbach et al. 2020)). There may be potential especially in cross-level and cross-sectoral collaborations; generally seen as appropriate for handling wicked environmental problems (Vogel et al. 2021). Such constellations provide a broad base with capacity to balance and mitigate (political) volatility at any single governance level and support embedding as well as diffusion and scaling (Moore et al. 2015) of innovations across sectors and contexts.

Taken together, the BIOTraCes case studies of the various biodiversity initiatives suggest that their potential for contributing to transformative change depends less on the presence of any single type of strategy than on the ability to combine planning with adaptability, reflexivity and persistence. The findings indicate that strategies are more efficient when they are open to continuous revision, informed by experience as it unfolds and attuned to local contexts. Small, locally grounded advances may not appear transformative in isolation, but collectively these Small Wins (Termeer et al. 2024; Termeer & Dewulf 2019) can contribute to broader systemic shifts. Revisiting the BIOTraCes cases, currently seeds in different stages of growth (Blythe et al. 2018), will in later stages allow for analysis of the extent to which early strategic orientations have translated into durable, embedded change.

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7 Strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation, dialogue (T3.3)

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7.1 Introduction

The original title of Task 3.3, 'strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation, dialogue', is understood to include participation and other forms of interaction. As a shorthand for these strategies, we will use the term 'co-strategies', with 'co' standing for collaborative or interactive (such as in co-production and co-creation). The reason to dedicate a chapter to this category of strategies, is the assumption that co-strategies have a particular transformative potential (Ansell et al., 2022; Leventon et al., 2022, Reed et al., 2018).

In this chapter, we ask: Which co-strategies are employed in biodiversity innovations? The following section presents the Methods used for collecting and analysing these co-strategies. Next, the Findings section first maps the range and types of co-strategies identified, highlighting recurring orientations such as supporting dialogue, building networks, and formalising processes. This is followed by the Discussion, which reflects on the main patterns and considers implications for transformative governance of biodiversity.

7.2 Methods

The study followed a mixed approach grounded in constructivist assumptions about knowledge co-production and meaning-making. We viewed strategies as relational narratives of change, embedded in institutional and socio-ecological contexts. Narratives can be understood as stories that address a specific problem (beginning), detail core objectives and a sequence of key actions (middle) and propose a solution (end) (Roe, 1994). Strategies similarly can be understood as a story: actors responding to a problem, pursuing objectives, and outlining actions towards a solution. In other words, strategies link interventions (consciously enacted interactions) with transformative dimensions such as intent, process, and outcome.

Our aim was to construct analytically generalisable insights about patterns of transformative strategies across plural contexts. Accordingly, we based this Task's cross-case analysis in the construction of what we call *mini-narratives*: concise accounts capturing how actors pursued particular strategies ('who does what, where, and why'), extracted to fit the dimensions of a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet.

Data collection

As described in [Materials and data collection methods](#), data comprised three complementary sources: written monitoring forms (WP2), two rounds of semi-structured interviews with research partner informants representing nine case studies, and discussions from the 'World Café' workshop held in Hungary.

Data processing and analysis

Two researchers conducted the analysis collaboratively. Each coded a subset of the material using the comment function in Microsoft Word, allowing flexible, transparent coding and exchange. Coding served to make the interpretation of the mini-narratives traceable in the data. In the case of the monitoring forms, fragments of texts were labelled with unique identifiers linked to the spreadsheet containing mini-narratives. In the case of the interviews and the Hungary workshop, a mixed inductive-deductive approach was taken. This approach was derived from theoretical concepts such as the PEPE principles (*pluralising, empowering, politicising, embedding*) and transformative governance literature, with inductive insights emerging from the material itself. From the coded excerpts, the researchers distilled mini-narratives following a standard schema (*actor, activity, resources, target group, context, occasion, purpose, and outcome*). Note that 'mini-narratives' describes the *form* used; these aided the identification of strategies, which reflect content. From this point onward, we will speak of 'strategies' more often than 'mini-narratives', and both terms may be understood as being interchangeable.

We only focused on 'co-strategies' with transformative aspirations – those that can be related to PEPE principles. Other strategies that emerged in the material, i.e. not interactive and/or not transformative (PEPE), were omitted.¹⁰ Next, double entries referring to the same strategy by the same actor were merged. Each was given a unique strategy ID and further annotated with actor type, strategy type, and PEPE attributes (see next section). These strategies were then subjected to thematic analysis to identify cross-case regularities, relational patterns, and distinctive modes of transformative action. The process was abductive and reflexive, iterating between theory and data, and between researchers, to ensure interpretive rigour and transparency.

Analysis from the mini-narratives

We developed working categorisations in an iterative process of data amalgamation and clustering. In line with WP3's objective to distil strategies for integrating biodiversity into decision-making, and T3.3's emphasis on learning, co-creation, and participation ('co-strategies'), we analysed how actors seek to open up, involve, or otherwise influence other actors as part of their (transformative) journeys. To accomplish this, we applied three categorisations to the strategies: actors, interventions, and PEPE (transformative principles). In the case of **actors**, we applied categories for both the actors *doing* the strategies, and for the actors *targeted by* those strategies. In the case of **activities** – the analytical unit describing the interventions or processes undertaken by the actor(s) – we conducted a two-stage abstraction. In the first round, we identified specific *subtypes* of activities; in the second, we grouped these into broader *main types* through interpretive

¹⁰ To provide an example of data processing, we briefly discuss the Lithuanian case study (Free-Flowing Rivers). We initially recorded 6 mini-narratives for Lithuania, sampled from the two interview rounds and the monitoring form. The workshop in Hungary enriched our insight in the case, but did not result in more strategies being added. Out of the six strategies, two – 'Guidebook for local municipalities' (by the research partner MRU) and 'Communicative strategy' (by the national government) – were deemed not to involve potentially transformative co-strategies. In the Guidebook case, the tool aimed at capacity-building but the activity could not be related to PEPE processes. It was not sufficiently convincing as a 'co-strategy'. The second case described the government's reportedly unhelpful communication strategy on dam removal – again not convincing as co-strategy and not tapping into PEPE processes. Next, two strategies employed by the research partner were merged with a third one, as to remove double accounts. Hence, two co-strategies remained.

synthesis. When associating activity types with strategies, we allowed combinations across levels. For instance, the subtype *participatory methods* could be linked not only to the main type *co-building* but also to *encounters* or *multi*, since co-strategies often involve multiple, overlapping processes. Allowing such cross-level combinations enabled us to capture this plurality while retaining analytical specificity.

Lastly, we used **PEPE principles** as categories. From the strategy descriptions we inferred whether strategies aimed at pluralising, empowering, politicising and/or embedding. In about half of the cases the descriptions were explicit about this, mentioning one or more PEPE principles in its activity or purpose. In other cases, PEPE was linked to strategies by coders' interpretation. To support interpretation of how the strategies relate to the PEPE principles, we used the following extended readings of each principle:

Pluralising refers to nurturing diversity in perspectives, knowledges, values, and relations with nature. It emphasises the importance of respecting differences, creating space for genuine engagement including disagreement and contestation, and avoiding premature consensus. Networked learning may also be an example of pluralising: creating space for reflection and considering alternative pathways.

Empowering concerns strengthening the agency and voice of actors who are marginalised, excluded, or less visible in decision-making. Collaborative approaches that facilitate (co-)learning and reflection are key to empower marginalised actors to co-produce actionable transformation options that are nature-positive, equitable and just. While pluralising focuses on ideas and relations to nature, empowering focuses on inclusion of actors and (marginalised) groups.

Politicising addresses structural factors that drive and perpetuate unsustainable practices and behaviours with negative impacts on biodiversity. It aims to make these structural factors explicit and expose their social and cultural character thereby making them amenable for critical assessment and change. Includes challenging power and disrupting systems that need to go.

Embedding captures how transformative practices become institutionalised or sustained. Local initiatives and their innovations can become embedded in (public/private) policies and institutions while at the same time working to transform them. Focuses on implementation, creating the new normal, strengthening the position of currently marginal ideas and groups within the system.

Quantitative analysis

The mini-narratives allowed for complementary quantitative exploration. Although the sample is non-probabilistic and not intended for statistical inference, simple quantitative summaries help to surface recurrent patterns, co-occurrences, and contrasts that might otherwise remain implicit in purely qualitative analysis. In this sense, quantification serves as an analytical aid for pattern detection and internal consistency checks, rather than a basis for generalisation. Our approach therefore remains interpretive, with quantitative outputs used to support transparency and reflexive interpretation of the data.

We interpreted *case study*, *actor*, *activity*, and *target group* as input variables, and PEPE principles as outputs.¹¹ Linking PEPE outputs to *individual strategies* was straightforward, merely requiring numerical counts (i.e. the number of strategies which involved pluralising, empowering, politicising, and/or embedding). Linking PEPE outputs to input variables, however, required more explicit numerical interpretation. The first step was the weighting of strategies. A strategy involving multiple PEPE principle (e.g. pluralising + empowering + politicising = 3 principles) would be counted 3 times, while a ‘single-PEPE’ strategy only once; we applied weighting to account for this. Secondly, we interpreted PEPE as an arc spanning from initial/internal to final/external orientations, expressed as four ordinal steps: pluralising = 1, empowering = 2, politicising = 3, and embedding = 4. For each of the four input variables, PEPE outputs were averaged per category, and the spread was represented as one standard deviation around the mean, thus indicating the extent to which strategies within each category were distributed across the PEPE span. Analysis was performed in R (R Core Team, 2023). Sankey diagrams were created using the *networkD3* package for R (Allaire et al., 2023), and weighted dot-and-bar plots were produced with *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016).

7.3 Findings

We registered a total of 71 co-strategies. The number varied considerably per case study: in relation to the Dutch eco-village case and Portuguese case most co-strategies were mentioned (15 and 14 strategies, respectively), while in the Lithuanian case we identified 2 co-strategies¹² and in the Romanian case 4 co-strategies (Table 7-1).

Table 7-1: Number of co-strategies per case study

Dutch Foodpark case	7	Portuguese case	14	Spanish case	8
Romanian case	4	Lithuanian case	2	Swedish case	6
Hungarian case	7	Italian case	8	Dutch eco-village & Province case	15

ACTORS, TARGET GROUPS, ACTIVITIES AND PEPE

Activity types

To support the analysis of strategies, we abstracted the described activities, resulting in 24 subtypes and 9 main types (Table 7-2). For most strategies, combinations of main types and subtypes adequately captured their core features. Some of the more composite strategies, however, resisted clear categorisation and were therefore grouped under the main type *multi*.

¹¹ We call them ‘PEPE outputs’ but this variable should *not* be seen as *outcomes achieved* from the strategies. PEPE principles were *aspired* in the strategies – to what extent strategies demonstrably contributed to pluralising (etc) ‘in the field’ is another matter.

¹² See note 10 above.

Table 7-2: Overview of activity types in co-strategies, divided over main types and subtypes

Main type	Description and Activity subtypes
Advocacy [11]	Speaking for certain values and ideas, addressing particular target audiences. <i>Subtypes:</i> Activism; Bottom-up action; Experimenting, demonstrating, engaging; Influencing policy through network
Co-building [14]	Building practices and structures together. <i>Subtypes:</i> Bottom-up action; Coalition building; Creating and embedding infrastructure / tools; Network building; Participatory decision-making/ co-governance; Participatory methods
Encounters [24]	Fostering encounters between community members. <i>Subtypes:</i> Collaborative / peer learning; Communicative / Storytelling; Community engagement; Events; Group building; Listening / interviews; Participatory methods; Reflexive encounters; Trust building; Workshops (dialogue / create conversations)
Engaged research [14]	Research and researchers with and for biodiversity innovations. <i>Subtypes:</i> Artistic or creative intervention; Engaged research supporting SP's strategy; Group building; Network building; Workshops (dialogue / create conversations)
Multi [5]	Multi-pronged approaches. <i>Subtypes:</i> Experimenting, demonstrating, engaging; Multi-strategy
Public engagement [3]	Engaging publics/community members (but not necessarily fostering 'encounters' among them). <i>Subtypes:</i> Citizen science; Experimenting, demonstrating, engaging; Training and practical tools

Note that some subtypes belong to multiple main types (elaborated in Methods section).

Actors

To make sense of actors ('who is 'doing' the strategy?'), we formulated five loose categories, applying one per strategy (Table 7-3). When the strategy involved more than one actor, the applied categories would still hold. Since BIOTraCes features a large role for participatory action research (PAR) or other forms of engaged research, the project's research partners (RPs) rank highly in the actor frequency table; highest in fact (n=21). When including strategies where the initiative was shared between RP and the societal partner (or another local innovator network), this number is even higher (n=29).

Local or regional networks working on nature inclusion took the initiative slightly more frequently in our sample (n=32), but in our analysis we decided to split these networks in two categories: focused networks (n=17) and broad networks (n=15). Focused networks include initiatives with a clear mandate or outspoken message or objective. While the word 'network' may sound too ambiguous for these initiatives, we still preferred the term, highlighting how each initiative is composed of (groups of) individuals with varying commitments and capabilities. It also assists comparison with the 'broad networks' in our sample, which includes regional coalitions and umbrella organisations spanning multiple

organisations (NGOs, CSOs, firms), where members have their separate mandates. We did not study these networks themselves in this Task but only focused on the strategies.

Table 7-3: Overview of actor categories

Actor category	Description and examples
Research partner [21]	Includes all BIOTraCes research partners.
Focused network [17]	A group or organisation working together closely to achieve specific (transformative) objectives. Examples: Foodpark Amsterdam (Dutch Foodpark case), De Beuk housing cooperative (Dutch eco-village case), Terra Sintrópica (Portuguese case), and the Swedish Association for Nature Conservation (Swedish case).
Broad network [15]	A local or regional network of actors working together on broader (transformative) objectives. Examples: Local Action Group (Romanian case), Simeto Participatory Presidium (Italian case), Mértola Food Network (Portuguese case), Parents' associations in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spanish case), Forest owners in Sweden (Swedish case).
RP collaborative [8]	Research partner (RP) working together closely with the societal partner (SP) and/or other local (focused or broad) networks.
Local or regional government [10]	A few cases included co-strategies of a local government (CEA department in Vitoria-Gasteiz; Spanish case) or a regional government (Province of Overijssel, Dutch eco-village case). In both cases, these were also Societal Partner in the project.

The number in squared brackets indicates the number of strategies recorded. The examples cover virtually all involved actors, but a few more isolated actors are not mentioned.

A final category includes local and regional governments (n=10). While more layers and bodies of government are implied in BIOTraCes cases, our strategy table included only those governmental strategies that could be seen as co-strategies with PEPE qualities. In the interviews and Hungary workshop we asked informants whether governments and vested interest parties empowered local stakeholders – either through participative policy-making, or through other ways. Almost no formal cases of policy participation occurred across the nine cases, neither at the national nor the local level. Informants in most cases also thought governments did little to *empower* the biodiversity innovations. This does not mean that governments or other vested parties never fulfilled constructive and important roles in the biodiversity innovations; it does mean that we found very few 'potentially transformative co-strategies' coming from these parties (see Box 7-1).

Target groups

In categorising the *target groups* of the strategies, we also stayed deliberately broad. In about half of the cases (n=33), the target groups could be summarised as 'local communities'; sometimes these were more specifically identified as 'school pupils' or 'the

elderly', but we chose to group them under the same label. A smaller sample was directed at communities of farmers, herders or forest owners (n=7), or at biodiversity innovator networks (typically the 'focused networks' above; n=5). Other strategies were directed towards governmental bodies (n=10), or those including established organisations, such as conservation agencies or housing corporations. Combinations of the above – bringing together different communities as well as members of (established) organisations – were targeted in 16 strategies.

Box 7-1: Examples of roles played by governmental and vested interest parties

- The local governance context in **Sicily** (Italian case) was reported to lack any participatory conduct or culture – towards citizens, but also in terms of coordination between institutions.
- Participatory work in the **Romanian** case was in the hands of the Local Action Group, established in 2007 as a public-private partnership under the EU rural economy LEADER programme. Other policy participation at the municipal or national level was not mentioned when prompted.
- In the **Lithuanian** case, the national government provides opportunities (funding) for community initiative, but appears not to align those with the needs of communities.
- In the **Hungarian** case, main government actors are not empowering the herders, but influential people at ‘intermediate’ levels of power *are* getting on board.
- In **Wageningen**, the Netherlands, the social housing corporation supported De Beuk (Dutch eco-village case) with a declaration of intent and funding. The Province of Gelderland also provided funding. The Wageningen municipality consulted De Beuk to improve its policy on ‘collective private commissioning’ (a legal form of co-building).
- In the **Swedish** case, the forest owner organisation acts as a vested interest party and is a slow mover on continuous cover forestry (CCF). Change in this organisation was enforced by a group of members successfully tabling a motion in favour of CCF.
- After an extended period of colliding, **Foodpark Amsterdam** and the Amsterdam municipality engaged in a ‘joint fact-finding process’ (Dutch Foodpark case). It delivered mutual understanding and elevated the position of Foodpark, but was not used subsequently to profoundly revise the existing developing plans and the economic paradigm in order to be transformative.
- In the Portuguese case/**Mértola**, the municipal council fulfils important (even ‘pivotal’ supportive and pro-active roles within the Mértola Food Network. However, different actors in the area work so closely together that the informants found it difficult to tell which initiative should be attributed to the Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA), the municipality, the Food Network, or the rural entrepreneurship NGO ESDIME. In particular the ‘co-strategies’ were less obviously those of the municipality. In our table of co-strategies, we therefore recorded Mértolan strategies as belonging to ‘broad networks’ (except for TSA which is a ‘focused network’).
- We recorded a handful co-strategies with associated PEPE principles for the Netherlands/**Province of Overijssel** (Dutch eco-village case): e.g. participatory design sessions including youth and running the Natuur Voor Elkaar (‘nature for each other’ + ‘nature accomplished’ word play) programme.
- The general experience in the Spanish case/**Vitoria-Gasteiz** is that active citizen participation is declining. However, pro-active participatory conduct by the government is also lacking. That said, we recorded a municipal co-strategy involving citizen science (monitoring biodiversity), as well as a municipal peer learning programme with PEPE qualities.
- Several case studies pointed out that, while **EU policy frameworks** formally require member states to ensure public participation in environmental and spatial governance, these mechanisms often remain procedural and distant from citizens’ everyday realities.

Relation between research partner and the networks involved

The strategies of research partners varied along with the networks in their cases. Table 7-4 shows which type of network the research partners mainly dealt with. In most of the cases, these also were the Societal Partners. In the table, we included targeted communities as 'dispersed networks'.

Table 7-4: Research partners and main networks targeted by them in their participatory research

<i>Cases (by research partner)</i>	<i>Focused networks</i>	<i>Broad networks</i>	<i>Dispersed networks</i>
UT: Dutch Foodpark case	Foodpark Amsterdam		
WR: Dutch eco-village case	De Beuk	Natuur Voor Elkaar (initiative of Province of Overijssel)	
UBB: Romanian case		Local Action Group	
CES: Portuguese case	Terra Sintrópica	Mértola Food Network	
UNICT: Italian case		Participatory Presidium	
BC3: Spanish case		Schools, teachers, parents' associations*†	
CER: Hungarian case	Women herders		Male herders
MRU: Lithuanian case	Dam removal activist‡		River communities*
UGOT: Swedish case			Forest owners

* Not a BIOTraCes Societal Partner.

† The BC3/Spanish case is exceptional in that the Societal Partner involved is a governmental branch, whereas in other cases they are NGOs or other bottom-up actors. The schools, teachers and parents' associations have been a primary focus of the (participatory) research of BC3. Therefore we included those in the table rather than BC3's Societal Partner.

‡ The Societal Partner in the Lithuanian case is an individual and not a 'network'. Nevertheless, we included this partner as a focused network in the analysis. It might be claimed that this activist also works in networked ways, drawing close their allies in the mission of dam removal.

PEPE processes

Of the 71 co-strategies recorded, 42 aimed for pluralising, 43 for empowering, 20 for politicising and 18 for embedding (Figure 7-1). This sum exceeds 71: as mentioned it is possible for a strategy to aim for more than one PEPE process. Indeed, 36 strategies could be associated with multiple PEPE principles, while 35 strategies were associated with single ones. Out of the multi-PEPE strategies, the combination of *pluralising* and *empowering* was observed most often (n=13). This is not surprising, because of the relatively high occurrence of pluralising and empowering (together found 85 times) compared to *politicising* and *embedding* (together found 38 times). They also make for a logical combination: pluralising and empowering often go hand in hand, while politicising and embedding are more distinct processes related to larger (outside) networks. Most of the pluralising+empowering strategies involved participatory activities aimed at community engagement, bringing together different voices to facilitate exchanges on plural values of biodiversity, nature, and/or local identity. Interestingly, this tandem was well balanced across case studies: eight out of all nine biodiversity innovations included pluralising+empowering strategies. When including strategies that include also politicising and/or embedding (i.e. PEP' or PE'E), all nine case studies are represented with at least one strategy (n=23 strategies).

Figure 7-1: Venn diagram displaying PEPE processes associated with co-strategies (n=71)

The full 'PEPE' set was recorded for 6 strategies. These often involved the more overarching strategies of the societal partners. An example is the dynamic and multi-strategy approach of Foodpark Amsterdam (FPA; Dutch Foodpark case). It was reported that FPA consists of 'seasoned activists, always mobilising a diversity of strategies', with a view on their larger transformative ambition (paradigm shift from industry-first to commons-based) and seeking to leverage opportunities and conditions around their main frontline, the Amsterdam Lutkemeerpolder. This 'diversity of strategies' includes co-strategies: we recorded another five for FPA, which together span the PEPE range (Table 7-5), corroborating the overarching co-strategy.

Table 7-5: *Co-strategies of Foodpark Amsterdam (Dutch Foodpark case)*

Pluralising	Empowering	Politicising	Embedding
Overarching strategy FPA: adaptive and multi-strategy approach toward transformation			
Community engagement in neighbourhood			
Clay workshops (engaged art + participatory research)		Sunflower seed bombs (engaged art, community activism)	Coalition building for tendering process, seeking alignment with entrepreneurs and community

The other ‘full PEPE span’ strategies were:

- The multi-strategy approach of the Participatory Presidium of the Simeto Valley (Italian case). It stood out that beyond networking, the Presidium functioned as an umbrella for the organisation of a large amount and diversity of encounters (workshops, meetings, participatory processes), creating space for discussion and exchange, with a view on reimagining the territory.
- In the Portuguese case/Mértola, the network of actors involved (Terra Sintrópica, the Municipal Council, EDSIME, etc) enacted a meta-strategy of experimenting, demonstrating best practices, and inviting people to come and see/ experience.
- The Mértola Food Network (Portuguese case) also displayed attention to the full PEPE span in their actions toward fostering short food chains and local procurement.
- In Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spanish case), the parents’ associations employed ‘various independent initiatives - bringing plants, fundraising (sales, crowdfunding), schoolyard diagnostics, developing schoolyard designs (including surrounding area)’ in the early stages of schoolyard greening.
- Also in the Spanish case, BC3’s overarching strategy for supporting schoolyard greening (which we labelled as ‘engaged research’) included four associated co-strategies, each linked to a different ‘PEPE’ process.

Associations between actors, activities, target groups and PEPE

The combinations of different categories in actor type, activity type, target group and PEPE principle were many. Visual inspection of the data helps understand the strategic dynamics prevalent in the BIOTraCes cases (7-2). For instance, when government bodies were targeted, this was often through ‘advocacy’ activities, while local communities were most often targeted through ‘encounter’ activities. Research partners very often performed ‘engaged research’, but also a fair amount of supporting ‘encounters’ within local communities.

Broad networks engaged most frequently in ‘co-building’, more than focused networks. This is a surprising result on first sight, because co-building can be seen as ‘more advanced’ than fostering encounters within the community (which was the most frequent activity in the ‘focused networks’ actor type). However, it can be explained through the fact that focused networks ‘have already built’ their internal relations and ways of working, while for broad networks this is a more ongoing concern.

Figure 7-2: Links between five interpretive levels of the strategies: (1) case study, (2) actor, (3) activity, (4) target group and (5) PEPE principles.

NB: A Sankey diagram does not allow individual strategies to be followed across levels; it visualises only the overall volume moving from one category to the next. A further caution concerns how connections should be read. For instance, flows between target group and PEPE do not imply that the target group performs the pluralising (etc.); rather, they show that the actor’s strategy has been coded as producing that effect.

Linking input variables – case studies, actors, activities and target groups – to PEPE ‘output’ revealed subtle but interesting differences (Figure 7-3 a-d below). In general, most BIOTraCes case studies reflect a fair spread across PEPE, but in three cases (Romanian case, Portuguese case and Swedish case) co-strategies leaned more toward the pluralising/empowering side. On the other end, the Italian case (Simeto River Partnership) reflected a slightly more politicising/embedding emphasis (Figure 7-3a).

Effects of actors (Figure 7-3b) were minute. That also applies to target groups, with one exception: when government bodies were targeted, politicising/embedding was more prevalent (Figure 7-3c). Since politicising and embedding focus on power and systems, this is an expected result.

The strongest response can be seen in activity types. While it is not surprising that public engagement and community encounters serve mostly to pursue pluralising and empowering, co-building as an activity displays a clearly shifted (but broad) focus across the PEPE span (Figure 7-3d). We underscore that the composition of our sample strongly shapes the patterns that can be observed, and treating PEPE as ordinal categories should serve exploratory purposes only (not evaluative).

Figure 7-3 (a-d): Relations between the four 'input levels' (from a-d: case study, actor, target group, and activity) and the PEPE principles as indicative 'outputs'. The four PEPE principles are represented as an ordinal sequence (pluralising = 1, empowering = 2, politicising = 3, embedding = 4). Dots indicate the weighted average position, while grey bars illustrate the variation in PEPE associations within each category (one standard deviation around the mean). No statistically significant variation was found.

PURPOSES, CONTEXTS AND OUTCOMES

This section discusses the fields 'context', 'occasion', 'purpose' and 'outcome' of the strategies. These were optional fields, which were only completed when the material provided data.

Contexts and occasions

We defined context as 'institutional and socio-cultural context in 'the territory' and impact sector', and occasion as 'barriers, lock-ins, root causes, power differentials, etc.'. Both fields were included in the strategy table to aid analysis. Since both the institutional contexts and occasions are discussed elsewhere ([Strategies and approaches in \(transformative\) biodiversity initiatives \(T3.2\)](#) and [Opportunities for leverage and amplification \(T3.1\)](#)) we do not discuss them here.

Purposes

Purposes were recorded for 50 out of 71 strategies. In reviewing these purposes, we distilled three main patterns. These patterns are not mutually exclusive – they often go side by side – but may point to different emphases or orientations in the strategies.

1. Reconnecting human–nature relations and socio-ecological practices

Many strategies focused on reconnecting people with nature and ecological processes. This includes aims such as 'creating stronger ties with nature' (Romanian case), 'restoring connection to soil and raising interest in biodiversity' (Dutch Foodpark case), or 'reinforcing [the community's] connection to the river' (Italian case). Others emphasise revaluing and revitalising existing knowledge and practices, for example 'revaluing traditional knowledge to support biodiversity regeneration' (Romanian case) and 'revitalise and innovate practices' (Portuguese case). These purposes often combine social and ecological concerns, for instance by linking cultural identity and local ecological expertise to conservation planning or envisioning 'nature positive living' (Dutch eco-village case).

2. Inclusion and empowerment of marginal or underrepresented group

A second group of strategies seeks to create conditions for participation and visibility of actors who are often absent from dominant processes. Examples include efforts to 'empower herders' (Hungarian case), to 'bring the forest owners together and to elicit their plural values' (Swedish case), and 'create a conversation space that was lacking', such as for parents in the Basque/Spanish case. Some initiatives aim to strengthen the legitimacy of these actors ('keep legitimacy for doing something with nature', Dutch Province case), or to open up engagement to new publics such as youth or female forest owners. In several cases, empowerment is described in practical terms, such as providing 'bits of money' (Dutch Province case) or enabling expression 'in a setting which allows them to express themselves more freely' (Swedish case).

3. Creating spaces for dialogue, trust, and learning

Many strategies emphasise the importance of interaction and relationship-building. They refer to 'participating in networking conversations among farmers to support each other', 'creating spaces for discussion' (both Italian case), or 'building trust' (Lithuanian case). Such spaces are often designed to facilitate mutual learning ('to learn from each other and understand top-down and bottom-up processes', Basque Country/Spanish case) and reflection ('adjusting strategies and goals. Learning by inviting broader network to help reflect', Portuguese case). Rather than focusing on outcomes, these purposes are oriented towards maintaining arenas for exchange and communication.

Overall, the purposes vary in scope and emphasis but collectively point to efforts that combine socio-ecological aims with social organisation, inclusion, and interaction as key elements in strategies for transformative biodiversity governance.

Outcomes

In 41 strategies, outcome data was included. Evaluating outcomes is often a challenge in transformative contexts, especially when strategies are ongoing (see [Cross-case analysis](#)). Several patterns can be identified across the reported outcomes, though results vary in scope, durability, and scale.

1. Partial embedding of biodiversity and learning processes

Many strategies resulted in the creation or strengthening of initiatives that link biodiversity to social and educational settings. Examples include 'green schoolyards integrated into teaching' (Basque country/Spanish case), or workshops that 'caused some integration of biodiversity into cultural identity and well-being' (Romanian case). Procedural learning was reported in the Basque/Spanish case – 'better, more intensive participatory processes' emerged over time – but outcomes remained uneven and contingent ('processes and outcomes different among schools', 'it remains to be seen if this really helps to create stronger human–nature relationships over the long run'). Several cases noted procedural or organisational advances, such as the creation of a geoportal for mapping large-scale photovoltaics (Simeto Valley, Italian case), a landscape cooperative (Dutch eco-village case), or a motion to provide biodiversity advice being adopted in the Swedish forest owner organisation (Swedish case).

2. Shifts in social relations and ownership

Many outcomes relate to the formation of new relations, ownership, or recognition. These include 'sharing of herder secrets', 'increased bridging social capital' (both Hungarian case), and community members 'taking ownership and responsibility for the area or community' (Simeto Valley/Italian case). In a few instances collaboration was said to empower the community and 'give them a clearer understanding of how policies are made'. However, these shifts were often partial or individual rather than structural ('empowerment of herders, mostly at individual level'; (Hungarian case) 'we did not empower them – but we did add value' (research partners on their work in the Dutch Foodpark case and Portuguese case)).

3. Opening up of dialogue and mindsets

Several cases indicate that the activities *opened up discussions* among previously disconnected groups or helped bridge knowledge systems. Examples include the 'dialogue between farmers and non-farmers, or foresters versus conservationists' (Swedish case), and efforts that 'acted as a territorial mediator between local and institutional actors' (Italian case). Such openings were often temporary, linked to specific workshops or events, and depended on facilitation ('what we can say is that the workshop was appreciated... it opened up some discussions which wouldn't have happened otherwise', Swedish case). In the Romanian case, workshops similarly 'caused some integration of biodiversity into cultural identity and well-being', 'bridged local and scientific knowledge', and 'caused more recognition for the value of traditional farming practices'. They contributed to 'people's minds and perceptions about biodiversity and cultural identity' and to 'cross-cultural relations, dialogue between or within local community groups that rarely discuss together, although these exchanges were not expected to continue beyond the participatory activities.

4. Network formation and networked learning

In many cases, the strategies contributed to the establishment or strengthening of networks, both within and across localities. Some outcomes refer to the gradual consolidation of connections, such as '[our work] mostly opened individual herders, but over time, broader (national) networks started emerging' (Hungarian case). In several cases, these processes supported coordination and learning between previously separate actors, as described in one account where 'the event helped social learning and building of the network – fostering connections between the Province and a wider network of other types of actors around 'Natuur Voor Elkaar'' (the 'Nature for Each Other' network spearheaded by the Province of Overijssel/Dutch eco-village case).

4. Uneven inclusion and participation

Outcomes often highlight uneven participation. Marginalised or less resourced groups remained difficult to engage ('illegal migrant labourers hard to include', 'women participation sometimes was low', 'rich schools have lots of money while marginalised schools still scramble'). Some initiatives reached diverse publics ('nice mix, but still white majority'), while others attracted narrow circles ('creative people who liked claying participated, rather than the general public'). Participation was frequently associated with a *sense of ownership and responsibility* (mentioned in the Romanian case, Italian case and Portuguese case).

5. Institutional and procedural openings, but limited structural change

Some outcomes reflect institutional recognition or procedural embedding, such as the motion adopted in the Swedish case, or initiatives becoming embedded in networks (see above) and infrastructures (such as the Simeto Valley geoportal, Italian case). Others remained peripheral or precarious (for instance De Beuk, Dutch eco-village case, or the Hungarian herders), or encountered administrative barriers ('complex bureaucratic hurdles, and scarce and irregular funding', Basque Country, Spanish case). Some examples suggest becoming more formalised while losing critical edge, such as strategies 'shifting

from disruptive to collaborative modes' (in Simeto Valley/Italian case and Basque Country/Spanish case).

The formalisation of ongoing processes occurred as *outcomes* in multiple cases (e.g. Italian case, Dutch Foodpark case, Dutch eco-village case, Portuguese case, Swedish case). In the Italian case, formalisation was also mentioned explicitly as part of the *purposes*. Italian strategies sought to establish instruments and procedures ('fundraising/financing of activities') or to embed participatory methods within governance arrangements, for instance by using workshops or public discussions as recurring mechanisms ('embed the process and the method to start a public discussion on the removal of the [Simeto river] barriers'). This result reflects the Italian case's strategic orientation towards embedding relative to the other BIOTraCes cases that surfaced in the PEPE analysis above (see Figure 7-3d). In the words of one of the involved researchers, their method is to 'build a community of practice network around what we're doing', embedding the processes and tools involved in networks as a means to scale up (or scale out) the intended transformations.

In summary, outcomes commonly involved localised openings, relational shifts, or procedural progress, but structural and sustained changes ('embeddings') were less in number and evidence.

READING BETWEEN THE LINES: BIOTRACES' TENTATIVE META-STRATEGIES

What cross-sections emerge when analysing co-strategies in their totality? The following five patterns can be seen as meta-strategies, woven together differently across the nine BIOTraCes cases.

(1) Many strategies collected for Task 3.3 involve **creating interactive space** for discussion on and appreciation of biodiversity-relevant topics, and **broadening involved communities**. This includes most of the activity types in Encounters and Public Engagement and emphasises the PEPE-principles of *pluralisation* and *empowering*. Outcomes often mentioned are 'opening up' of discussions, mind-sets, and – in our interpretation – new fields of action.

(2) Scaling out practices (advocacy, tools/training). This meta-strategy is also focused on reaching audiences, but more specific and specialised ones. It includes activities in Advocacy, which often serve to *politicise*, as well as diverse 'sub-activities' (dispersed over multiple categories, see Table 7.2) that focus on *embedding* practices in adjacent or more distant networks (e.g. river communities, municipalities). For example, the researchers and Societal Partner in the Simeto Valley/Italian case seek for their strategies to be adopted by local communities of practice. Scaling out practices can either require close and continued interactions (such as in the Simetan case) or more isolated interactions (such as guidebooks for municipalities or provinces) – which arguably have less transformative potential, but may compensate by cleverly leveraging institutional power. In this case, reports on outcomes often reiterated the actors' activities and outputs; actual results obtained in the target actors/fields were less evident.

(3) Building/strengthening the network and consolidating initiatives. Networking as a strategy is evident in all cases. In some cases it takes the hue of community building, and is closely aligned with meta-strategy 1 ('creating spaces') above. But in most cases, explicit and formalised networks were built or strengthened. Sometimes, novel entities

emerged: a landscape cooperative, a geoportal, a tendering coalition. Overall, building networks can help both to *pluralise* and *empower*, as to *embed*. With the right network composition, *politicising* can also be achieved (clearly visible in the Dutch Foodpark case). Reported outcomes often entailed 'growth of the network', mostly with pluralising and empowering effects.

(4) Demonstrating (new/old) practices. Foregrounding the value of innovations that are sometimes 'new', but often also rooted in tradition (knowledge, ways of looking, relationalities), was visible across many cases. The Hungarian case (traditional herding) and Romanian case (high-nature value farming) stand out in this regard, but the value of locally embedded practices and the plurality of values attached to nature are evident from the Netherlands (the Foodpark and its discourse of 'commoning'/Dutch Foodpark case) to the Swedish case, Italian case and Lithuanian case. Demonstrating new/old practices contributed mostly to *pluralising* and often also *empowered* the involved communities.

(5) As a final meta-strategy, **participatory action research** (PAR) can be mentioned (including forms of engaged research which do not fully qualify as PAR). This is an obvious undercurrent across BIOTraCes cases given the project's aims and composition. PAR can contribute across the PEPE spectrum. In BIOTraCes, PAR (engaged research) strategies leaned slightly more toward the *politicising/empowering* side (Figure 7-3c), but as mentioned this result is sensitive to sampling.

7.4 Concluding discussion

The majority of strategies recorded for Task 3.3 involve *creating interactive space* for discussion on and appreciation of biodiversity-relevant topics, as well as *broadening involved communities*. In line with this, *pluralising* and *empowering* emerged as the dominant PEPE principles. Without a doubt, these are important principles for biodiversity innovations. The IPBES Transformative Change Assessment highlights how views of dominion over nature have spread and consolidated globally, constituting a key underlying cause of biodiversity loss. Addressing this requires repluralising idioms, empowering marginalised groups, and reconnecting people with each other and with nature (IPBES 2024). *Pluralising* aims to promote nature-inclusive views and practices, diversifying them and increasing their salience across communities (e.g. Himes & Muraca, 2018; West et al., 2024), while *empowering* seeks to strengthen the communities – and the views and practices within them – that contribute to biodiversity-positive outcomes for society (Petriello et al., 2025). The BIOTraCes cases reflect this primary need for creating discursive and interactive space for biodiversity-positive engagement.

In conjunction with that, the BIOTraCes cases richly feature *network building and strengthening*. These range from non-formalised networks (e.g. herder networks in the Hungarian case) to large, formalised ones (e.g. Mértola Food Network/Portuguese case, the Participatory Presidium of the Simeto River/Italian case, or the 'Dealurile Târnavelor' Local Action Group in the Romanian case).¹³ It varies whether they have a clear, transformative orientation ('focused networks'), or entail 'broad networks' with more general aims, even if all of them focus on local or regional betterment. Indeed, the broad networks are larger, often multi-stakeholder, including NGOs, associations, firms, and

¹³ These networks all existed prior to BIOTraCes involvement.

government bodies. The focused networks are more often composed of peers: aspiring residents of an ecovillage (Dutch eco-village case), women herders, 'seasoned activists' (Dutch Foodpark case), or the people in Terra Sintrópica (Mértola, Portuguese case). A third category we called 'dispersed networks', which is an optimistic way of describing unconnected individuals. These are the herders in the Hungarian case, the forest owners in the Swedish case, or river communities in the Lithuanian case. They, of course, are never wholly unconnected: they are all embedded in their communities in some way, and BIOTraCes has sought to foreground the relational opportunities (or relational capital) present in these communities. In all this, mostly the emphasis was (again) in *pluralising* and *empowering*.

But what about *politicising* and *embedding*? Judging by our data, the biodiversity innovations primarily rely on internal and adjacent networks rather than on wider 'networks of networks'. While some cases also sought to *politicise* on behalf of the community or to support *embedding* of their purposes in wider networks and systems, these principles were pursued less frequently and evidently than *pluralising* and *empowering*. However, politicising and embedding are no less important than pluralising and empowering (Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016; Stirling, 2008; Turnhout et al., 2020), and require the exercise of power through networks to reach sites of power (Avelino, 2017; Avelino et al., 2019; Chambers et al., 2022; Strasser et al., 2022). The relative scarcity of such strategies in BIOTraCes may reflect the difficulty of accessing external networks, which often involve entrenched power structures, such as governments or vested interest parties, or more distant communities and the general public. In some cases, these target groups were explicitly addressed, as in CER's advocacy for herder culture directed both at the public and mid-level governments, or in Foodpark Amsterdam's politicising activities and lobbying for short food chains in Mértola (Portuguese case). Multi-level interactions or dependencies did occur in all cases, but in our mini-narratives they more often figured as *context* (e.g. barriers stemming from government policies) than as clear instances leveraging power through networks. This unevenness – both in terms of PEPE and the networks engaged – can be an impediment to transformative change. Especially since in few cases governments and other vested interest parties fulfil transformative roles. However, we note that many biodiversity innovations are at early stages, producing openings and building capacities, and hopefully laying the groundwork for amplification and systemic impact.

Our analysis shows that strategies are neither atomistic nor linear. They do not exist as self-contained, bounded entities; rather, they are relational and networked, a point recognised in other research (e.g. Pel et al., 2020). For example, in multiple BIOTraCes cases, we observed *nested* strategies: overarching strategies could be distinguished from more focused, applied ones. Overarching strategies typically endure longer, shaping an initiative's long-term orientation. Focused strategies may follow sequentially or unfold in parallel. In constructing mini-narratives from informants' accounts, we also found that means and ends are often closely connected, and difficult to tell apart. Some purposes resembled endpoints ('to improve nature-human relations'), while others appeared as midpoints ('to build the network'), not being very distinct from activities. The softening of artificial means/ends distinctions is a known theme in transformative theory, challenging unhelpful modernist separations (Dwyer & Minnegal, 2010; MacCallum, 2008; Tribe, 1973; Wegener et al., 2025). This integration is a strength: good strategies are integrated wholes. In particular, PEPE principles can be seen as integrating across the strategy. For example, pluralising is *enacted* in activities, *aimed for* in purposes, and potentially *realised* in outcomes. On the other hand, unclarity in the design and logic of a strategy can be a

risk – such as conflating processes with outcomes or activities with results. Theory of Change approaches have been developed precisely with these challenges in mind (Dhillon & Vaca, 2018).

This research has sought to contribute to understanding strategies as *relational processes* – interactive strategies across actor boundaries. Outcomes, then, are also best understood as *relational*: interrelated and interdependent advances concerning pluralisation of views and values, engagement and empowerment of communities, shifts in systems, and biodiversity-related improvements. The BIOTraCes cases showed a wide variety in co-strategies, while the purposes converged toward three broad types (reconnecting people and nature, including marginalised groups, and creating spaces for learning and interacting). The centrality of ‘creating spaces and encounters’ throughout the strategies reveals that transformation toward biodiversity-positive futures is still in early stages. Connecting pluralising and empowering strategies to politicising and embedding ones, exercising the power of networks, will demand more emphasis in both transformative research and praxis.

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8 Innovative thinking for just and effective governance (T3.4)

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8.1 Introduction

This report (D3.2) provides a detailed narrative of the analytical pathway that led to the preparation of the policy brief planned for Task 3.4, connecting gender equity, transformative strategies, and just governance. While the policy brief synthesised the consortium’s shared insights and recommendations for advancing just and effective biodiversity governance, the present document unfolds the methodological, thematic, and conceptual steps that underpinned that synthesis. It retraces the steps through which individual reflections converged into a shared analytical framework, highlighting how gender equity, intersectionality, and transformative strategies became central to reimagining biodiversity governance as both a social and ecological endeavour.

At the heart of this analytical trajectory lies the concern with how governance can become both **effective and just**. In the context of biodiversity regeneration, effectiveness depends on connecting the European, national, and local governance levels in a coherent way, while **integrating diverse knowledge(s), actors, and temporalities into decision-making**. Justice, in turn, demands attention to accountability, but also to inclusiveness and redistribution of voice and responsibility across governance scales. **It is at this point that gender equity and diversity promotion emerge as essential dimensions of transformative governance**, recognising that ecological transitions require fair institutional arrangements, participatory mechanisms, and locally grounded approaches capable of aligning European, national, and territorial priorities within biodiversity and regeneration strategies.

In recent years, research and innovation — including in environmental and biodiversity-related fields — have increasingly sought to align with the principles of the European Research Area (ERA), which emphasises equality, openness, and inclusiveness in scientific excellence (European Commission, 2021, 2025a). The ERA Framework establishes that excellence in science and innovation depends on equality, diversity, and openness, calling for systems capable of identifying and addressing structural asymmetries in research and policymaking. Intersectionality and gender equality have thus become priorities, following the European Union’s commitments under the ERA Policy Agenda and the Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025. As a result of the growing dialogue between the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the ERA Research & Innovation Framework, policymakers are now required to pay closer attention to intersectionality — understood here as “the complex, irreducible, varied, and variable effects which ensue when multiple axes of differentiation – economic, political, cultural, psychic, subjective, and experiential – intersect in historically specific contexts” (Brah & Phoenix, 2004, p. 76). In practice, this means recognising how overlapping structures of power and inequality — including gender, class, and ethnicity — shape people’s differentiated experiences of biodiversity loss and participation in governance. BIOTraCes — *Biodiversity and Transformative Change for Plural and Nature-Positive Societies* — through Task 3.4, explored what effective and just biodiversity governance might entail when viewed through lenses of gender equity and the participation of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups in governance processes.

Building on this experience, the challenge that emerges today is how to translate the principles of justice, inclusiveness, and multi-level coordination into coherent action — capable of linking local and regional transformation strategies with national reforms in high-impact sectors, and with transnational frameworks for biodiversity and climate resilience. **Achieving just and effective governance therefore requires policies that are simultaneously grounded and interconnected: rooted in local realities, responsive to social inequalities, and aligned with broader European and global commitments to nature-positive and inclusive transformation.**

CONTEXT OF ANALYSIS

Within the European Union, the European Research Area (ERA) has become a cornerstone for aligning research and innovation with the principles of equity, openness, and sustainability. The ERA Policy Agenda (2022–2027) explicitly integrates gender equality and intersectionality as cross-cutting objectives in research and innovation, reinforcing the idea that scientific excellence requires inclusiveness and diversity. Together with the Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025, it calls for R&I systems to identify and address interlocking asymmetries - those combining gender, race, disability, and socioeconomic status - that affect both knowledge production and its translation into policy.

Over the past decade, the ERA has shifted from a focus on competitiveness and mobility in science toward a more transformative agenda, linking research to societal challenges such as gender equity, climate change, and biodiversity regeneration (European Commission, 2025b; Council of the European Union, 2025).

The European Research Area (ERA) Framework and the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025 have made important advances in integrating gender equality and intersectionality into research and innovation. By emphasising the need to address overlapping asymmetries—of gender, race, class, age, and ability—the ERA agenda has begun to reorient how research frameworks consider biodiversity loss as both a social and ecological phenomenon. This alignment between the ERA and the EU Biodiversity Strategy represents a promising step toward policy coherence, yet its implementation remains uneven. Research projects and governance frameworks still rarely intersect in practice, and the lessons emerging from gender-based experiences of biodiversity loss remain underutilised in policy design.

By framing inclusiveness as a precondition for excellence, the ERA has positioned gender equality and intersectionality as key indicators of institutional progress. However, despite these commitments, their translation into biodiversity governance and environmental research remains limited (EIGE, 2023).

SOCIAL DIMENSIONS OF BIODIVERSITY DECLINE

European biodiversity governance remains predominantly shaped by technical perspectives, with limited attention to its social dimensions. Questions of justice, inclusion, and representation remain secondary, and governance structures still privilege established actors — large landowners, industrial lobbies, or state agencies — over smallholders, women, and minority groups. When participation is encouraged, it often remains symbolic rather than transformative. This imbalance reveals a structural weakness: by treating

social equity as peripheral, biodiversity policies risk reproducing the very inequalities that obstruct their effectiveness.

Gender remains one of the most persistent blind spots. Although the European Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the Nature Restoration Law have introduced more comprehensive environmental targets, they remain largely gender-neutral in both design and evaluation. Women's differentiated roles, vulnerabilities, and contributions in managing natural resources seldom appear in these frameworks, despite growing evidence of their significance for adaptation, mitigation, and ecological care. The absence of gender perspectives thus weakens not only the social legitimacy but also the ecological effectiveness of governance arrangements.

GENDER-DIFFERENTIATED IMPACTS OF BIODIVERSITY DECLINE

Women, especially those in rural and low-income communities, are among the most vulnerable to climate change and biodiversity loss: they depend heavily on local ecosystems for food, water, and fuel, yet often lack secure land rights, access to finance, or a voice in governance. As a result, biodiversity loss not only undermines ecological resilience but also exacerbates gender inequalities, making women disproportionately affected by its consequences.

In agriculture, women face a double vulnerability: they are less likely to own land or control productive resources, and more likely to depend on small-scale, biodiversity-rich farming systems that are directly threatened by intensification and land degradation. Women manage 29% of EU farms, but with wide disparities - close to 50% in Latvia and Lithuania, and less than 10% in Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands (Eurostat, 2016). In organic farming, the share is even lower (26.9%), despite evidence that women-led farms adopt more environmental and climate measures. When biodiversity declines, these women farmers are among the first to experience economic insecurity and food system fragility.

In forestry, women comprise only 20% of the workforce in Europe (UNECE/FAO, 2023). Here, vulnerability arises not only from exclusion in decision-making, but also from gendered labour patterns: women are more concentrated in informal or seasonal forestry work, with lower income security and fewer protections. When biodiversity-rich forests are degraded, women's opportunities to generate livelihoods and sustain family wellbeing shrink disproportionately.

Gender inequality also shapes vulnerability in the built environment. Studies increasingly indicate that gender-diverse leadership on corporate boards correlates with stronger adoption of sustainable building practices (Denis, 2022), while women's absence in decision-making often translates into urban design that neglects their safety, mobility, and ecological needs (UN-Habitat, 2012; Kneeshaw & Norman, 2019). Pioneering urban planning in Vienna has shown how gender-sensitive design (safe lighting, childcare access, green space) can reduce vulnerability by ensuring that women and girls benefit equally from healthy environments. Ecovillages such as Findhorn highlight how women's leadership in regenerative practices not only contributes to ecological sustainability but also creates more socially resilient communities.

Exclusion from governance deepens women's vulnerability. Globally—and in Europe—women are underrepresented in ministries, councils, and community governance bodies responsible for land and water management (UNEP, IUCN, 2018). Yet they are often the

primary users of these resources: responsible for water collection, household food production, and community care. When rivers are polluted, forests cleared, or land privatised, women are often left with fewer alternatives to secure livelihoods and household wellbeing, amplifying their exposure to biodiversity loss. These disparities illustrate how structural inequalities in access to land, finance, and institutional recognition persist across Europe, constraining both women’s agency and the transformative potential of biodiversity governance.

Intersectional evidence further shows that rural, migrant, indigenous, and minority women often face **compounded disadvantages**, making it essential to design adaptation and mitigation strategies that account for multiple, overlapping inequalities.

It is also important to acknowledge the role of **gender-diverse and dissident identities** - including trans women and men, non-binary and gender non-conforming people - in biodiversity governance. Their contributions, though less studied, expand the scope of inclusive strategies and highlight the need for policies attentive to the full diversity of gender identities (European Institute for Gender Equality – EIGE, 2022).

Box 8-1: Summary of key evidence: women as vulnerable groups in biodiversity loss

- **Dependence on ecosystems:** Women rely more heavily on biodiversity for subsistence (food, water, fuel) but have less secure land rights and access to resources.
- **Agriculture:** Women manage 29% of EU farms but face systemic barriers; biodiversity decline directly threatens their livelihoods.
- **Forestry:** Women are only 20% of the workforce and often in more precarious, informal roles, heightening vulnerability when forests are degraded.
- **Urban & Building:** Lack of gender-sensitive planning increases women’s vulnerability in cities; inclusive design reduces risks and enhances resilience.
- **Education:** Girls are both more affected by ecological harm and more active in environmental education; excluding them weakens biodiversity governance.
- **Governance gaps:** Women’s underrepresentation in land and water governance bodies means their vulnerabilities are rarely addressed in policy responses.

INCLUSIVE KNOWLEDGE AND DATA FOR BIODIVERSITY GOVERNANCE

Achieving just and effective biodiversity governance requires rethinking how knowledge is produced, validated, and mobilised. Conventional monitoring and policy frameworks have long privileged biophysical indicators - species counts, land cover, carbon fluxes - while overlooking the social and cultural dimensions that shape people’s relationships with biodiversity. This bias obscures how gender, class, and ethnicity condition both exposure to biodiversity loss and capacity for adaptation.

The *Framework for Inclusive Gender Analysis in Research and Innovation Content* (European Commission, 2025b) calls for data systems capable of capturing lived

experiences and local perspectives. Moving beyond gender-disaggregated statistics, it advocates for intersectional data that reflect how multiple inequalities intersect in shaping ecological vulnerability and agency. This approach requires combining quantitative and qualitative insights, integrating community-generated data, and valuing everyday practices of care, stewardship, and environmental maintenance as legitimate sources of ecological knowledge.

In biodiversity governance, such inclusive data practices can bridge the persistent gap between scientific and experiential knowledge. When local perspectives - often held by women, small producers, and **marginalised groups - are included in monitoring and decision-making, governance becomes more accountable and context-sensitive.** Recognising these actors as *knowledge holders* rather than passive stakeholders enhances legitimacy and strengthens the long-term sustainability of regeneration efforts.

This implies moving from institutional compliance with equality frameworks toward a transformative understanding of inclusion. Women and other underrepresented groups are not merely beneficiaries or vulnerable populations; they are active agents whose situated knowledges contribute to adaptive, resilient, and socially grounded biodiversity governance. Embedding such epistemic diversity into governance systems is therefore both an ethical and a strategic imperative for ecological transition in Europe.

Box 8-2: Summary of key evidence: women in adaptation and mitigation

- Women make **critical contributions** to biodiversity conservation, sustainable agriculture, and natural resource management, yet their efforts remain undervalued (Sasvari et al., 2010).
- In agriculture, women are **31.6% of farm operators**, but management ranges from ~45% in Latvia/Lithuania to <10% in Germany, Denmark, Netherlands (Eurostat, 2020).
- In forestry, women account for just **20% of the workforce** in Europe (UNECE/FAO).
- **Systemic barriers** - land access, finance and training constraints, and cultural stereotypes - limit women's visibility and influence.
- **Inclusive gender analysis** enhances governance, resilience, and innovation, but must also account for intersectional disadvantages faced by rural, migrant, and minority women (EC, 2025).

8.2 Method of analysis

The analytical process for this chapter combined **inductive and deductive reasoning** to capture both the emergent dynamics in the case studies and the predefined theoretical concerns of WP3. While the *policy brief* (Deliverable 3.4) synthesised the cross-cutting findings and policy implications of this work, the present document expands on the analytical pathway that led to those conclusions — namely, how evidence from the

consortium's internal reflections was interpreted, coded, and translated into collective insights about just and effective biodiversity governance.

The analysis was based on a **hybrid thematic approach** (Swain, 2018; Xu & Zammit, 2020), simultaneously grounded in the data provided by research partners and informed by theoretical categories derived from the literature and from the guiding questions used in the WP3 reflective interviews (see Chapter 4). These interviews were designed not to assess fieldwork outcomes, but rather to understand how each research team perceived and articulated the governance challenges, leverage points, and transformative strategies emerging from their ongoing work. In that sense, the process was both reflective and meta-analytical: it invited partners to interpret their experiences and to identify the broader lessons arising from their cases.

To ensure analytical coherence across the nine case studies, **each partner was treated as a single unit of analysis**, regardless of the length or level of detail of their response. Codes were therefore counted once per partner if present, preventing longer or more elaborate responses from disproportionately influencing the overall thematic weight. This approach ensured an equitable comparison across contexts and reflected the diversity of perspectives rather than the verbosity of individual contributions.

The **coding process** combined inductive and deductive procedures. Codes were primarily generated inductively from the participants' own language and emphasis, allowing recurrent ideas, expressions, and concerns to emerge directly from the material. At the same time, a deductive lens was used to link the data to key conceptual categories identified earlier in the project — such as the quality and limits of governance, the presence of power asymmetries, the representativeness of vulnerable and marginalised groups, and the degree of participation within biodiversity-related decision-making processes.

Once coded, the material underwent **thematic construction**: codes were merged, grouped, and hierarchised into broader themes and subthemes that revealed the structural patterns underlying the different cases. Relationships among themes were then visualised to identify clusters of meaning around governance gaps, participation barriers, exclusions, and emerging practices. The resulting **visual map** served as both an analytical and communicative tool, supporting the synthesis of findings and indirectly informing the policy brief. It provided a structured overview of how different issues interconnected — for instance, how gender blindness intersected with institutional rigidity, or how plural knowledge systems contributed to transformative governance. **Emerging good practices were also mapped when they suggested a possible trend or innovation across contexts.**

Throughout this process, **validation and reflexivity** were key principles. The analysis adhered strictly to the participants' reflections to preserve content fidelity, while also acknowledging the situated nature of each partner's perspective. Rather than imposing external interpretations, the aim was to recognise the contextual specificities of each case and to identify common dynamics that could be meaningfully compared across Europe.

The resulting analysis also drew upon **collective workshops and cross-case exchanges** organised within WP3, which allowed teams to reflect jointly on the patterns emerging from their discussions and to identify convergences or tensions between different sectors and geographical contexts. These workshops provided essential feedback loops, refining the thematic synthesis and helping to build shared understanding among partners.

In sum, this methodological pathway — from reflective interviews to coding, thematic mapping, and collective validation — enabled the task to move beyond descriptive comparison towards an integrated interpretation of how governance practices, power relations, and inclusivity shape the prospects for transformative change in biodiversity governance.

INTERVIEWS

The interviews conducted during this task were conceived as reflective dialogues within the consortium, engaging the research partners responsible for the BIOTraCes case studies. Rather than external assessments, these exchanges aimed to capture the shared interpretations, challenges, and transformative strategies emerging from each case. The intention was to consolidate collective learning across the project, while maintaining an analytical focus on governance, inclusivity, and the conditions that enable or constrain transformative change.

Each research team was invited to respond to a set of guiding questions related to the policy brief, which focused on identifying how transformative strategies could promote just biodiversity governance. These questions were designed to stimulate critical reflection on key dimensions such as the quality and limits of governance arrangements, the visibility and participation of marginalised groups, and the power asymmetries influencing decision-making processes. By connecting the interviews to the aims of the policy brief, the process helped translate the consortium's collective experience into shared analytical insights — bridging individual case knowledge with the broader synthesis required for policy reflection.

This approach generated a corpus of responses that, while rooted in specific local experiences, provided a comparative and self-reflexive lens through which to identify transversal patterns across the cases, laying the analytical groundwork for both the policy brief and the present report. These reflections were guided by a set of shared questions designed to prompt critical engagement with key dimensions of just biodiversity governance — from the quality of governance and inclusiveness of decision-making to the visibility of marginalised groups and the transformative potential of emerging practices.

The process was conducted by the WP3 task leaders and unfolded in three stages: the first round of interviews (M27), a *World Café* during the consortium meeting in Hungary (M30), and a second round of interviews between M31 and M34. Within this process, Task 3.4 contributed with a specific focus on what could be understood as **just and effective governance** in biodiversity regeneration. The analysis aimed to identify (1) fine-tuned decision-making processes in transformative change for biodiversity; (2) the attention given to environmental inequalities and the constraints experienced by specific social groups; (3) the level of citizen participation; and (4) the extent to which biodiversity governance adopted gender-sensitive approaches — including practices and policies supporting women's empowerment and recognising their key contributions to adaptation and mitigation.

Its first round of questions explored transparency and accountability mechanisms, the ways in which governance arrangements addressed power imbalances, and how underrepresented and vulnerable groups were considered in decision-making. During the *World Café* held at the consortium meeting in Hungary, questions focused more explicitly on gender, asking how women were involved in co-governance activities and how their specific contributions to biodiversity regeneration were recognised. The final round

revisited the attention given to diverse stakeholders and competing needs in each case study, deepening the analysis of vulnerability and inclusiveness in governance practices.

Together, these reflections oriented the analytical process and provided the empirical and conceptual foundation for the collective synthesis that followed — including both the analytical narrative presented here and the shared understanding that informed the policy brief.

VISUAL MAP AND THEMATIC ANALYSIS

The interviews and exchanges carried out under Task 3.4 unfolded in three main stages: the first round of interviews (M27), the *World Café* held during the consortium meeting in Hungary (M30), and a final round of exchanges between M31 and M34. Each of these stages contributed to refining the analytical understanding of just and effective governance in biodiversity regeneration. The first round provided the basis for the **visual map** (Figure 8-1), while the subsequent discussions helped to expand and deepen its analytical scope — especially in relation to gender visibility, intersectional vulnerabilities, and the role of community agency in biodiversity governance.

The visual map was produced by the CES team as part of Task 3.4 and later integrated into the analytical process for D3.2. It derives from the thematic analysis of the first round of interviews (M27), which addressed four key dimensions of what could be understood as *just and effective governance* in transformative change for biodiversity: (1) fine-tuned decision-making processes; (2) attention to environmental inequalities and the constraints experienced by specific social groups; (3) the level of citizen participation; and (4) gender-sensitive approaches in governance practices and policies.

Developed through the coding and clustering of responses to these four **dimensions**, the visual map functions both as an analytical and a communicative tool. Analytically, it synthesises the most recurrent issues emerging from the first round of responses; communicatively, it provides a shared representation of how governance dynamics, inclusion, and power relations intersect **across the cases**.

The map organises these relations into six thematic clusters:

1. **Gender Invisibility in Biodiversity Governance**, highlighting the invisibility of women's roles, the under-recognition of gendered labour, and the limited participation of women and minorities in biodiversity governance.
2. **Political and cultural barriers for inclusion**, revealing inefficiencies, lack of transparency, and self-preserving institutional routines.
3. **Exclusion and underrepresentation**, showing structural asymmetries, resource concentration, and the marginalisation of small farmers, vulnerable groups, and minorities.
4. **Knowledge, Language, and Imaginaries**, exposing the neglect of traditional ecological knowledge and the dominance of narrow framings of nature.
5. **Participatory Research Tools and Community Engagement Strategies**, documenting participatory experiments, collaborative learning, and local mobilisation, but also limits and fatigue.

6. **Environmental and spatial injustice**, illustrating how governance might privilege aesthetic or managerial approaches over ecological regeneration and multispecies coexistence. It also points to more-than-human marginalisation.

Building on the synthesis produced during the *World Café* held at the consortium meeting in Hungary (M30), an **indirect thematic analysis** was conducted to identify the most salient patterns and concerns raised by participants in response to Task 3.4's guiding questions. While the discussion was not structured as a formal interview, it generated a rich collective reflection on gender and governance across cases. The analysis focused on recurring meanings and shared observations emerging from the synthesis prepared after the session, revealing three interconnected themes that illustrate how gender dynamics intersect with governance structures and biodiversity practices:

1. **Gendered Governance Leadership** — governance practices and leadership structures are deeply marked by gender, with women's participation often restricted to informal, social, or cultural roles, while men dominate institutional and technical domains.
2. **Under-recognised Gendered Knowledge** — women's ecological knowledge and practical contributions to biodiversity regeneration remain largely invisible or undervalued, despite their centrality to local environmental care and community management.
3. **Institutional and Conceptual Neglect of Gender in Biodiversity Governance** — both local governance bodies and policy frameworks tend to overlook or detach gender considerations from biodiversity governance, treating gender equity as an external or secondary issue rather than a structural component of just and effective governance.

Figure 8-1: Visual map — Main thematic clusters

WORKSHOPS AND CROSS-CASE ANALYSIS

Beyond the interviews and thematic analyses, a series of workshops and collective discussions related to **intersectionality and recommendations for regenerative governance** — key aspects for Task 3.4 — were organised. These encounters functioned as spaces of learning and reflexivity, allowing participants to collectively examine how issues of gender, vulnerability, and environmental justice intersect within governance practices. Together, they provided the basis for the cross-case reflection that informed both the *Policy Brief* (Deliverable 3.4) and the present analytical report.

Three key workshops marked this process:

First Workshop on Intersectionality and Governance (M18). Held during the consortium meeting in Mértola (May 2023), this workshop introduced intersectionality as an analytical and experiential framework. Participants engaged in the *Privilege Exercise*¹⁴, followed by group reflections and a collective discussion structured around three guiding questions:

- Which nature-based solutions could better reflect the heterogeneity of ordinary people within a community?
- How do spatial and representational justice apply to the case studies?
- How have disadvantaged situations experienced by some social groups worsened the environmental burdens they face daily (e.g., thermal comfort, floods, drought)?

This first encounter grounded intersectionality in lived experience and situated knowledge, linking environmental governance to everyday inequalities.

Workshop ‘Building Intersectionality into Governance for Transformative Change’ (M22). This session explored the operational meaning of intersectionality within governance contexts. Its dual objective was to consolidate a shared conceptual basis and to initiate collective thinking around a set of indicators on *Effective and Just Governance* — to be developed by CES as part of its expected outputs related to Task 3.4.

Discussions revolved around the social and governance relevance of intersectionality, its links to environmental challenges, and the importance of adopting gender-sensitive approaches within biodiversity governance. Participants reflected on how intersectional perspectives could contribute to more equitable decision-making and on the potential of such lenses to strengthen the indicators of fair and inclusive governance.

After presenting different models of indicators, the session concluded with a collective reflection on the question: *What should be the key points of attention when creating indicators that take intersectional issues into account within the scope of the BIOTraCes project?*

¹⁴ The *Privilege Walk* exercise was developed by feminist and anti-racist scholar **Peggy McIntosh** to raise awareness of how social hierarchies translate into material inequalities. Initially designed to discuss white privilege, it has been adapted by NGOs, universities, and community organisations to address multiple forms of social asymmetry. Participants stand side by side while a facilitator reads a series of statements; they step forward or backward depending on whether each statement applies to them, making visible the cumulative effects of privilege and exclusion. In the context of transformative learning processes, such as those promoted within *BioTraCes*, the exercise fosters reflection on positionality, empathy, and the structural dimensions of inequality.

Workshop on the Policy Brief (M31). This final workshop focused explicitly on transforming the insights derived from the case studies into shared recommendations for policymakers. Its purpose was to work collectively on the core dimensions identified through the case analyses — assessing both the strengths and the limitations of the experiences and translating them into policy-oriented reflections. The session was therefore directly linked to the production of the *Policy Brief* (Deliverable 3.4), aiming to ensure that it reflected a genuinely collective discussion within the consortium.

The workshop was structured according to the main sections of the policy brief. Participants discussed, based on their case studies, the key messages emerging from their research, the most relevant findings regarding inclusive and gender-sensitive governance, and the recommendations considered most pertinent to advance fair and regenerative governance practices.

Together, these workshops fostered a process of collective reasoning that transcended individual case studies, contributing to a more coherent and inclusive understanding of just governance within BIOTraCes. They also served to strengthen the integration between conceptual reflection, empirical learning, and the co-production of knowledge across the consortium.

The reflections and exchanges developed throughout these workshops formed the conceptual and collective groundwork for the subsequent synthesis. The following section summarises the main cross-cutting findings that emerged from this iterative process — integrating insights from the thematic analyses, the *World Café*, and the workshops — to outline the key lessons on inclusive, gender-sensitive, and transformative governance across the BIOTraCes case studies.

8.3 Findings

JUSTICE AND INCLUSION IN BIODIVERSITY GOVERNANCE

The analysis conducted within Task 3.4 reveals a complex and uneven landscape of transformative governance across the BIOTraCes case studies. Despite local experimentation and growing awareness of the need for inclusive and regenerative approaches, several persistent barriers continue to limit the translation of policy commitments into concrete practices. **Decision-making processes in biodiversity governance remain largely dominated by established actors**, with marginalised and vulnerable groups—particularly minority women, migrants, Roma, and racialised communities—rarely holding meaningful influence. Where inclusion mechanisms exist, participation often assumes a symbolic character, leaving structural hierarchies intact. Many local actors express scepticism toward multi-stakeholder partnerships, citing power asymmetries and the absence of trust between research institutions, public authorities, and civil society. These concerns highlight the enduring distance between participatory rhetoric and genuine co-governance.

Although biodiversity-oriented policies are increasingly mainstreamed at European and national levels, their practical implementation often falls short. Across contexts, the **procedural and regulatory frameworks guiding biodiversity governance remain fragmented and rigid**, largely because they must operate within sectoral regulations — for instance, in agriculture, forestry, or infrastructure planning — that follow distinct logics and priorities. In practice, environmental impact assessment procedures and agricultural

subsidy schemes still tend to prioritise compliance and productivity over ecosystem restoration, while rigid land-use classifications¹⁵ and complex licensing processes make it difficult to coordinate interventions across sectors and territories. These institutional misalignments constrain cooperation among local actors and delay the adoption of regenerative approaches.

This situation leads to **contradictions between ambitious policy discourse and on-the-ground operational realities**. Territorial initiatives aligned with EU biodiversity goals frequently encounter conflicting regulations or bureaucratic rigidity that erodes continuity and confidence. In several cases, these institutional inconsistencies have bred fatigue and disillusionment among local actors, revealing the importance of coherent and trust-based approaches to environmental governance — particularly between public authorities, local administrations, and community-led organisations engaged in regenerative and conservation practices. Building stable channels of dialogue and mutual accountability across these levels is essential to ensure that biodiversity goals translate into workable, context-sensitive actions.

Bureaucratic obstacles and **governance routines further limit the capacity for transformation**. In many contexts, public administrations tend to privilege control and compliance over experimentation and learning, creating institutional environments resistant to collaborative innovation. The persistence of vertical structures reinforces opacity and hinders the emergence of adaptive solutions. However, this is not a universal pattern. Certain territories have begun to explore more adaptive and collaborative governance models that integrate public institutions with civil society networks, **illustrating how experimentation can coexist with accountability**. These experiences demonstrate that transformation is possible when local administrations embrace flexibility and shared responsibility. Yet, across most cases, governance cultures still reproduce opacity and hierarchy, reinforcing institutional inertia and hindering the emergence of participatory and regenerative approaches. Transformative change therefore requires not only technical or financial adjustments but also a shift in administrative ethos: from procedural rigidity to trust-based collaboration. **Transformative change therefore demands not only financial or technical reform, but also a shift in governance culture**—one that redistributes authority and legitimises the agency of community-led initiatives.

A strong tension also persists between ecological and social imperatives. While most case studies align with environmental objectives, tensions arise when ecological transitions challenge existing livelihoods or local economic priorities. **Social dimensions—particularly those concerning gender and minority inclusion—are often treated as external impositions** rather than as integral components of biodiversity governance. This perception reflects a broader unease with the integration of justice-oriented approaches into environmental agendas. Addressing this tension requires more than adapting the terminology; it entails working through the cultural and political sensitivities that shape local acceptance and resistance to such agendas.

¹⁵ In most European countries, land-use classifications and territorial planning instruments define rigid categories of use — agricultural, forestry, urban, or conservation — each with specific legal restrictions. These boundaries often reflect sectoral logics rather than ecosystemic relations, limiting integrated, landscape-scale interventions that combine agricultural, social, and ecological objectives. This structural rigidity can be observed across the EU, including in countries such as Portugal, France, Italy, and Spain.

The findings also point to a **recurring disconnection between biodiversity goals and social justice concerns**. Environmental efforts are frequently pursued without addressing the unequal vulnerability and distribution of power that underpins ecological degradation. Consequently, regeneration processes risk reinforcing exclusion rather than dismantling it. Gender and intersectional dimensions of environmental change remain especially underexplored. **Women’s differentiated exposure to climate risks, their unequal access to resources, and their critical contributions to adaptation and mitigation continue to receive limited recognition in governance frameworks**. The absence of gender-sensitive data and indicators perpetuates this invisibility, obstructing the assessment of whether regeneration strategies align with broader equity and justice goals.

Despite mounting evidence of women’s pivotal role in sustaining biodiversity—through seed preservation, food production, and care work—their contributions remain undervalued and peripheral to formal governance. Across contexts, **women’s ecological knowledge and labour are rarely acknowledged as integral to biodiversity regeneration**. This systematic under-recognition not only weakens inclusiveness but also undermines the transformative potential of governance innovations. Similarly, community-based initiatives that embed biodiversity within everyday life have proven essential for regeneration, yet they remain fragile and structurally unsupported. Their continuity often depends on short-term funding and project-based logic, with limited integration into formal policy systems. The sustainability of these initiatives therefore hinges on institutional mechanisms capable of providing stable recognition and resources.

Spatial justice and non-human agency also remain largely neglected dimensions of biodiversity governance. Territorial inequalities and unequal access to land continue to shape who benefits from and who bears the costs of regeneration. **The social dimension of how space and landscapes are shaped, accessed, and redistributed receives little attention within restoration approaches**. Many local strategies still privilege human-centred and resource-based understandings of nature, overlooking the agency of non-human entities — that is, the active role of living systems such as soil organisms, pollinators, water flows, and vegetation in shaping ecological dynamics and sustaining livelihoods. Too often, Nature-based Solutions and other landscape and biodiversity restoration strategies maintain a perspective focused on resources and ecosystem services, ignoring the capacity of these non-human actors — such as rivers, algae, bacteria, fungi, and insects — to respond, adapt, and reshape ecological relations. Recognising more-than-human interdependence is essential for broadening the ethical scope of governance and aligning biodiversity regeneration with the principles of environmental and social justice.

Finally, **traditional and tacit knowledge - often held by small producers, women, and local communities - remains undervalued in comparison to formal expertise**. Yet these forms of situated knowledge play a crucial role in both ecological awareness and social cohesion. Their recognition within governance processes represents not only an act of equity but also a key opportunity for innovation and resilience.

EMERGING INNOVATIONS AND PROMISING PRACTICES

Alongside these structural challenges, the analysis also reveals tangible innovations and emerging practices that point towards the possibility of transformative change for biodiversity. Across several cases, **transformative change is being advanced through**

pluralising, embedding, politicising, and empowering practices - the principles that underpin the BIOTraCes approach. These efforts include the broadening of actor participation, the rooting of governance in situated realities, the exposure of entrenched power asymmetries, and the strengthening of communities' collective agency. Together, these dynamics demonstrate how transformation emerges from experimentation, negotiation, and the pursuit of more inclusive and context-sensitive forms of governance.

In multiple territories, creative and inclusive engagement approaches have expanded the reach of biodiversity initiatives, bringing in groups traditionally excluded from formal decision-making. **Artistic, performative, and experiential practices have proven effective in overcoming social and cultural barriers**, opening spaces for alternative forms of knowledge and expression. **By strengthening people's agency and voice in defining local priorities, these participatory experiments also deepen inclusion, as they expand the conditions for negotiation, collaboration, and collective ownership within communities.** These processes not only enhance the legitimacy of governance but also contribute to building trust and a shared sense of purpose. These inclusive and agency-enhancing initiatives are gradually informing institutional practices, paving the way for emerging forms of co-governance.

Co-governance models have begun to take shape through collaborations between public institutions, researchers, and civil society actors. Although still fragile, these initiatives mark a gradual institutional shift towards shared accountability and collective problem-solving. They challenge the persistence of hierarchical routines and signal a willingness to experiment with more horizontal and adaptive arrangements.

The growing recognition of multiple knowledge systems further supports this shift. Across cases, the limits of technical expertise are increasingly acknowledged, and experiential, **practice-based knowledge(s) have been valued as crucial components of transformation.** Co-learning processes have become fertile ground for innovation, enabling mutual adaptation between scientific, policy, and community perspectives. This pluralisation of knowledge is reconfiguring how authority circulates within governance spaces and strengthening the legitimacy of community-based expertise. See [*Strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation, dialogue \(T3.3\)*](#).

Emerging trans-local collaborations also signal an important development. **Partnerships and networks that connect communities facing similar challenges have fostered solidarity-based learning and cross-territorial adaptation of good practices.** These connections nurture a sense of shared responsibility and care that transcends local boundaries, linking the regeneration of specific territories to a broader European horizon of transformation.

Finally, the analysis underscores the social dimension of biodiversity restoration. Initiatives that promote collective learning, trust-building, and social cohesion help to reweave the relational fabric necessary for durable change. Such efforts foster a shared sense of belonging and collective purpose, gradually shifting local imaginaries towards cooperation, care, and reciprocity. **Educational and intergenerational programmes have been particularly effective in cultivating ecological literacy and embedding biodiversity values within everyday life.** By linking learning with practice and by framing regeneration as both a social and ecological project, these initiatives are helping to shift local imaginaries toward cooperation, reciprocity, and care — essential preconditions for transformative governance.

8.4 Discussion

POLICY COHERENCE FOR JUST BIODIVERSITY GOVERNANCE

At national and European levels, biodiversity governance must evolve from compliance-driven systems to frameworks that actively enable biodiversity restoration and social regeneration, while ensuring equity and accountability. Embedding regenerative criteria - such as measurable improvements in soil health, biodiversity indicators, circular use of resources, and social inclusion outcomes - into funding mechanisms for high-impact sectors can catalyse this shift. Financial incentives that reward soil improvement, wildlife management, and nature-based solutions would encourage more sustainable and inclusive production models, while contributing to fairer income distribution and reduced precarity among rural actors. Introducing 'transition insurance' policies — designed to de-risk experimentation and support regenerative entrepreneurship — could further help local actors implement transformative strategies without bearing disproportionate financial risk. Such tools would strengthen social resilience and create long-term conditions for innovation and learning, supporting companies, cooperatives, and communities engaged in regenerative practices.

Reducing social and territorial inequalities also requires rethinking how funding reaches those on the ground. Calls that specifically support young people and women to remain active in their territories through regenerative work can strengthen both biodiversity outcomes and rural cohesion. Equally, simplifying EU and national funding procedures is essential for allowing small-scale and community-led initiatives to access and manage resources. In addition, introducing micro-grant schemes, participatory budgeting processes, and incentives for short-supply-chain and community-based procurement schemes could help rebalance current funding asymmetries. The current concentration of funds in large-scale actors limits the transformative potential of grassroots experimentation and undermines inclusiveness in the governance of transition processes.

Moreover, such mechanisms can also integrate **social criteria** aimed at improving living and working conditions for marginalised and vulnerable groups — including migrants, Roma people, racialised and low-income communities, as well as elderly people, youth, and women — who are often confined to the most precarious and underpaid segments of agri-food labour, while facing disproportionate exposure to environmental degradation. In the EU, this approach is consistent with **Socially Responsible Public Procurement (SRPP)**, as defined in *Directive 2014/24/EU*, which allows the inclusion of clauses on labour inclusion, gender equality, decent working conditions, and the integration of vulnerable groups into public procurement frameworks.

Several European countries have already introduced mechanisms that, while respecting EU competition rules, indirectly prioritise local and community-based provisioning. National and regional authorities can include criteria such as short supply chains, seasonal and organic production, low carbon footprint in transport, or socially responsible procurement to favour local actors without explicitly restricting geographical scope. In France, for instance, the *Loi Egalim* requires that at least 50% of food served in public catering be sustainable and locally sourced. In Italy, *biodistretti* have pioneered territorial contracts that integrate local procurement and inclusion goals. Similar approaches in Austria and Denmark prioritise short food chains and regional sourcing within public meal programmes, demonstrating that procurement can be both legally compliant and territorially regenerative.

A more coherent coordination between the European Green Deal, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and the Recovery and Resilience Facility is also critical. Despite shared goals, these instruments often operate in isolation, generating overlaps or contradictions in implementation. Enhancing their operational alignment would ensure that biodiversity regeneration and social justice objectives are mutually reinforcing across scales.

Integrating social justice into the CAP entails recognising and addressing the unequal distribution of resources, opportunities, and decision-making power within the agricultural sector. This can be achieved by linking CAP funding mechanisms and eco-schemes to clear social inclusion criteria — for instance, by supporting **small and medium-sized farms, women farmers, migrant and seasonal workers, and young people striving for more equitable conditions in agriculture**. It also implies strengthening conditionalities that promote **fair working conditions, gender equality, and access to land, finance, and training** for underrepresented groups. By doing so, the CAP can move beyond purely production-oriented objectives and act as a driver of **territorial cohesion, equitable rural development, and inclusive biodiversity regeneration**.

Just governance further depends on building multi-level accountability. Collaboration between EU, national, and local authorities must move beyond consultation towards genuine co-decision and shared responsibility. Participatory monitoring mechanisms can bring local voices into the evaluation of biodiversity policies, strengthening both legitimacy and transparency. Reinforcing the ERA framework through participatory science and inclusive knowledge systems would also bridge the distance between research, policy, and practice, recognising diverse forms of expertise — from academic to experiential — as equally relevant to decision-making.

Finally, empowerment must become one of the main guiding principles of biodiversity governance. Moving beyond awareness-raising, Member States should commit to frameworks that guarantee communities and local actors' genuine decision-making power. This requires long-term institutional and financial support for community-led initiatives, as well as recognition of care, reciprocity, and collective agency as foundations of transformative governance. Empowerment, in this sense, means transferring not only skills but also legitimacy and resources, ensuring that those most affected by ecological transitions have the means to shape them directly.

LOCAL AND REGIONAL PATHWAYS FOR INCLUSIVE GOVERNANCE

At the local and regional levels, where biodiversity regeneration materialises most directly, inclusive governance depends on strengthening capacities, recognition, and collaboration. Training local actors — including municipal staff, forest councils, water committees, and NGOs — to identify gender-differentiated risks is a crucial step toward equitable adaptation. Applying gender and representativeness indicators in nature-based projects can further ensure that underrepresented groups are not only consulted but effectively included in decision-making. Co-governance arrangements, co-designed with community participation, can integrate the voices of women, Roma, migrants, youth, and elderly people into biodiversity strategies.

Equally important is recognising the heterogeneity of women's experiences. Intersectional approaches must guide local adaptation plans, accounting for the distinct vulnerabilities of rural, migrant, Indigenous, and elderly women. Small-scale, low-barrier strategies — such

as community seed banks, women herder networks, or social economy cooperatives — should be valued as entry points for broader governance inclusion. Supporting these practices helps anchor regeneration in community life and prevents local initiatives from being overshadowed by externally imposed models.

To advance inclusivity, it becomes essential to promote living labs and experimental spaces where biodiversity solutions are co-created with local communities. These participatory labs can bridge institutional and community knowledge, ensuring that regeneration strategies remain locally grounded. Supporting diverse local economy models — including cooperatives, solidarity-based enterprises, and partnerships between producers and municipalities — contributes to both ecological regeneration and social resilience. Financial support should also target the initial costs of adopting regenerative techniques, particularly in regions facing multiple challenges such as desertification, depopulation, and ageing populations.

Finally, encouraging innovative and inclusive business models can foster long-term sustainability. Local entrepreneurs — especially women and young people — can play a pivotal role in making biodiversity governance economically viable. Recognising and supporting their participation not only strengthens regeneration efforts but also reinforces the social and economic foundations of transformative change.

POLICYMAKING APPLIED TO RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

At the European policy level, research and innovation frameworks have played a decisive role in setting the direction for how biodiversity and justice are addressed together. Embedding inclusive gender perspectives into the European Research Area (ERA) is not simply a matter of representation, but of improving the quality and social relevance of environmental knowledge. To advance transformative change, it becomes crucial to mainstream gender within biodiversity-related research agendas, ensuring that regenerative and climate-oriented innovations systematically integrate gender-sensitive analysis. Expanding the ERA monitoring system to include such considerations would enable a more coherent evaluation of how gender and equity contribute to the effectiveness of sustainability transitions.

This also calls for sustained investment in capacity building. Providing researchers and practitioners with training in intersectional methodologies can strengthen their ability to capture the lived experiences of biodiversity loss and regeneration. By combining empirical evidence with intersectional insight, biodiversity governance can become more attuned to social complexity and to the differentiated vulnerabilities that underlie ecological crises. Likewise, strengthening gender equality and diversity data within governance systems is indispensable for revealing how biodiversity degradation disproportionately affects marginalised groups. Reliable and gender-disaggregated data are key to building policies that reflect the realities of those most impacted.

Beyond the research sphere, it is equally vital to raise public awareness and promote local ownership of inclusive gender agenda. Achieving the objectives of the European Commission on gender equity requires the engagement of local civil society organisations and municipal authorities, whose support is fundamental to overcome resistance and ensure that equality is not perceived as an external imposition. Mobilising high-impact sectors — such as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and urban development — to embed gender-sensitive biodiversity criteria in their policies would also help close the gap between

policy ambition and practice. Without such alignment, efforts toward regeneration risk reproducing existing inequalities rather than dismantling them.

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9 Biodiversity interdependencies of SDGs (T3.5)

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9.1 Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were designed as a global framework for tackling interconnected social, economic, and environmental challenges (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2025). They represent an ambitious effort to align global priorities (e.g. environmental, social, economic and geopolitical) and mobilise collective action (e.g., of people, communities, NGOs, industries, local, national and global policy makers and authorities) toward ways of living that respect planetary limits. Yet, while the SDGs defines broad areas for transformation and provides general guidelines, the scale and complexity of social, economic and environmental challenges vary widely across countries, communities, and ecosystems, shaping how these goals are understood, prioritised, and acted upon (Arora-Jonsson, 2023).

Biodiversity-focused goals, such as SDG 14 Life below water and SDG 15 Life on land (in some sources also SDGs 13 – climate action and 6 – clean water and sanitation), were specifically built to address the biodiversity loss related crisis (Azote for Stockholm Resilience Centre, 2016; Obrecht et al., 2021) and occupy a crucial position within this framework. Healthy ecosystems lay the basis for progress across other domains: from food security and public health to climate resilience and economic stability.

The interdependence of goals is now widely acknowledged (Breuer et al., 2019; Nilsson et al., 2016; Reyers & Selig, 2020), and biodiversity is increasingly recognised as a foundation for achieving nearly all other SDGs (Blicharska et al., 2019). Healthy ecosystems are fundamental for achieving progress in other domains, as they provide the essential resources required to sustain nature and humanity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022; Crossman et al., 2018; World Economic Forum, 2020). Nature-reliant industries alone account for more than half of global gross domestic product, approximately 44 trillion USD (World Economic Forum, 2020), illustrating the economic importance of properly functioning ecosystems. Conversely, biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation can cascade into social and economic instability. When ecosystems recover, benefits often ripple outward, supporting sustainable agriculture, cleaner water, and improved human well-being (Dainese et al., 2019).

The SDGs, though widely adopted, are increasingly criticised for many reasons (Arora-Jonsson, 2023; Bogers et al., 2022; Swain, 2018; Veland et al., 2022; Vogt, 2022). They are said to be too generic and hard to measure, to reinforce global power imbalances, impose a one-size-fits-all approach that neglects the unique needs of the Global South, prioritise corporate interests over local communities, and overlook historical injustices like colonial exploitation. They are also seen as overly focusing on anthropocentric concerns

¹⁶ This chapter is related to and partially based on deliverable D3.5 *Policy Brief* and deliverable D3.6 *Infographic*. Other consortium partners contributed to these deliverables and are acknowledged [here](#) and [here](#).

and perpetuating reliance on international aid rather than fostering autonomy for historically exploited nations (Adelman, 2018; Kopnina, 2019).

These tensions invite a re-examination of what the SDGs mean and/or achieve in practice, especially in areas directly related to biodiversity conservation and regeneration. If the SDGs are to remain meaningful instruments for transformation, their conceptual and structural shortcomings should be acknowledged alongside their strengths. Doing so opens space for adapting the framework to real-world contexts and for integrating more inclusive and locally shaped approaches.

Within this wider debate, the BIOTraCes project contributes empirical insight from case studies across Europe, exploring how the interdependencies between biodiversity and the SDGs manifest in diverse contexts. Task 3.5 focuses specifically on these interconnections, how different goals supports or hinders biodiversity recovery, and how biodiversity itself enables sustainable development across sectors such as agriculture, forestry, water, and urban environments. By examining these dynamics through participatory and cross-case approaches, this work aims to inform strategies and policies that move beyond declarative sustainability toward place-based transformative change. Based on the literature discussed above and on internal discussions with Work Package 3 team, we will focus on analysing the following four key statements:

- Reaching SDGs depends on biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- Biodiversity recovery depends on reaching other SDGs;
- SDGs as leverage and/or barriers for biodiversity conservation;
- SDG Interdependencies are aligned with PEPE principles.

9.2 Method

To explore these statements, the survey was conducted in SurveyMonkey platform. The method is described extensively in [Survey on sustainable development goals \(T3.5\)](#). In brief, in November 2024, the MRU team conducted a survey across all BIOTraCes case study partners to explore how SDGs are understood and enacted within diverse biodiversity-related contexts. The instrument, refined through collaboration with Task 3.5 partners, combined closed and open-ended questions and a creative mapping exercise to capture interconnections between biodiversity and SDGs as they appear in everyday project work. Nine research teams from eight European countries participated, either collectively or through delegated representatives, while a shorter version of the survey gathered perspectives from societal partners. Together, these responses provided full coverage across the consortium and revealed how the SDGs' relevance and meaning shift across heterogeneous local contexts. Descriptive and thematic analyses were used to identify common patterns and context-specific nuances, offering a grounded view of how SDGs take shape within practical biodiversity work.

9.3 Findings

REACHING SDG'S DEPENDS ON BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Across the consortium, participants emphasised that biodiversity and ecosystem services underpin the achievement of multiple SDGs. Biodiversity was often described as a **foundational enabler**, a precondition for social well-being, food security, local livelihoods,

and community resilience. Several case teams explicitly framed biodiversity as *the starting point* from which other SDGs could meaningfully unfold.

In multiple responses, participants linked **healthy ecosystems** to specific SDG outcomes such as **food security (SDG 2)**, **clean water (SDG 6)**, and **climate action (SDG 13)**. One team (Q12, Hungarian case) observed that *'if biodiversity improves, the condition of grasslands improves, and the situation of herders improves because of more healthy animals, more animals or products to sell.'* Similarly, another team (Q12, Portuguese case) noted that **wildlife management and habitat conservation** create opportunities for sustainable tourism and eco-friendly local businesses, which in turn promote community well-being and economic development. Biodiversity was thus seen not as a competing goal but as a practical route toward other SDGs.

Teams also highlighted that **ecosystem services sustain human livelihoods and social stability**. For instance, river and wetland restoration projects were reported to reduce erosion, improve soil quality, and enhance recreation opportunities: all contributing to improved health, economic activity, and social cohesion (Q10, Portuguese case; Q11, Portuguese case; Q12, Lithuanian case). This aligns with other cases where biodiversity improvements were said to *help generate better living conditions for local people* (Q12, Dutch Eco-village case / Dutch Province case). In such examples, biodiversity recovery directly supported multiple non-environmental SDGs, revealing its role as a cross-cutting enabler.

Several participants described this link through the concept of **ecosystem regeneration as leverage for transformation**. One team emphasised that restoring ecosystems *'contributes to water retention, reduces erosion, and enhances the overall productivity of the land in a sustainable way'* (Q15, Portuguese case), while another viewed biodiversity management as *maintaining the soil and water balance of grasslands* (Q15, Hungarian case). These statements connect ecological processes to social and economic well-being, suggesting that biodiversity is not an isolated environmental concern but a systemic driver of sustainable development.

At the same time, participants acknowledged that these positive dynamics are **not automatic**. In several cases, the benefits of biodiversity for achieving other SDGs depended on active local management and governance. For example, one team observed that *'stakeholders only talk about fish and sediments'* when discussing biodiversity recovery (Q15, Lithuanian case), implying that a limited understanding of ecosystem complexity could weaken its contribution to broader SDG outcomes. Others stressed the need for social inclusion and knowledge sharing to ensure that biodiversity improvements truly translate into tangible benefits for communities (Q16, Dutch Foodpark case; Q16, Lithuanian case).

Taken together, the data show that participants perceive biodiversity and ecosystem services as **central to achieving the SDGs**, particularly by supporting food security, water quality, economic diversification, and community resilience. Yet these links remain **context-dependent**, requiring inclusive governance and local ecological literacy to convert ecological gains into sustained social outcomes.

BIODIVERSITY RECOVERY DEPENDS ON REACHING OTHER SDG'S

Across the case studies, biodiversity recovery was not seen as an isolated ecological goal but as something tightly connected to social, economic, and institutional change. Teams repeatedly stressed that biodiversity can only flourish when other SDGs, especially those focused on inequality, education, governance, and livelihoods, are also cultivated.

Several teams (Hungarian case, Portuguese case, Romanian case, and Swedish case) described biodiversity and ecosystem services as inseparable from social stability and local economic well-being. Hungarian case involving grasslands showed this interdependence: *'The herders need the grass to graze. The grassland needs the herders to maintain the grassland by grazing it'* (Hungarian case, Q12). Here, biodiversity and livelihoods sustain one another. Portuguese case viewed regeneration through a similar lens, linking ecological recovery to social justice and inclusion. They argued that improving soil fertility and water regulation through regenerative practices *'can stabilise local food systems and reduce dependency on external inputs'* (Portuguese case, Q11). These examples show that regeneration is not only environmental target, but it is also social, about rebuilding livelihoods, redistributing power, and restoring the human–nature relationship.

Many cases echoed the same idea: where social deprivation, exclusion, or weak governance persist, biodiversity cannot recover. Participants pointed to corruption, emigration, and lack of education as major barriers. P5's team captured this well: *'Empowerment, social capital, stopping the emigration of youngsters, the high levels of corruption, educational challenges, gender equity and ethnic fragmentation (...) largely determine the state of biodiversity in the near future'* Romanian case, Q16). These social conditions, they argued, define whether biodiversity can thrive. P6 added that stronger inclusion of women and fairer governance can accelerate progress since *'women tend to prioritise environmental values more than men'* (Swedish case, Q16).

Education emerged as another key factor supporting biodiversity recovery. Lithuanian case and Spanish case representatives both emphasised that learning can nurture ecological awareness. Representatives from the Lithuanian case suggested that *'ensuring quality education related with sustainability and biodiversity could help. Children with comprehensive knowledge could influence their parents' values'* (Lithuanian case, Q16). Similarly, Spanish case representatives with *'green schoolyard'* initiative illustrated that engaging children with nature early can shape long-term attitudes. They noted that greener schoolyards *'provide ecosystem services such as improved air quality (...) stormwater absorption (...) and physical and psychological health of pupils'* (Spanish case, Q10).

Economic development was seen as both an opportunity and a risk. Some teams (Portuguese case, Lithuanian case and Romanian case) pointed out that sustainable local businesses, such as eco-tourism or biocultural entrepreneurship, can reinforce biodiversity recovery when growth is decoupled from exploitation. As Romanian case representative put it, *'The rich natural capital and biocultural values provide identity for the region and people from the cities search for this identity'* (Q12). But others (Dutch Foodpark case, Spanish case, Italian case) warned that SDG frameworks still too often rely on capitalist growth models. P8 said that *'the concept of 'ecosystem service' is scarcely compatible or even harmful for biodiversity, because it conveys the logic of exploitation and extraction'* (Italian case, Q11).

Despite such concerns, participants broadly agreed that social cohesion and good governance (SDG 16) form the backbone of ecological restoration. Teams emphasised participatory decision-making, inclusive governance, and trust between citizens and institutions as essential for long-term biodiversity recovery. Portuguese case representative described this connection thusly: *'When marginalised groups (...) have a stronger voice and access to resources, biodiversity conservation can benefit from a more inclusive approach that leverages local knowledge (...) traditional practices (...)'* (Q16). This shared view (reflected in Dutch Foodpark case, Portuguese case, Romanian case and Dutch eco-village case / Dutch Province case) suggested that achieving goals on equality, justice, education, and well-being creates the foundation for biodiversity to recover and endure.

Overall, the case studies converge on a following idea: biodiversity recovery cannot happen without social recovery. Achieving non-biodiversity SDGs is not optional, it is essential. As Hungarian case representative put it, *'If a local herder community can maintain because of non-biodiversity-related SDGs, the community can help the regeneration of biodiversity through their work'* (Q16). Poverty reduction, education, equality, and trust are the cornerstones on which ecological renewal could be built. Without them, biodiversity goals risk remaining abstract or externally imposed.

SDG'S: LEVERAGE OR BARRIERS FOR BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION?

Across the case studies, participants described the SDGs as both a source of leverage and a source of limitation for biodiversity conservation. For some, the SDGs provided a valuable common language to engage policymakers and connect local work to global agendas. For others, they remained distant, abstract, or even counterproductive when applied to complex local realities.

Several teams viewed the SDGs as a **useful advocacy tool**, a broad framework that can legitimise biodiversity initiatives in institutional or funding contexts. The Dutch Foodpark case team noted that SDGs may *'serve civic initiatives to make themselves legible at a larger policy level, for example for funding and recognition'* (Q1). Similarly, the Portuguese case team emphasised that the goals can *'enhance civic engagement, especially in rural and remote areas,'* providing a way to translate community-based biodiversity conservation efforts into policy language that decision-makers understand (Q1). In this sense, the SDGs were seen as a form of leverage, a symbolic and political resource that allows local actors to speak the same language as governments, funders, and international institutions.

At the same time, many participants criticised **SDGs' limitations**, especially their tendency to remain generic, technocratic, or detached from lived realities. The Lithuanian case team described their use as *'declarative, difficult to understand and translate into practice,'* often resulting in *'artificial application'* or even *'a manipulative tool for greenwashing'* (Q1). This sentiment was echoed by the Spanish case team, who observed that while the SDGs promote a holistic focus, they largely reflect *'a global minimum consensus'* that allows governments to continue their *'economic models while reconciling them with sustainability,'* rather than pursuing real systemic change (Q1).

Several teams also questioned whether the SDGs' underlying logic supports biodiversity at all. The Italian case team argued that the goals are *'fully framed within the paradigm of capitalist endless growth'* and therefore risk undermining ecological protection by maintaining the same extractive logic they claim to reform (Q1). The Dutch Foodpark case

extended this critique, pointing out that the SDGs '*do not sufficiently recognise colonial histories and mainly provide solutions that would allow wealthy regions in the global North to continue with business as usual*' (Q1). From this perspective, the SDGs act less as transformative instruments and more as tools that reproduce existing global inequalities and anthropocentric thinking.

Despite these strong critiques, participants did not dismiss the framework entirely. Some expressed that even if the SDGs are flawed, they can still be strategically mobilised to promote biodiversity objectives within established systems. As the Dutch Foodpark case team phrased it, '*they may be useful in specific cases to remind authorities of their commitments and reduce harm*' (Q1). Likewise, the Dutch eco-village / Dutch Province case team framed the SDGs as an '*intersectional platform*' that highlights how biodiversity overlaps with goals such as health (SDG 3), inequality (SDG 10), and sustainable cities (SDG 11), creating opportunities for '*bio- and lifestyle innovations*' (Q1).

Taken together, the responses portray the SDGs as a double-edged framework: an imperfect but sometimes necessary instrument. On one hand, they provide political visibility, common vocabulary, and legitimacy to biodiversity-related work. On the other, they risk diluting transformative ambitions, legitimising unsustainable systems, and masking local power dynamics under global narratives of progress. To sum up, the SDGs can serve as useful leverage when strategically localised and critically examined, but uncritical adoption risks turning them into barriers rather than catalysts for biodiversity transformation.

ALIGNMENT OF SDG INTERDEPENDENCIES WITH PEPE PRINCIPLES

Across the case studies, participants' reflections on the SDGs revealed multiple ways in which the four PEPE principles, Pluralising, Empowering, Politicising, and Embedding, were echoed, challenged, or only partially realised. While the SDGs often served as a unifying framework, participants consistently emphasised the importance of context, participation, and justice – values that resonate strongly with the spirit of PEPE, though not always with the SDG framework itself. It is important to note that participants were not directly asked about the PEPE principles in the survey; rather, the analysis identified naturally emerging instances of PEPE-aligned ideas within their reflections on SDG interdependencies.

Pluralising was the most visibly reinforced principle across the responses. Many teams stressed that biodiversity and sustainability must be interpreted through multiple worldviews and forms of knowledge rather than a single technocratic narrative. The Portuguese case team emphasised that pluralising means ensuring that marginalised voices are included when discussing both the impacts of biodiversity loss and the goals of biodiversity regeneration. They highlighted that pluralising is not only about developing goals that benefit these communities, but also about redistributing power so that local people can actively shape biodiversity outcomes (Q1). Similarly, the Hungarian case and Romanian case teams emphasised that SDGs cannot be separated in real life, they '*are specific objectives of interrelated processes*' (Q1), and therefore might require approaches that respect local interdependencies between ecology, economy, and culture. This recognition of diversity, both ecological and social, supports pluralisation by rejecting one-size-fits-all solutions. However, several participants warned that the SDGs' universal framing can erase difference, noting that their '*development legacy*' and '*capitalist roots*'

risk silencing non-Western and community-driven perspectives (Dutch Foodpark case and Italian case, Q1).

The principle of Empowering was expressed through attention to participation, education, local autonomy as well as community and people's agency. Many teams linked biodiversity recovery to empowerment of communities, particularly those historically excluded from environmental decision-making. The Portuguese case and Swedish case teams highlighted that equitable participation of women and marginalised groups strengthens biodiversity governance, since *'women tend to prioritise environmental values more than men'* (Swedish case, Q16) and participatory models *'enable marginalised groups to benefit from and contribute to ecological recovery'* (Portuguese case, Q16). The Lithuanian case and Spanish case teams also saw education as a tool of empowerment, noting that *'children with comprehensive knowledge could influence their parents' values'* (Lithuanian case, Q16) and that green schoolyard initiatives foster early ecological awareness (Spanish case, Q10). Yet empowerment was not always assured; the Romanian case team cautioned that corruption, youth emigration, and low institutional trust *'largely determine the state of biodiversity in the near future'* (Q16), suggesting that empowerment requires more than awareness, it demands social stability and supportive governance structures.

Politicising, acknowledging that biodiversity transformation is not neutral but inherently political, appeared more implicitly in the data. Several teams questioned the SDGs themselves as part of the problem, rather than a neutral framework. The Dutch Foodpark case team directly criticised their *'failure to recognise colonial histories,'* while the Spanish case and Italian case teams argued that global targets often *'reinforce existing economic hierarchies rather than challenge them'* (Q1). These reflections reveal that the SDG framework, while aspirational, can reproduce the very power asymmetries it seeks to address. At the same time, other teams (e.g., Portuguese case and Dutch eco-village case/ Dutch Province case) demonstrated politicisation through practice, showing how biodiversity initiatives can reframe SDGs from bottom-up. Portuguese case team described efforts to align SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) with inclusive governance, where *'local voices and needs shape biodiversity solutions'* (Q1). Similarly, The Dutch eco-village case / Dutch Province case approached SDG interlinkages as a space to negotiate new forms of agency, positioning local innovation as both ecological and political action. Across these examples, politicisation emerges not from rejecting the SDGs outright, but from reclaiming them as tools for contesting inequality and redistributing voice within governance.

Embedding, integrating biodiversity within broader systems of policy, economy, and everyday life, was most clearly reflected in cases where ecological and social functions were treated as interdependent. Participants repeatedly stressed that biodiversity cannot be separated from livelihood systems or governance structures. As one team put it, *'The herders need the grass to graze. The grassland needs the herders to maintain the grassland by grazing it'* (Hungarian case, Q12). Similar dynamics appeared in cases linking biodiversity to food security, education, and urban design, showing that environmental goals become meaningful only when rooted in local realities. However, while local practices often demonstrated embeddedness in action, institutional frameworks were seen as lagging behind. The Spanish case and Lithuanian case teams noted that SDGs are frequently applied *'artificially'* or *'declaratively,'* reflecting weak policy integration and limited cross-sectoral alignment (Q1). This contrast suggests that while embedding often

emerges organically through local practice, its translation into formal SDG processes and policy frameworks remains limited or inconsistent across cases.

Taken together, the data suggest that the interdependencies between SDGs can both align with and challenge the PEPE principles. Elements of Pluralising and Empowering were most visible in participants' emphasis on inclusion, knowledge diversity, and locally rooted agency, while Politicising and Embedding appeared more unevenly, often emerging as reflections on inequality, power, and policy gaps. Across cases, the SDGs provided a common language and reference point for discussing transformation, yet participants repeatedly noted that their frameworks remain too abstract or top-down to fully support plural, empowering, politically aware, and embedded approaches to biodiversity governance.

9.4 Discussion

The findings across all four analytical points reveal a complex but coherent story: biodiversity is not simply one goal within the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) framework, it is the ecological foundation upon which sustainable development stands or falls. At the same time, the data show that the realisation of biodiversity goals is inseparable from the fulfilment of social, economic, and institutional dimensions of sustainability (Azote for Stockholm Resilience Centre, 2016; Blicharska et al., 2019; World Economic Forum, 2020). This indicates both, the potential and the limits of the SDGs as instruments for just, transformative change.

BIODIVERSITY AS A SYSTEMIC ENABLER

Participants consistently described biodiversity not as a discrete target but as a cross-cutting condition for achieving most SDGs. Biodiversity and ecosystem services were portrayed as the life-support systems that sustain food security, health, livelihoods, and community resilience. This perspective echoes recent scholarship emphasising that biodiversity functions as the connective tissue of the SDG framework rather than a single sector within it (Blicharska et al., 2019; Reyers & Selig, 2020). By framing biodiversity as a prerequisite rather than an outcome, participants positioned ecological restoration as the necessary entry point for sustainable development.

However, the data also reveal that this understanding is not yet mirrored in policy and institutional design. Participants frequently noted that biodiversity is still treated as a specialised domain rather than an integrative concern. This fragmentation weakens cross-sectoral collaboration and constrains the capacity to leverage biodiversity as a unifying driver of sustainability. The challenge ahead lies in translating the systemic understanding observed in practice into governance structures that recognise biodiversity's enabling role across policy areas (Bogers et al., 2022; Termeer et al., 2024).

THE SOCIAL PRECONDITIONS OF ECOLOGICAL RECOVERY

The cases further illustrate that biodiversity recovery depends fundamentally on the fulfilment of other SDGs. Participants repeatedly emphasised that without poverty reduction, education, gender equality, and inclusive governance, biodiversity efforts remain superficial or short-lived. This finding challenges traditional conservation models

that isolate ecological goals from social realities. Instead, it supports an emerging consensus that environmental recovery and social justice must proceed together, that social recovery is the soil in which ecological recovery takes root (Nilsson et al., 2016; Obrecht et al., 2021).

The emphasis on livelihoods, empowerment, and local governance aligns with theories of just sustainability and environmental justice (Buelow et al., 2023; Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021), which stress that fairness, participation, and redistribution are prerequisites for durable ecological outcomes. In this sense, the data point to a bidirectional relationship: biodiversity enables sustainable societies, but sustainable societies enable biodiversity (Reyers & Selig, 2020; United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2025). This reciprocity moves beyond simple notions of 'balance' toward a model of mutual reinforcement, a socio-ecological contract that must be cultivated rather than assumed.

THE SDG'S AS A DOUBLE-EDGED GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

The third analytical point indicates an ambivalence running through the data: the SDGs serve both as leverage and as limitation. On one side, participants acknowledged the SDGs' value as a shared global language, offering legitimacy and political traction for biodiversity initiatives in policy and funding arenas. On the other, they criticised the framework for its technocratic and depoliticised character — for providing visibility without necessarily enabling transformation (Bogers et al., 2022; Swain, 2018).

This duality reflects a deeper tension between global universality and local specificity. While the SDGs can connect local projects to global agendas, their standardised logic often obscures place-based realities, historical injustices, and power asymmetries. Participants' concerns about greenwashing, superficial implementation, and capitalist growth paradigms highlight this dissonance. The implication is not to abandon the SDGs but to engage them critically (Buelow et al., 2023; Swain, 2018; Vogt, 2022), to use them as scaffolding for context-driven approaches rather than as templates for uniform action. Locally grounded reinterpretations of SDGs may thus represent the most promising pathway for translating global ambition into transformative practice (United Nations, 2024).

The PEPE principles as diagnostic lenses for transformation

Applying the PEPE principles – Pluralising, Empowering, Politicising, and Embedding – provides an additional interpretive layer for understanding how SDG interdependencies either support or constrain transformative change (Chambers et al., 2020). The data suggest that Pluralising and Empowering were the most clearly aligned with participants' practices and reflections. Many emphasised inclusion, contextualisation, and diversity of knowledge systems, echoing the principle of Pluralising. Empowering was also strongly present, particularly in the recurring focus on education, community participation, and equitable governance as enablers of biodiversity recovery.

Politicising and Embedding, however, appeared more unevenly. Politicisation emerged mainly through critique: participants identified the SDGs' colonial and economic underpinnings, exposing how global frameworks may reproduce rather than dismantle structural inequalities (Adelman, 2018; Kopnina, 2019; Vogt, 2022). Yet, some teams demonstrated a form of healthy, bottom-up politicisation in through practice, creating participatory spaces where marginalised voices could mobilise for their rights, reshape

governance and challenge top-down decision-making. Embedding was most visible in local examples where biodiversity was integrated into daily life, livelihoods, and education. However, participants also noted that formal institutions lag behind these grounded practices, often applying the SDGs superficially rather than structurally. This mismatch points to a broader governance gap: local actions often embody PEPE values more fully than the global frameworks meant to support them.

TOWARD CONTEXTUALLY GROUNDED, JUSTICE-ORIENTED TRANSFORMATION

Overall, the findings converge on a simple but demanding insight: transformation cannot be technocratic. It requires contextual, plural, and power-aware approaches that treat biodiversity as both ecological and social infrastructure. The interdependencies between SDGs are not just technical linkages but moral and political ones. Achieving biodiversity-related goals therefore depends on creating enabling conditions for justice, inclusion, and local agency, conditions that allow transformation to take root where people live and act (Van Dijk et al., 2023; Veland et al., 2022; Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021).

From this perspective, the SDGs retain value not as fixed targets but as evolving reference points — a language that can be reinterpreted through place-based practice. Integrating the PEPE principles into SDG implementation could strengthen this evolution by rooting abstract goals in plural voices, empowering communities, acknowledging power relations, and embedding ecological thinking across governance levels. The challenge is not only to make the SDGs measurable but to make them meaningful: reflective of real-world interdependencies and capable of supporting the kind of transformation that is both sustainable and just.

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10 Concluding discussion

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In this concluding chapter, we revisit the PEPE principles – pluralising, empowering, politicising and embedding – around which the BIOTraCes project is based, and consider the findings from the respective tasks 3.1-5 through this conceptual lens.

10.1 Pluralising

Pluralising concerns acknowledging the roles of multiple stakeholders and variation in views and values, emphasising bottom-up perspectives.

Many of the leverage points identified in **T3.1** support the principle of pluralising. They contribute to the pluralisation of knowledge and values that inform policy making and overall governance which also allows relational and marginal perspectives to be expressed. This ultimately supports shifting overall imaginaries to be more inclusive of multiple forms of human-nature relations. A key leverage point lies in the research activities deployed for the co-production of knowledge. These activities offer important spaces for plural perspectives to be shared and communicated/disseminated as they serve as spaces of dialogue where diverse actors can meet, spread awareness and knowledge regarding the local biodiversity challenge and the innovation, and can help draw attention to traditional and local knowledges of marginalised groups in governance processes.

Amplification processes increasing the impact within the local context pluralise for instance by bringing together a wide range of actors holding different values, knowledges, and worldviews. By creating local communities and networks, those plural voices can be shared locally and contribute to pluralise local governance structures and imaginaries of the territory. Amplifying out by building and participating in cross-scale networks helps to transfer and exchange local perspectives and knowledges to other places and communities, enabling processes of learning from similar, but also socially-ecologically different places by providing situated local knowledge to tackle global issues. These processes help to scale plural notions emerging from local contexts.

T3.2 found that the cases shared an emphasis on stakeholder engagement and participation in processes of (transformative) change to ensure their varied perspectives are voiced and – hopefully – heard. They encourage participation and engagement, including representation of diverse groups and perspectives among stakeholders. One aspect is a broadened view of the importance of diverse forms of knowledge. Many case studies emphasise local, contextual knowledge – including traditional knowledge – as essential for the success of biodiversity initiatives. They also focus on knowledge co-production where ‘experts’ or researchers interact with local stakeholders. There are indications that pluralising efforts in the case studies can contribute to place attachment/local pride, reconnection to local heritage, and strengthened local and regional peer networks.

Despite these efforts, broad representation can be difficult to achieve in practice. Participation often becomes restricted to certain groups (e.g., men or highly educated

professionals and established organisations), reflecting power asymmetries and diversity among local stakeholders. Achieving broad participation of local communities is difficult, especially marginalised or (socially or geographically) hard-to-reach groups. The cross-case analysis also revealed friction between different types of knowledge, reflecting power asymmetries between local groups and experts/government representatives and flawed communication.

In the **T3.3** findings, pluralising emerged as a pervasive principle, reflected in efforts to open spaces where multiple worldviews, values, and knowledge systems could meet. Such strategies often focused on dialogue and encounter, ranging from designing and organising events (festivals, workshops) to structured spaces such as experimentation sites and organised networks. In early-stage cases, initial trust had to be built, paving the way for richer deliberations downstream. Informants mentioned they went in to 'listen' where other actors had rather 'sent' messages or where previously encounters had been rare. While this does not automatically transpire into pluralising limited agendas, these encounters did open up communities and transgressed cultural boundaries.

Many strategies within biodiversity innovations contribute to pluralising by combining emphasis on 'encounters' with experimental work and showcasing biodiversity-inclusive practices – whether 'old' or 'new' ones. These strategies allow expression of marginalised values and practices, tapping into traditional or more-than-human repertoires. Because of this, pluralising often went hand in hand with empowering: building people's capacity to act and generating momentum to move towards transformative change.

In **T3.4**, pluralisation emerged as a central condition for transformation in biodiversity governance. Efforts to bring together different actors, epistemologies, and values – scientific, local, and experiential – revealed how diverse knowledge systems can coexist and enrich governance processes. However, this coexistence is rarely straightforward: institutional inertia, epistemic hierarchies, and fragmented communication channels still limit the recognition of alternative ways of knowing and acting. The cases show that pluralising governance is less about adding voices than about redistributing epistemic authority – acknowledging that multiple ontologies of nature coexist within European territories and that regeneration cannot rely solely on technocratic expertise.

Where pluralising practices succeeded, they did so by creating hybrid spaces where negotiation, translation, and mutual learning became integral to decision-making. These arrangements reveal that inclusive governance requires sustained facilitation, attention to power asymmetries, and institutional mechanisms that value participation as a generative, not symbolic, process. The challenge now is to strengthen such infrastructures of dialogue and ensure that pluralisation becomes an enduring characteristic of governance cultures, rather than an experimental exception.

The **T3.5** findings show that pluralising is key to turning the SDGs into biodiversity actions that make sense locally. Participants stressed that real transformation depends on including many kinds of knowledge and experience—scientific, local, traditional, and cultural. Instead of using the SDGs as a strict checklist, local actors shaped them around the realities of their own places: grasslands, rivers, forests, and cities. This plural approach worked best when different forms of knowledge came together, showing that biodiversity recovery thrives when people learn from each other's perspectives. Participants agreed that the SDGs cannot succeed if they are applied without local adaptation. They also warned that the SDGs' global language often overshadows local realities, making it crucial to keep different interpretations visible in decision-making.

10.2 Empowering

Empowering entails an ambition of strengthening the voices of marginalised groups.

In **T3.1**, leverage points identified that point towards processes of empowerment are those enabling meaningful participation of local communities in the decision-making process and those that put specific emphasis on the inclusion of marginalised actors, so their voices and perspectives are given space to be expressed and listened to, e.g., through the research activity. For instance, in some cases, traditional knowledge holders are empowered by collecting their knowledge and communicating it to policymakers. In other cases, marginal actors are empowered to partake in workshops and share their perspectives. However, overall, the principle of empowering was relatively marginal in T3.1. An assumption for why empowerment did not appear so much in the leverage points lies in the fact that, for many biodiversity innovations to be amplified, local communities and their empowerment are important as a first step, so the local innovation emerges. However, for its long-term success and stability, reaching decision-making processes and impacting governance structures are more important. That is, more emphasis in leveraging and amplification is placed on processes that support pluralisation and embedding of the innovation.

Empowerment can be seen as both a source from which initiative arise, and as something that is strengthened as through these. **T3.2** finds examples of empowerment in local actors' ability to initiate and sustain diverse initiatives to support biodiversity by addressing its various drivers across high-impact sectors and in different contexts. Not least, the biodiversity initiatives, while at varied stages of evolution, point to the importance of persistence and the presence of individuals and groups willing to act as torchbearers. Networking and connecting with others is a key strategy, whether as a way of expanding a social movement, targeting and lobbying for change through policy and decision-makers, or cooperating and exchanging knowledge (co-learning) between local groups and, for example, researchers. Long-term engagement allows initiatives to grow, mature, build confidence and capacity, and hence resilience. However, the cross-case analysis also shows that many initiatives are fragile, not least due to their dependence on relatively short-term budget cycles and vulnerability to political volatility at local, regional, or national levels. An insufficient resource base or lack of political support can undermine continuity and lasting empowerment. Grassroots actors also remain conditioned by structures and higher-level authorities, and hence their empowerment – at least in the short term – mainly occurs within constrained settings.

Empowering was closely associated with pluralising in the co-strategies recorded for **T3.3**. Pluralising emphasises views and agendas, while empowering looks at the people. Empowering was pursued in mostly the same kind of strategies as emerged for pluralising: strategies focused on creating encounters, on involving communities, performing engaged research and strengthening networks connecting actors. The strategy type 'co-building' was somewhat more prevalent, meaning that empowering emphasises the strengthening of networks and building of co-governance structures somewhat more than the encounters/creating spaces emphasis in pluralising. Outcomes of 'empowering' strategies highlighted how people gained a sense of ownership, or sometimes cultural pride, in the biodiversity innovations at hand. Increases in recognition and visibility were also often mentioned. Empowering strategies seemed often to work out well, with positive outcomes reported. However, the degree to which the marginalised communities are actually

'empowered' in the face of the wicked problems and unequal opportunities of our biodiversity case studies remains to be seen. This was not evaluated in the project.

In **T3.4** empowerment is seen as both a process and a condition for transformative governance. The BIOTraCes findings emphasise that community agency – particularly among women, vulnerable people, and marginalised groups – flourishes when institutions share not only knowledge but also decision-making power, resources, and legitimacy. Across the cases, empowerment took form where local actors were recognised as co-creators of governance rather than beneficiaries of external interventions. These experiences underline that empowerment is inseparable from autonomy; otherwise, participation will mean licence to operate rather than effective community resilience.

To consolidate empowerment, governance frameworks must provide stable financial and institutional support for community-led initiatives, ensuring that transformative action is not contingent on temporary projects. Recognising care, reciprocity, and collective agency as foundations of governance expands the understanding of what counts as political action and who counts as a decision-maker. In this sense, empowerment is not an endpoint but a relational dynamic – one that transforms both institutions and communities by redistributing responsibility for ecological transition.

In **T3.5**, empowerment emerged as both a human and ecological necessity within the SDG context. Participants emphasised that achieving biodiversity-related goals depends on giving communities and the ecosystems they represent, the capacity to act. Education, participatory governance, and gender inclusion repeatedly appeared as effective ways to make the SDGs meaningful on the ground. Empowerment also extended to non-human entities: species, rivers, and ecosystems that rely on human representatives to voice their needs within SDG decision-making processes. Several cases showed that when local people gain the skills and legitimacy to represent nature, biodiversity gains political standing, which also strengthens food systems and local resilience. Yet empowerment remains fragile where corruption, emigration, or institutional distrust persist, revealing that the social dimensions of the SDGs: justice, equality, and participation, are inseparable from their environmental aims.

10.3 Politicising

Politicising addresses political barriers to transformative change (e.g. power asymmetries, dominating interests and paradigms, path dependencies and 'lock-ins').

Leverage points contributing to politicising in **T3.1** are those factors that challenge paradigms and offer alternative practices to the dominant economic system, e.g., through alternative community-based economic structures such as local food and energy networks or local supply chains. Politicising leverage points can also be found in those processes that create alternative socio-ecological and locally rooted imaginaries, framing local initiatives as alternatives to high-impact sector 'wrongs'. These include, for example, small-scale agriculture and forestry practices that challenge dominant monocultures and extractivist paradigms; community practices such as the Commons or ecovillages that counteract individualised and nature-disconnecting ways of life; and educational approaches focusing on relational and embodied learning that aim to overcome a neoliberal educational paradigm based on standardised evaluations.

T3.2 finds that the case studies demonstrate how civic and grassroots movements can meaningfully influence public debate and discourse, challenging established norms and practices within diverse governance contexts that have high impacts on biodiversity. Stakeholders employ a wide range of communication and advocacy strategies to reach different audiences and target groups – from local communities and specific population groups to holders of formal power across various geographical- administrative levels. At times, influence is exercised through pragmatic and covert means, such as the use of neutral or depoliticised language, rather than through more overtly political or confrontational approaches.

At the same time, the local and small-scale nature of most biodiversity initiatives, along with their limited resources, often constrains their ability to tackle broader systemic issues or structural barriers. The cross-case analysis reveals that many initiatives combine strategies focused on communication and awareness-raising with efforts to influence economic and regulatory frameworks. While a few case studies explicitly pursue systemic transformation, most operate with more modest or incremental ambitions, working within their local contexts to create openings for broader change over time.

In **T3.3**, politicising was less prevalent as a strategic orientation in the co-strategies than were pluralising and empowering (about half as frequent, 20 vs 42/43 strategies). Politicising was in some cases associated with specific activities such as lobbying, activism, writing a manifesto or creative/artistic manifestations. In other cases, it was exercised – or intended – as part of more general approaches such as network building or the execution of workshops or demonstration sites. In such cases, politicising and empowering were frequently also pursued. Politicising focused more often on external networks, and government bodies in particular.

T3.4 notes that politicising biodiversity governance involves navigating a delicate boundary between empowerment and distortion. Across the cases, politicising emerged at times as an act of reclaiming agency; when communities, associations, and local actors contested decisions that affect their territories and asserted their right to co-define ecological priorities. In this sense, politicisation is essential to justice: it acknowledges that contestation, negotiation, and disagreement are integral to democratic transformation. When opened to diverse actors, politicising becomes a means of making governance accountable, transparent, and responsive to those most affected by biodiversity loss.

Yet the cases also reveal another side of politicisation: its potential for institutional capture. Politicising processes in which biodiversity and climate agendas are appropriated by partisan or sectoral interests risk eroding trust and fragmenting collective action. In such situations, environmental policies can be reduced to instruments for short-term political or economic gains, or narratives of control, rather than serving as frameworks for shared responsibility and transformation. This form of politicising distorts transformation by reinforcing existing hierarchies and power structures instead of challenging them.

For these reasons, the findings highlight the need to distinguish between politicisation that opens spaces for inclusion and politicisation that narrows them. Constructive politicising requires institutional reflexivity: mechanisms for dialogue, self-assessment, and accountability that ensure biodiversity governance remains oriented toward justice rather than instrumentalisation. Recognising this tension is key to sustaining trust and accountability in biodiversity governance.

The **T3.5** findings show that transformations leading to biodiversity recovery are inherently political. Participants viewed the SDGs as both a global opportunity and a structural constraint, a language that can mask inequalities even as it creates new spaces for contestation. The teams pointed to colonial legacies, economic hierarchies, and growth-oriented paradigms that continue to undermine ecological limits. Politicising biodiversity therefore means exposing these tensions and reclaiming the SDGs as instruments for negotiation rather than compliance. Several cases showed that local actors use SDG narratives to challenge centralised power, demand accountability, and steer governance toward fairness and ecological integrity. In this sense, politicising is not about rejecting the SDGs but about ensuring they serve justice rather than preserving the status quo.

10.4 Embedding

Embedding relates to integration of seeds for transformative change in the economy, governance and policy and social practice. Embedding takes place through e.g. upscaling of initiatives of local origin and establishing connections to key stakeholders and power structures across public, private and civil society sectors.

T3.1 asserts that embedding plays a central role in increasing the impact of biodiversity innovations. While many case studies are initiated and driven bottom-up, their long-term success depends on achieving embedding within both the local context and higher-impact sectors. This occurs through integration into legal frameworks across policy scales – i.e. when supported by European strategies, national laws, or locally implemented policy tools. Further, co-governance processes that include community actors in decision-making help ensure that innovations are embedded in local structures without losing sight of community needs and values often overlooked by higher-level policies. Niche innovators operating within institutional contexts can play a key role by bridging community perspectives and institutional dynamics, thereby promoting change from within. Amplifying and embedding biodiversity innovations also occurs through the exchange of successful practices and local initiatives in networks, particularly with policymakers across different contexts and scales. Ultimately, the processes with the greatest impact are those capable of influencing legal frameworks and policy design.

A few case studies also feature purpose-created organisational structures including multi-actor coalitions, which could – if they continue to evolve into important parts of the governance and institutional settings – potentially be(come) venues for embedding and institutionalisation.

Yet, many initiatives operate in relative isolation from formal policy frameworks and depend on the efforts of individuals and networks rather than institutionalised mechanisms. The short-term cycles of many initiatives likewise obstruct their embedding; the initiatives typically lack stable funding or integration into formal long-term plans. The case studies demonstrate examples of successful local experiments and innovation. For these initiatives to scale and diffuse, they need to navigate hurdles including bureaucratic inertia, institutional rigidity and limited visibility at higher levels.

T3.2 notes that, given the strong networking activities, emphasis on information and knowledge-oriented strategies, and diverse target groups in many case studies, their potential for embedding primarily lies in influencing values, social norms, and social practices. However, there are also examples where local initiatives have affected more formal, higher-level processes and gained recognition, suggesting growing acceptance of

alternative, non-business-as-usual models. A few case studies feature purpose-created organisational structures, including multi-actor coalitions, which – if they continue to evolve within pertinent governance and institutional settings – could (be)come important venues for embedding and institutionalisation.

Yet many initiatives still operate in relative isolation from formal policy frameworks, relying on the efforts of individuals and networks rather than institutionalised mechanisms. The short-term nature of many projects likewise hinders their embedding, as they often lack stable funding or formal integration into long-term plans. While the case studies provide examples of successful local experimentation and innovation, scaling and diffusion require overcoming hurdles such as bureaucratic inertia, institutional rigidity, and limited visibility at higher levels.

T3.3 interprets embedding as integrating biodiversity-positive approaches into everyday life—through views, structures, or practices. Embedding can involve institutionalisation, such as formalising a network or adopting a motion within it (e.g., the Södra forest owner organisation in the Swedish case). More often, however, embedding occurs more softly, through the strengthening of non-formalised networks and leveraging these to spread and anchor ideas. In such cases, the distinction between pluralising, politicising, and embedding may be unclear, depending on the case's emphasis. Moreover, strategies are often networked: an embedding strategy may be planned or executed in parallel or sequence with others targeting different PEPE principles. This nesting or co-unfolding of strategies was a recurring finding in the cross-case analysis. Cases beyond the early stage (focused mainly on trust building and creating encounters; see 'Pluralising') more often employed overarching strategies encompassing the full PEPE span.

T3.4 considers embedding transformative change as integrating regenerative principles into everyday life, linking policy ambitions with the lived realities of local actors and ecosystems. The cases show that transformation occurs not through isolated innovations but through the capacity to make regeneration part of daily practices in production, consumption, distribution, and care. Embedding also involves rethinking how economic and legal frameworks recognise territorial/geographical specificities, as biodiversity regeneration cannot flourish when policies treat local initiatives as deviations from standard models.

The case experiences from across Europe illustrate that embedding change depends on flexible regulatory environments, responsive rules for e.g. procurement, and funding mechanisms that align with the rhythms and scales of community-based practices. Translating biodiversity goals into concrete actions – such as farm-level experimentation, short food supply chains, or locally managed restoration projects – requires institutions to value continuity, trust, and long-term engagement. Embedding therefore calls for moving beyond project-based approaches toward policies that foster stability, relationality, and the regeneration of socio-ecological bonds.

T3.5 found that across the cases, participants showed that the interdependencies between the SDGs mirror the very idea of embedding: biodiversity conservation cannot stand apart but must be built into all areas of policy and practice. Rather than treating it as a separate environmental goal, participants called for strategies to weave biodiversity into the core of other SDGs, such as food security, water management, education, and social well-being. Embedding therefore means developing actionable ways to make biodiversity a part of these goals.

Annex A

Monitoring form questions

Excerpt from BIOTraCes WP2 – Case Study Monitoring Form, December 2024

Section 3 – Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes (WP3)					
<p>14. Can you identify top-down (institutional) biodiversity initiatives that a) could be considered opportunities for leverage, e.g. by challenging the business-as-usual? and b) that are blocking change (as perceived by the bottom-up initiatives)? If so, how? At what scales and by whom are these initiatives employed (local, regional, national, EU)? (task 3.1)</p>					
<p>Identify how institutional initiatives that enable or hinder leverage with a local and/or broader impact sector interact in your case study.</p>					
<p>15. Which strategies to achieve change are used by the actors (in the public, private and/or civil sector) in your case and what is the goal/desired change? Do they use one single strategy or a combination of several strategies? If several actors are involved, do their strategies differ, and in what ways? How and to what extent are the strategies influenced by relevant governance arrangements? (task 3.2)</p>					
<p>Provide a detailed response that describe strategies explaining more about this change, that can for example remove barriers, create leverage, upscale, develop discourse.</p>					
<p>16. In the table below indicate with a number from 1 (not relevant) to 5 (very relevant), to what extent are these participatory strategies relevant in your case study, and the social actors employing these strategies in interactions with others. (task 3.3)</p>					
Strategies	Actors employing these strategies				
	Societal partner	Researchers	Government	Business	Other
Learning					
Cocreation					
Consultation					

Dialogue					
Other					
17. Is governance, in your case study, attentive to possible environmental inequalities in the territory, and to what extent have these efforts positively impacted underrepresented and disadvantaged groups? (task 3.4)					
Explain the governance approach to environmental inequalities and how these efforts impact groups like indigenous people, Roma people, black communities, migrants and refugees, Muslim communities, minority women.					

Annex B

Interview guide Round 1

February 2025

BIOTraCes WP3 *Strategies and Approaches for Just and Transformative Changes*

Round 1 of interviews with the BIOTraCes case study teams

Interview guide

T3.1 *Opportunities for leverage and upscaling (Lead: BC3)*

What types of biodiversity innovations are present in the case (they may be directly linked to biodiversity or indirectly linked e.g., striving for food commons)?

In case there are different actors present in the case, are there different biodiversity innovations depending on the different types of actors?

Top-down initiatives in the local case study:

Can you identify top-down (institutional) biodiversity initiatives that could be considered opportunities for leverage, e.g. by challenging the business-as-usual? Are there opportunities for upscaling?

Can you identify top-down (institutional) biodiversity initiatives that are blocking change (as perceived by the bottom-up initiatives)? How?

At what scales are these initiatives employed (local, regional, national, EU, global)? By whom?

Bottom-up/ grassroots biodiversity innovations in the local case study:

Which biodiversity innovations in the case study can be considered an opportunity for leverage and why? Who are the actors (non-institutional) driving the initiative?

Are these initiatives unique to the local context/case study or do they reflect broader conditions or processes, i.e. beyond the local context? How do they connect to biodiversity challenges of the broader impact sector?

Can you already identify an upscaling of the biodiversity innovation? If yes, how is this happening? Which are the supportive factors and who are the driving actors of upscaling?

Barriers/lock-ins:

Which obstacles or barriers or lock-ins are present in your case study that prevent an upscaling? Which are the constraining factors and actors?

Are there differences in how the different actor groups frame those obstacles/barriers/lock-ins?

How are actors responding to those lock-ins? What would be needed from the different actor groups to better respond to those barriers?

T3.2 Strategies for public, private and civil society actors to initiate and accelerate transformative change (Lead: UGOT)

Who is in charge of developing/choosing the strategies that you have identified in the case study (vulnerable groups representation, sector/organisation?).

Who is supposed to be influenced or impacted by these strategies?

How would you characterise the strategies in terms of 'carrots' (economic incentives), 'sticks' (e.g. regulation) or information?

Are the strategies planned or do they evolve spontaneously?

How are the strategies implemented in terms of organisation and practical issues? (e.g. making contacts, work planning, timing of efforts etc)

T3.3 Strategies for learning, co-creation consultation (Lead: WR)

How does/did the societal partner employ participatory strategies to achieve its transformative goals? Give an example, indicating the stakeholders they involve. How did that play out? how does this strategy contribute to transformation?

How did this contribute to pluralising (perspectives, values, knowledges) and inclusion (marginalised or missing voices)?

How did this contribute to internal reflection, building internal capacity and self-empowerment?

How do researchers collaborate with stakeholders? Give an example. What was transformative about it? How did it play out?

What collaborative activities/ interventions/ forms of action research empowered societal partners and marginalised groups, and how?

Where was collaboration between researchers and societal partners more difficult? How did the parties deal with these difficulties?

To what extent is the policy/ governance context of the case study participatory? Give an example. Who were key actors in this? How did it play out?

How did it affect the agency of biodiversity innovators?

How accessible are participatory processes to non-expert stakeholders, considering factors such as language, framing, technical knowledge, and logistical barriers?

T3.4: Innovative thinking for just and effective governance (Lead: CES)

What measures are taken to ensure transparency with regard to decisions and policies related to biodiversity governance? Is the process of accountability more horizontal or vertical?

How does governance in your case deal with or mitigate power imbalances among different stakeholders?

Which underrepresented groups (Roma people, indigenous communities, migrants, racialised people) and vulnerable people (e.g. older people, children, youth, women) are taken into account by the local governance strategies in your case study?

How have the participation, the knowledge and perspectives of the community (=ordinary citizens, minorities included) been considered in biodiversity governance practices?

Annex C

Interview Guide Round 2

June 2025

BIOTraCes WP3 *Strategies and Approaches for Just and Transformative Changes*

Round 2 of interviews with the BIOTraCes case study teams (June-July-September 2025)

Interview guide

T3.1 *Opportunities for leverage and upscaling (Lead: BC3)*

Which of the four prototypes in the figure below best describes your case? Why? What are the barriers you encounter in your case study (e.g. those mentioned in the figure, or others)?

Where and how would you embed (i) the high impact sector, and (ii) broader civil society in the prototype relating to your case study? What is their role in relation to your biodiversity innovation?

Considering your prototype, where would you identify opportunities for upscale and leverage in your case study?

Who are the relevant top-down actors in your case study (at which policy scales are they)?

Top-down & bottom-up approaches

T3.2 Strategies for public, private and civil society actors to initiate and accelerate transformative change (Lead: UGOT)

So far, which are the **key outcomes/results/impacts** of the biodiversity innovation in your case study? How have the implemented **strategies contributed** to this, and how can you tell? Can you give an example?

What **unforeseen outcomes** have emerged, either positive (e.g. social cohesion) or negative (e.g. externalities/injustice)? Can you give an example?

If there are negative effects, how are these handled?

How has the implementation of **strategies changed over time** as the case study progresses? (e.g. depending on the development of the biodiversity innovation: initiation, establishment, acceleration...). Can you give an example?

If there have been changes, what are the triggers of this change? (e.g. new insights/learning; local support or resistance etc).

How have the **governance structures or institutional settings** (e.g. public/private/civil sector) of the case **influenced the choice of strategies and how these have played out**? Can you give an example?

T3.3 Strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation (interactive strategies) (Lead: WR)

In this interview round, we would like to better understand the transformative shifts that occurred as a result from the interactive strategies. We do that through the lens of 'opening up' – the opening of people's minds, plural values, social processes and (formal/economic) institutions toward propelling more biodiversity-inclusive outcomes.

How did the Social Partner and/or Research Partner achieve an **'opening up'** in the case? Who were involved? I.e.: who caused or initiated it, and who/what was opened up?

Was there a particular **transformative moment** that could be identified here?

Can you describe the **context** for that moment: a (strategic) decision, an (external) trigger, or other context/occasion factor?

After opening up, have there been steps (progress) towards **embedding or stabilising** the result of that 'opening'? Did that bring the case closer to transformation?

T3.4: Innovative thinking for just and effective governance (Lead: CES)

In your case study, how has the societal partner managed to consider different stakeholders' interests and needs? Who are these different stakeholders? Can you exemplify these competing needs?

In your case study, how has the societal partner given attention to vulnerable groups (children, youth, women, older persons, person with disabilities)?

Annex D

Workshop/focus group discussions at consortium meeting in Hungary, May 2025

T3.1

What are the **major root causes** of your case study which your biodiversity innovation is aiming to overcome? including **underlying causes, indirect drivers, direct drivers**

In already identified **opportunities for leverage**, are they **amplifying within, out, beyond**?

T3.2

To what extent do the **strategies used by the main stakeholders** to pursue their aims **support transformative change** towards increased biodiversity, together with equity and justice? Which are the **strengths and weaknesses**?

You can choose to focus the discussion on the strategic approaches as a whole, or specific strategies (or both).

Please give **examples** from your respective case studies.

T3.3

Did the social partner **challenge** and/or **disrupt**?

What does that mean?

Are pathways being weaved?

Did **dominant players** empower the societal partner?

How did the societal partner leverage this opportunity?

Did this interaction contribute to the legitimacy of the participatory process?

Please give **examples** from your respective case studies.

T3.4

What challenges do your societal partners encounter in involving **women in decision-making and co-governance activities**?

Can specific **contributions of women to biodiversity regeneration** be identified in your

case study? How are these contributions/knowledges recognised and supported?

Annex E

SDG Survey interface and content (research partners)

Interdependencies of SDGs Survey

Dear BIOTraCes team,

Why are we reaching out?

MRU team, along with UGOT, CER, BC3, and UBB, have developed a set of open and closed questions. These questions aim to explore the connections between the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and various aspects of biodiversity conservation in each case study.

How does this fit with the project plan?

Your responses will help us address **Task 3.5 Biodiversity Interdependencies of SDGs** (task duration M13-42), from **Work Package 3**. In this task, as outlined in our project proposal, we will use insights from all case studies to provide recommendations for policymakers.

What will be the result of this task?

Once we gather and summarize the responses from all case studies, we will produce the following outputs:

- Policy Brief on SDG Interdependencies (D3.5, due January 2025)
- Infographic on Biodiversity Interdependencies of SDGs (D3.6, due January 2025)
- Also, the Factsheet for Local Enterprises, including a set of SDG-based indicators

How does this task connect to other project deliverables?

The knowledge generated in this task will contribute to the completion of Deliverable D1.2.

Who should respond to the survey?

Each case study team should complete the survey collectively. Given the diversity within teams, we suggest you decide internally who is best suited to answer the questions. This could be the whole team or selected members, depending on your expertise and focus areas.

What is the final day for submitting survey responses?

11th November 2025

Final notes

Thank you for taking the time to contribute to this task. Your insights are important in shaping the project's outcomes and guiding efforts in biodiversity conservation and SDG interdependencies.

Annex F

SDG Survey interface and content (societal partners)

Interdependencies of SDGs Survey for Social partners

Dear social partner,

Why are we reaching out?

BIOTraCes team has developed a set of open and closed questions. These questions aim to explore the connections between the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and various aspects of biodiversity conservation in each case study.

How does this fit with the project plan?

Your responses will help us to achieve project's aims. We will use insights from all case studies to provide recommendations for policymakers.

What will be the result of this task?

Once we gather and summarize the responses from all case studies, we will produce the following outputs:

- Policy Brief on SDG Interdependencies
- Infographic on Biodiversity Interdependencies of SDGs
- Also, the Factsheet for Local Enterprises, including a set of SDG-based indicators

Who should respond to the survey?

Social partners of the case study are invited to participate in this survey.

What is the final day for submitting survey responses?

11th November 2025

Final notes

Thank you for taking the time to contribute to this task. Your insights are important in shaping the project's outcomes and guiding efforts in biodiversity conservation and SDG interdependencies.

* The name of your case:

* The name of your organisation:

Annex G

SDG survey: Example of graphical task visualisation

Please choose five or fewer SDGs relevant to your case study (previously selected in survey tool) and replace the general SDG icon with them. Remember: objects can be resized, deleted or altered in any other way, if needed.

Instructions

- Using the example above, a map of ideas, factors, entities, or other relevant indicators that link biodiversity and the SDGs in the case study should be created. Indicators can include anything considered important, such as political institutions, NGOs, communities, stories, governments, images, knowledge systems, historical artifacts, individuals, or non-human entities. These are just a few examples; there is flexibility to expand on them or introduce new (graphical or text-based) elements.
- An example of potential relationships between biodiversity and the SDGs is provided for inspiration. This example can be modified as needed—elements can be rearranged, and relationships, colors, forms, sizes, and fonts can be adjusted. Irrelevant items can be deleted, and new images, ideas, and structures can be introduced. The *Sandbox* can be easily resized by dragging the lower right corner of the white space.
- If relevant, a legend (explanatory notes or comments) could be introduced for the elements in the picture. For example, some links between elements may be direct, while others are indirect, so different types of arrows could be considered to connect them.
- Each case study in this project is at a different stage. Some partners have well-established relationships with their social and community stakeholders and have collected extensive data, while others are still forming these connections and beginning to gather data. We understand that these differences might influence how each team views the connections between biodiversity and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). What matters here is your team's current perspective on the potential relationships and factors involved in linking biodiversity to the SDGs, based on your knowledge of your case. Please feel free to share your team's unique viewpoint, regardless of the current stage of your project.